

Aminoferrocene- or ferrocenylaniline-based ROS amplifiers with anticancer activity

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Introduction

Cancer and its treatment

Influence of cancer: Cancer is a disease mainly caused by uncontrolled cell proliferation originally based on gene defects, leading either to a solid mass known as a tumor or to liquid cancer, i.e., blood or bone marrow-related cancer. Cancer has become a significant threat to human health, with its number of deaths comprising about one-sixth of deaths globally every year.¹ According to the latest cancer incidence and mortality data from the International Center for Cancer Research, about 1.93 million new cancer cases and about 10 million deaths worldwide in 2020. Compared with 2012, the number of new cases and deaths jumped by nearly 35% and 22%, respectively.²⁻³ Regarding costs, in the United States alone, the total cost of cancer care in 2020 is expected to reach 173 million USD.⁴ The global cancer situation is continuing to worsen. Improving cancer patients' curative and survival rates is a crucial challenge in cancer treatment.

Cancer treatment: Cancer treatment depends mainly on the type and origin of cancer, including surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy, hormone therapy, and targeted therapy (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Standard methods of cancer treatment.

Solid tumors that are non-metastatic and accessible, such as skin tumors, generally can be identified and removed by local excision. However, this method cannot be applied to diffuse cancers such as leukemia or most metastatic cancers in their advanced stages. Radiotherapy uses a specific radiation dosage to damage cancer cells and shrink tumors. It can treat about 45% of cancer cases, mainly including prostate, cervical, breast, and thyroid cancers, due to easy accessibility. A

drug treatment that applies cytotoxic agents to kill cancers is called chemotherapy. Chemotherapeutic drugs can reach cancers and kill fast-growing cancer cells. As this is mainly administered orally and intravenously, chemotherapy is the most common non-invasive cancer treatment. In addition, chemotherapy can be applied to all types of cancer with a highly successful curative rate. However, as it has more widespread applications, its severe adverse effects and drug-induced resistance are becoming increasingly frequent to hamper its application.⁵⁻⁶

Cancer cells, like healthy cells, need hormones to stimulate growth. Hormone therapy can block cancer cells from exposure to hormone signals with analogues of hormone signaling molecules, thereby stopping cell division. Clinically, hormone therapy is considered an adjuvant therapy because of its side effects and relatively few potential patients.⁷ Targeted therapy is the last and most advanced conventional cancer treatment. Some cancer cells can be identified by markers such as anaplastic lymphoma kinase (ALK) and B lymphocyte antigen CD20. This treatment can reduce the damage to surrounding tissues by using drugs that only target these markers. In addition to this therapy being relatively complicated and expensive, its long-term side effects are still unclear.⁸

Among all cancer treatment methods, chemotherapy is highly efficient and the most effective, resulting as the main one used in clinical applications. The primary study of this thesis is related to the development of small molecule anticancer prodrugs, which is a new chemotherapy-based cancer treatment. Therefore, the following paragraphs will focus on chemotherapy.

Chemotherapy: As mentioned above, cancer cells have a significantly faster proliferation rate than normal cells. Based on this difference, cytotoxic drugs used in chemotherapy can kill cancer cells by mainly interfering with cell division. In the 1940s, a type of cytotoxic molecules called nitrogen mustard were found could significantly reduce the incidence of lymphoma, which began the era of chemotherapy.⁹⁻¹⁰ Since that, the number of cancer patients receiving chemotherapy has considerably increased, as well as chemotherapeutic drugs.

Many different chemotherapy drugs are available. However, as for the mechanism of action, chemotherapeutic drugs are not that diverse. In brief, they can inhibit mitosis through DNA damage or interference, thus preventing rapid cell

proliferation. Specifically, chemotherapeutic drugs can generate electrophilic reagents to attack DNA, RNA, or proteins, inactivating these biological macromolecules and thus effectively inhibiting or killing cancer cells. There are mainly three types: antimetabolites, DNA interactive agents, and antitubulin agents (**Table 1**).¹¹

Table 1. Overview of typical chemotherapeutic agents

Group	Subtype	Representative cytotoxic agent
Antimetabolites	Pyrimidine analogues	5-fluorouracil, cytarabine, gemcitabine
	Purine analogues	Mercaptopurine, clofarabine, Methotrexate
DNA interactive agents	Alkylating agents	dacarbazine, temozolomide, procarbazine
	Cross-linking agents	platinum complexes, nitrogen mustards, nitrosurea
	Intercalating agents	aclarubicin, Mitoxantrone
	Topoisomerase I inhibitors	irinotecan, topotecan
	Topoisomerase II inhibitors	etoposide, teniposide
	DNA cleaving agents	bleomycin
Antitubulin agents	Taxanes	paclitaxel, docetaxel
	Vinca alkaloids	vincristine, vinblastine, vindesine
	Other antitubulin agents	ixabepilone

Chemotherapy side effects: Although chemotherapy is highly effective, it often results in medium or even severe side effects during clinical application. These side effects are induced by the fact that when most chemotherapeutic drugs target nucleic acids to kill rapidly growing cancer cells, they also inhibit or kill some kinds of healthy cells that divide at a similarly high speed, such as hair follicle, skin, digestive, immune, and hematopoietic stem cells (**Figure 2**). Clinical side effects mainly include alopecia, severe nausea and vomiting, poor immune functions, and hematopoietic dysfunction.¹²⁻¹³ Ideal cytotoxic drugs are expected to kill cancer cells rather than healthy cells, known as cancer-specific cytotoxic drugs, with selectivity between cancer cells and healthy cells.

Figure 2. Low selectivity of chemotherapeutic drugs that kill both cancer cells and rapidly growing healthy cells.

Chemoresistance: In addition to clinical side effects, as cytotoxic drugs are more frequently used, chemoresistance, the ability of cancer cells to evade or to cope with the presence of chemotherapeutic drugs, has continued to appear and attract attention. This is another leading cause of cancer treatment failure, leading to cancer's rapid recurrence or progression and, ultimately, death of patients.

During chemotherapy, the chemoresistance mechanism is caused by intrinsic and mainly acquired drug resistance (**Figure 3**, modified from reference)¹⁴. In some patients, primary cancer cells often cannot be recognized promptly thus proliferate during the first exponential phase due to their small size and asymptomatic characteristics. To some patients, a small number of specific cells can acquire intrinsic resistance from mutations during this stage. Later, when cancer is detected and chemotherapy is administered, most drug sensitive cells are quickly and continuously killed, leaving a small number of the above-mentioned intrinsic drug resistant cells due to their slow reproduction rate. After the first treatment, this small number of drug resistant cells boost the second exponential phase in the above group of patients. At this stage, cancer develops into a mixture of intrinsic and acquired drug resistant cells, together with some drug sensitive cells. When the same drug was reused, treatment efficacy dropped sharply due to mono drug resistance. As a result, either increasing the dosage of the previous medication or applying another cytotoxic drug with different mechanisms could optimize the situation, while this usually started another acquired drug resistance cycle. Eventually, multiple drug resistance appeared together with more severe side effects due to increased drug dosage.¹⁴

Figure 3. Mechanism of chemoresistance.

The intrinsic and acquired drug resistance mechanism mainly consists of mutations for molecular drug targets, alternation in drug-tumor interaction modes, and auto-modification for tumor microenvironments.¹⁵ All these facts demonstrate the need for diversified anticancer drugs with novel mechanisms. This has been the primary goal of anticancer medicinal chemists during the past several decades. Such drugs can avoid existing chemoresistance and increase the successful cancer treatment index.

Intracellular ROS generation and distribution

ROS generation: ROS are usually used to describe superoxide (O_2^-)-derived free radical molecules, such as singlet oxygen (1O_2), hydroxyl radical (OH^\bullet), superoxide anion ($O_2^{\bullet -}$), and superoxide anion-derived non-radical molecules, such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). Each oxygen atom contains two unpaired electrons in the outermost electron layer. Molecular oxygen obtains one electron to form superoxide anion ($O_2 + e^- \rightarrow O_2^{\bullet -}$) and then protonates to form hydrogen peroxide ($O_2^{\bullet -} + H^+ \rightarrow HO_2^{\bullet -}$; $2HO_2^{\bullet -} \rightarrow H_2O_2 + O_2$). Hydrogen peroxide can produce three electrons through a Fenton reaction ($Fe^{2+} + H_2O_2 \rightarrow Fe^{3+} + OH^\bullet + OH^-$), yielding a highly active hydroxyl radical (OH^\bullet).¹⁶

ROS bioactivity mainly involves two aspects: upmost, ROS active molecules at moderate physiological levels act as signaling molecules to mediate many physiological processes in cells. On the other hand, as a risk factor for multiple diseases, the absence of ROS can cause chronic granulomatous diseases while their

accumulation can perform from tumor-promoting effects to serious oxidative damage to biological macromolecules such as DNA, protein, and lipids, leading to cell death. One of the major sources for intracellular ROS comes from nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase. NADPH oxidase (NOX) can catalyze O_2 and NADPH to produce O_2^- . Subsequently, it gets converted into H_2O_2 by intracellular and extracellular superoxide dismutase (SOD), while the resulting H_2O_2 can further transform into oxidant hypochlorite (OCl^-) and HO^\bullet catalyzed by transition metals like myeloperoxidase (MPO) and Fe^{2+} (**Figure 4**).¹⁷ These enzymes were initially found in phagocytes, which they kill by producing high levels of local oxidative stress. Moreover, several subcellular structures in cells can generate ROS, e.g., mitochondria, endoplasmic reticulum (ER), lysosome, and plasma membrane, which will be explained as follows.

Figure 4. Simplified diagram to illustrate ROS reaction paths and effects on cells.

It has been confirmed that cancers' cellular ROS level was elevated compared to healthy cells, as their tumor microenvironment differs from healthy tissue. For instance, most cancer cells, either *in vitro* or *ex vivo*, release an enhanced amount of ROS. Therefore, their functions strongly rely on elevated ROS levels. For instance, the highest intracellular concentration of hydrogen peroxide for Jurkat cells was determined to be less than $7 \mu M$. In some cancer cells, this value was estimated to reach 10 to $100 \mu M$. In contrast, the intracellular concentration of hydrogen peroxide in healthy cells varied from 0.001 to $0.7 \mu M$.¹⁸

ROS in lysosome: Lysosome is an organelle for intracellular digestion and contains various acidic hydrolases. It has been demonstrated to produce ROS from digestive function simultaneously. Acidic hydrolases' optimal activity in lysosomes requires a suitably acidic environment. Therefore, lysosomes' proton concentration is far higher than that in the cytoplasm. Ubiquinone (UQ) is unevenly distributed in the cell membrane of subcellular structures. The UQ concentration in lysosomes is also

considerably enhanced. UQ in lysosomes may use the UQ cycle as an active proton transporter to maintain proton concentration in lysosomes. In this cycle, the benzoquinone ring in UQ is the molecule's active site, and oxygen is its final electron acceptor.¹⁶

ROS in mitochondria: As an 'energy factory', Mitochondria are energy-converting organelles in eukaryotic cells that supply the necessary energy for bioactivities through oxidative phosphorylation. The experimental data showed that 2–4% of oxygen was not reduced to produce water but converted to ROS during mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation electron transfer mechanism. Briefly, mitochondria are the main subcellular structure as intracellular ROS sources (**Figure 5A**, modified from reference).^{16, 19}

Figure 5. (A) Simplified figure illustrating the mitochondrial ROS metabolism and (B) the folding pathway of oxidized proteins in the endoplasmic reticulum.

ROS in ER: ER is an organelle for synthesizing intracellular biomacromolecules, including proteins, lipids, and carbohydrates. The enzyme molecules involved the catalytic synthesis of biomacromolecules in the ER related to ROS production. During protein biosynthesis, once immature proteins enter the ER, this is followed by the formation of disulfide bonds with help from enzymes. Afterwards, functional proteins are produced. The ER plays a unique role in providing an oxidative folding environment for protein disulfide bonds. Evidence shows that the protein oxidative folding process in the ER is closely correlated to ROS production. Protein oxidative folding is biocatalyzed by disulfide isomerase, which receives electrons from the sulfur residue of peptide substrate and is oxidized by oxidoreductin1 (ERO1). Eventually, ERO1 transfers electrons to molecular oxygen, becoming involved in the catalytic reaction again, leading to ROS formation (**Figure 5B**). O₂ is considered as the final electron acceptor in the formation of protein disulfide bonds. It has been predicted that roughly

25% of cellular ROS originates from the formation of disulfide bonds assisted by protein oxidative folding in the ER during protein synthesis.¹⁶

Ferrocene-based anticancer derivatives

Ferrocene: Throughout the development history of anticancer drugs, inorganic metal complexes such as cisplatin, carboplatin, and oxaliplatin have been dominant metal complexes.²⁰ The anticancer effect of organometallic complexes has also recently begun to attract attention, among which ferrocene derivatives must be mentioned.

After Kealy and Pauson first synthesized and identified ferrocene in the 1950s, many research groups have conducted in-depth studies on its structural properties and applications, especially its anticancer activity.²¹⁻²⁴ Ferrocene consists of a sandwich structure with an iron atom capped by two parallel cyclopentadienyl ligands. As the most well-known organometallic complex, ferrocene has many exciting features. First, the lipophilicity of ferrocene derivatives enables these compounds to easily pass through the cell membrane, thus interacting efficiently with enzymes, DNA, RNA, and other cellular targets, reflecting their potential as an effective drug. Secondly, the redox reversibility from iron enables these compounds to participate in metabolic processes with enzymes (**Figure 6A**). Third, as an electron-rich system, ferrocene's aromaticity makes it a suitable bioisostere for aromatic rings. Like simple aromatic rings, ferrocene tends to have substitution reactions. However, these reactions differ from typical aromatic compounds. Ferrocene's sandwich structure causes these molecules to have a certain thickness, preventing them from approaching the active pocket of specific enzymes and thus having selectivity. From another perspective, ferrocene can also more effectively fill the functional enzyme pocket, resulting in a stronger affinity to improved activity (**Figure 6B**, modified from reference).²⁴

Figure 6. (A) Ferrocene reversible oxidation chemistry and (B) ferrocene as a bioisostere that replaces aromatic moiety with filling hydrophobic pocket effectively.

In summary, its selectivity and affinity differ from ordinary aromatic systems, giving it the potential to result in different biological activities. Moreover, its intrinsically low toxicity is also a favorable factor for its role as a drug. Studies on free radical-related anticancer medicinal chemistry have shown that the redox property of ferrocene can cause Fe(II) to undergo a reversible redox reaction that forms a highly oxidizing Fe(III), which indicates Ferrocene derivatives have the potential to produce free radicals such as ROS, performing cytotoxicity.²⁵

Ferrocene-containing anticancer compounds: To the best of my knowledge, the successful clinical application of ferrocene derivatives is limited to ferrocerone (sodium ortho carboxybenzoylferrocene tetrahydrate). Compared with inorganic iron formulation, ferrocerone is used to treat anemia symptoms as its organic iron elements enable the human body to absorb it easily.²⁶⁻²⁷ As for its anti-cancer effects, several anticancer agents have been successfully modified as ferrocene analogues through bioisostere exchange, including suberoylanilide hydroxamic acid (SAHA, an FDA approved agent for T-cell lymphomas treatment) to Jay Amin hydroxamic acid (JAHA, an organometallic analogue of SAHA containing a ferrocenyl group as a phenyl bioisostere), and hydroxyl-tamoxifen (OH-TAM) to ferrocene-hydroxyl-tamoxifen hybrid (hydroxyl-ferrocifen, Fc-OH-TAM, **Figure 7**).²⁴ These compounds showed better anti-cancer activity than the parent drug, indicating their potential clinical application.

Figure 7. Representative conversion of anti-cancer molecules to analogues using ferrocene as a bioisostere.

Ferrocifen type compounds are the most famous ferrocene compound currently in their preclinical research stage. TAM is a selective estrogen receptor modulator (SERM) that has an anti-estrogen effect on breast tissue, reducing epithelial cell proliferation that contributes to its clinical application for metastatic breast cancer and ovarian cancer. For the first time, Gerard Jaouen's research group designed and

synthesized a class of anticancer ferrocene compounds with distinctive redox properties, which have become classic cases in pharmaceutical organometallic chemistry.²⁸ In clinical practice, TAM, as the first-line drug for anti-breast cancer treatment, is ineffective for triple-negative breast cancer. When the ferrocene group was introduced into OH-TAM to produce Fc-OH-TAM, it retained the inhibitory activity against positive breast cancer and showed promising inhibitory activity against triple-negative breast cancer. This finding shows great hope for improving the treatment situation of breast cancer, as triple-negative breast cancer accounts for about 10-20% of the total.²⁹

Mechanism studies revealed the critical difference: after ferrocene replaces the original benzene ring, a reversible redox property occurs between Fe (II) and Fe (III), with a potential of about 400 mV. Thus, cancer will suffer from generated ROS and benzoquinone methyl products spontaneously oxidized from phenol, which exhibit cytotoxicity to induce cell death (**Scheme 1**).^{24, 30} Therefore, ferrocifen type compounds showed outstanding activity against drug-sensitive and resistant cancer cells. The newly established company Feroscan continues to conduct a comprehensive preclinical evaluation of pharmacokinetics, toxicology, and clinical promotion of ferrocifen type compounds.

Scheme 1. Redox activation of ferrocifen type compounds proposed by Jauen et al.

Ferrocene serves as a redox site, forming a quinone methide following oxidation and proton abstraction, which nucleophiles readily attack at the positions indicated by red arrows.

ROS-responsive anticancer prodrugs:

Anticancer prodrugs: Roughly 10% of commercially available medicine worldwide are considered prodrugs. Under ideal conditions, anticancer prodrugs are originally non-toxic compounds. However, active drugs are released near and/or at the action site after chemical or enzymatic biotransformation. Adrien Albert first proposed the concept of prodrugs in 1958, and by analogy, this strategy can be likened to a 'Trojan horse'. Specific prodrugs can be obtained using carriers or components that cellular targets (membrane receptors or enzymes) recognize.³¹ If the premoieties (PM) is cancer-specific which will only be cleaved in cancer cells, this prodrug is considered a cancer-specific prodrug. This mechanism significantly improves therapy efficacy and reduces toxicity, thereby improving the tolerance of cancer patients and maximizing anticancer activity (**Figure 8**, modified from reference).³²

Figure 8. Strategy of cancer-specific prodrugs.

Anticancer prodrugs with ROS sensitive premoieties: As mentioned above, elevated ROS level occurs in cancer cells compared to normal cells. It is reasonable that this difference in ROS levels proposes to design of anticancer prodrugs. Since the first ROS-responsive prodrug (arylboronic ester as ROS trigger) was reported in 2010 by the Cohen group, such type of prodrugs has been investigated deeply for anti-cancer

therapy.³³ Various ROS-responsive mechanisms have been proposed for acquiring more prodrugs with promising anti-cancer effects. ROS-responsive anti-cancer prodrugs comprise anti-cancer drugs, ROS-responsive chemical bonds, and other functional fragments to cover drugs' original cell-killing effects. After responding to cancer-specific high levels of ROS in site, the cleavage of sensitive bonds will trigger a release of active drugs to achieve the purpose of efficiently killing cancer cells.

The main sensitive premoieties for designing ROS-responsive prodrugs were shown in **Figure 9**.³⁴⁻³⁶ The mechanism of the oxidative cleavage of ROS-sensitive bonds: The first reported ROS-responsive prodrug comprised of arylboronic acid/ester (including phenylboronic acid, phenylboronic acid ester, and coumarin borate ester), which first a coordination happened between ROS and boron atoms, followed by a Baeyer-Villiger-like oxidation that forms a boron-carbon bond to become borate and arylphenol. Such arylphenol further spontaneously cleaves to form quinone and release free drugs. For α -ketoamide, like arylboronic groups, ROS directly attacks α -carbonyl to initiate Baeyer-Villiger oxidation, followed by spontaneous 1,6-elimination and hydrolysis to obtain active drugs. Another group uses thiazolidinone to shield the carboxyl group. Thus, ROS first attacks and oxidizes thiazolidinone, followed by the hydrolysis of amide bond promotes releasing active drugs from the shielding group.

For prodrugs coupled by alkyl sulfide/selenide, ROS oxidizes hydrophobic divalent sulfur/selenium to yield hydrophilic tetravalent or hexavalent sulfur/selenium, after which prodrug containing sulfur/selenide can easily be hydrolyzed to release free drugs during phase transition. As for prodrugs formed by a thioketone conjugation, under ROS oxidation, thioketone bonds are easily oxidized and cleaved, followed by self-cleavage from produced thiols to release drugs. With peroxalate ester as premoiety, oxalate bond from prodrug was first oxidized by ROS to 1,2-diethoxydione that is quickly cleaved and self-decomposed to carbon dioxide with drugs released. ROS tends to oxidize the electron-rich olefins for the last type of prodrugs formed by aminoacrylate, followed by a [2+2] cycloaddition reaction to release drugs via self-cleavage.³⁴⁻³⁶

Figure 9. Overview of ROS-responsive prodrugs with their oxidation mechanisms.

Among the sensitive bonds employed in ROS-responsive prodrugs, arylboronic acid/ester, thiazolidinone, and α -ketoamide substitutions are mainly used to directly conjugate with the terminal groups from drugs (amino, hydroxyl, carboxyl, etc.) to shield the original activity and generate typical small molecule anticancer drugs. Among these premoieties, the arylboronic ester group is the most common one for designing prodrugs since it is relatively stable, easily prepared, and has moderate ROS responsive ability. Alkyl sulfide/selenide, thioketone, peroxyoxalate, and aminoacrylate groups commonly appear as connecting arms. In most cases, they are applied to covalently connect materials with different characteristics at both ends to design multifunctional polymer/nanoprodrugs rather than small molecules.³⁴

Aminoferrocene-based ROS amplifiers as anticancer prodrugs

Classic aminoferrocene-based prodrugs: The ROS-activated aminoferrocene prodrugs belong to the arylboronic ester type prodrug described above with their distinction from them. These prodrugs contain ROS responsive premoiety and ROS amplifier in one molecule. Therefore, this thesis first introduces traditional ROS-related cytotoxic agents before describing ROS-responsive aminoferrocene prodrugs. As described in the section about ROS-responsive prodrugs, cancer cells produce more ROS than healthy cells because cancer cells can only be well-functioned with an elevated ROS level. Therefore, agents that induce exogenous ROS or other free radicals have potential as anticancer drugs. Such compounds include arsenic trioxide, thiosulfimine, procarbazine, β -phenylethyl isothiocyanate, motexafin gadolinium, and salts containing ferrocenium. Due to their non-specific activities, these ROS amplifiers not only generate ROS to cancer cells but also healthy cells (**Figure 10**). Although in most cases, such active-mutational ROS level is not toxic enough to cause healthy cells to die, it is high enough to stimulate cells transformation to induce secondary cancers.^{18, 37}

Figure 10. Enhancing effects from (non-) specific ROS amplifiers in cancer and healthy cells.

Our group was the first one to propose the concept of ROS-responsive aminoferrocene prodrugs and consistently reported new prodrugs in this field. Briefly, a series of aminoferrocene prodrugs were prepared by combining ROS-sensitive phenylboronic acid ester with aminoferrocene by carbonamide link (**Scheme 2**). Under strong oxidizing conditions from elevated ROS that only exist in cancer cells, the carbon boron bond of boronic group was cleaved, turning the prodrug into two cytotoxic products. The first product from spontaneously 1,6-elimination was a quinone methide that acted as an antioxidant system inhibitor. Another product was a redox-active

aminoferrrocene species that can catalytically reduce molecular oxygen and hydrogen peroxide to highly active ROS like $O_2^{\cdot-}$ and HO^{\cdot} respectively. In addition, the lifetime of such aminoferrrocene species was confirmed relatively short while the decomposed products can release Fe^{2+} to perform a Fenton reaction, which also induces oxidative stress.^{18, 37}

The cytotoxic specificity of aminoferrrocene prodrugs (i. e. **N1**) has been proven between cancerous primary chronic lymphoid leukemia cells (CLL) and normal primary mononuclear (MNC) by viability tests.

Scheme 2. The activated mechanism for aminoferrrocene-based prodrugs and representative organelles targeted prodrugs.

Codrugs of aminoferrrocene prodrugs: Based on classic aminoferrrocene prodrugs, our group previously also tested the codrug concept for aminoferrrocene prodrug system, in which the typical one was coupling aminoferrrocene prodrugs with clinical approved chemotherapeutical Pt (IV) complex (**Fpt1** and **Fpt2**, **Scheme 3**) to form a three-component (aminoferrrocene-Pt-aminoferrrocene) codrug. After ROS activation, platinum drugs and aminoferrrocene ions were released to achieve a synergistic therapeutic effect. The results showed that these prodrugs had significant toxicity for ovarian cancer cells (A2780) and corresponding cisplatin-resistant cells (A2780cis). At the same time, there was almost no cytotoxicity for human fibroblasts (HDFa), which proved that prodrugs had low systemic toxicity.³⁸⁻³⁹

Scheme 3. Codrugs of aminoferrocene-based prodrug with Pt (IV) complex.

Lysosome-targeted aminoferrocene prodrugs: Lysosome-targeted prodrug is the most successful prodrug that our group has developed. For the lysosome-targeted strategy, we covalently conjugated the basic prodrug with alkylated piperidine fragments, which were protonated in the lysosomal acidic environment, resulting in prodrugs getting trapped and enriched, followed by cell death caused by elevated ROS damage (**Ly1**, **Scheme 2**). In cancer cells, intracellular H_2O_2 entered lysosomes mainly through diffusion, resulting in H_2O_2 accumulation. Meanwhile, these organelles have many loosely bound iron ions that can catalyze H_2O_2 to transform into highly toxic OH^\cdot . Therefore, the accumulation of prodrugs in lysosomes, together with less GSH concentration, increased ROS level, and more active ROS, create a beneficial inhibiting effect on cancer growth.⁴⁰

Contribution from the author of this thesis

It should be mentioned that the critical contribution involved in this thesis to the topic of aminoferrocene- or ferrocenylaniline-based ROS amplifiers in the first three papers will be explained below.

Optimized mitochondria-targeted aminoferrocene-based prodrugs

For paper 1: our group previously proposed the concept of 'ROS responsive groups protecting mitochondrial-targeted groups' (pro-DLCs). In this concept, ROS was used to connect the delocalized lipophilic cation *N*-alkylaminoferrocene, and these moieties mitochondria-targeted in cancer cells. Unfortunately, because mitochondria

are considered resistant organelles, these prodrugs may exhibit insufficiently high cell uptake, leading to their unsatisfactory anticancer effects.⁴¹⁻⁴²

In this thesis, these mitochondria-targeted prodrugs were chemically optimized and applied as radiotherapy sensitizers. It is applicable for prodrugs used as radiosensitizers to reduce side effects in radiotherapy if they only enhance the level of ROS inside cancer cells but not normal cells. However, the previously known ROS pro-amplifiers are not suitable to realize such a strategy. Since functional mitochondria are needed to resist radiotherapy, dual-functional prodrugs that can target mitochondria and induce ROS at the same time were expected as radiosensitizers. In this thesis, a series of such prodrugs (**Mit2-Mit5**) with high lipophilicity by linking the original prodrugs with the triazobenzene side chain were obtained to possess better cell uptake and anticancer activity (**Scheme 4**). After conducting a preliminary screening of cancer antiproliferation activity, we selected the prodrug (**Mit4**) effective at a low μM concentration for further investigation. The LC-MS-UV experiment proved that **Mit4** was almost entirely converted to a hydrolyzed form in an aqueous solution within atomic emission spectrometry (AES) measurement showed that it could have better uptake by cancer cells A2780 than its parent prodrug (**Mit1**). Inside the cell, it induced a decrease of mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP) and increased total cellular ROS as well as mitochondria ROS. In addition, compared with its parent drug, **Mit4** was proved an effective radiosensitizer in treating human head and neck squamous cancers *in vitro*.⁴³

Scheme 4. Optimized mitochondria-targeted aminoferrocene prodrugs as radiosensitizers.

Endoplasmic reticulum-targeted aminoferrocene-based prodrugs

For paper 2: ER stress refers to protein folding and output as well as unfolded protein hydrolysis imbalance in cancer cells' ER organelle. Bortezomib is the first FDA-approved proteasome inhibitor to treat malignant disease. Its anticancer mechanism involves multiple cellular targets, including inducing ER stress and generating ROS. However, the appearance of dose-limiting toxicities and drug-resistance hampers its widespread clinical use.

After successfully developing mitochondrial and lysosome-targeted aminoferrocene prodrugs, we recently chose ER stress as a starting point to create ER-targeted aminoferrocene prodrugs (**Figure 11**). Compared to Bortezomib, such prodrugs were expected to have less toxicity for normal cells, meaning fewer side effects. First, considering the LogP value and solubility, we decided to use bile acid residue as a carrier to target the ER as such hydrophobic moieties were commonly accumulated in ER. A series of bile acids and aminoferrocene covalence-linked prodrugs were synthesized. Then, the prodrug (**ER1**, **Scheme 2**) with a cholic acid side chain was chosen as the lead compound after the preliminary inhibitory screening of various cancer cell lines *in vitro*. Membrane potential experiments to multiple organelles indicated that **ER1** first accumulated in the ER and then began to affect mitochondria and lysosomes as the secondary effect.

Figure 11. Proposed anticancer mechanism of ER-targeted aminoferrocene prodrugs.

Meanwhile, the fluorescent prodrug (**ER2**) was also synthesized to prove its ER targeted function under confocal microscopy. For selectivity, its activation only in cancer cells (ovarian cancer A2780) but not in healthy cells (human fibroblast cells

SBLF9) was also confirmed by fluorescence microscope. The real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) test demonstrated that these prodrugs could induce ER stress by CCAAT-enhancer-binding protein homologous protein (CHOP). Finally, we confirmed that **ER2** could be successfully activated *in vivo* and retained its ER targeted function. These prodrugs can enrich the existing ER-targeted drug library, become a new mechanism of anticancer prodrugs, and are expected to produce lower side effects than other previous ER-targeted drugs.⁴⁴

Ferrocenylaniline-based ROS amplifiers as anticancer prodrugs

For paper 3: recently, we found that the stability of aminoferrocenyl products as a ROS amplifier was unsatisfactory due to their low stability. These amplifiers can produce Fe(II) or Fe(III) during rapid degradation, with certain toxicity for healthy cells. Therefore, a new class of ferrocene ROS amplifying agents was designed and synthesized, known as aniline ferrocenyl amplifying agents (**Scheme 5**). The ferrozine-Fe(II) coordination experiment showed that this amplification agent had better stability. Meanwhile, introducing one more benzene ring meant that the resulting high LogP value had been shown to prolong the hydrolysis of borate esters, which is expected to facilitate cancer cells' rapid absorption of original drugs (non-hydrolyzed). The expected rapid uptake and release of more stable amplification agents caused the prodrugs to have stronger *in vitro* anticancer activity than the original aminoferrocene prodrugs. However, their solubility also dropped sharply, which will limit its further investigation. Their *in vivo* activity and cancer cell specificity require further study.⁴⁵

Scheme 5. Activation pathways for aminoferroce- and ferrocenylaniline-based prodrugs.

In addition to the above critical contribution, the author of this thesis partially

contributed to the following two papers.

Stable aminoferrocene-based anticancer derivatives

For paper 4: while different kinds of aminoferrocene prodrugs had been developed as anticancer agents, they had similar drawbacks, including low activity or unsatisfying specificity that hamper their further application, e.g., **Ly1**. By chemically blocking the ROS responsive group, we obtained unusual aminoferrocene drugs (e.g., **Ly2**) to overcome these weaknesses.

Lacking a cleavable boronic ester ROS responsive premoiety, **Ly2** was chemically stable to resist H_2O_2 in the cell-free test. Its anticancer activity (IC_{50}) towards cancer cells, including A2780 cells, BL-2, and primary CLL cells, was comparable with the original prodrug **Ly1**. However, this drug possessed unusual specificity. Compared with **Ly1** that showed non-toxicity towards normal B-cells, T-cells, and SBLF9 fibroblasts, **Ly2** is still significantly toxic to B-cells. The mechanism studies revealed more differences like passive uptake for **Ly2** but energy dependent for **Ly1**; mROS generation by **Ly2** but not **Ly1**. In addition, partially oxidized to ferrocenium species was confirmed from a fluorogenic version of **Ly2**. To find out the potential of ferrocenium species will affect its anticancer activity or not, brominated analogue **Ly2_Br** with higher redox potential was synthesized, which ended up with identical anticancer efficacy. Taken all together, **Ly2** was supposed to exhibit its anticancer effect in neutral form (**Scheme 6**). Furthermore, we confirmed its anticancer effect *in vivo*, which differs from previous aminoferrocene prodrugs.⁴⁶

Scheme 6. Possible activation route (right) for aminoferrocene-based drugs containing F- moiety under oxidative conditions in cancer cells compared to (left) corresponding prodrug containing boronic ester moiety.

Non-toxic chemodosimeters for singlet oxygen detection

For paper 5: during photodynamic therapy (PDT) for cancer patients, singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$), a highly reactive molecule of ROS, performs as the critical oxidant. The known fluorogenic $^1\text{O}_2$ -probes have a drawback of consuming intracellular antioxidants to form cytotoxic side products like radicals during detection. To overcome this weakness, we synthesized a type of 9-anthracenyl fluorescein conjugates that were expected not to touch cellular antioxidants when detecting $^1\text{O}_2$. Take the basic probe **C4** as an example. After reacting with $^1\text{O}_2$, it first turned into endoperoxide **C4_O₂**. Next step, by its spontaneously decomposing, nontoxic stable 9,10-anthraquinone formed with fluorescent product **5** readily for fluorescence detection (**Scheme 7**).

Since intramolecular reductants came from the 10-C-H bond, no external electrons were needed for the next step. Thus, this mechanism ended up with no toxic side products. The cell-free activation of probe **C4** was confirmed by mass spectrometry, NMR spectrometry, and fluorescence spectrum. In addition, fluorescence microscopy experiments confirmed its cellular activation in A2780 cells. Based on this probe, we prepared several other probes with modification on its fluorescein fragment from electron-rich to electron-withdraw groups or the introduction of an extra phenyl group to explore the structure-activity relationship. Eventually, the non-toxic advantage was proved by testing such probes in human leukemia cells (HL-60).⁴⁷

Scheme 7. The mechanism of new $^1\text{O}_2$ activated fluorogenic chemodosimeters **C4**.

Co-authored contributions to the publications

Paper 1. Intracellular amplifiers of reactive oxygen species affecting mitochondria as radiosensitizers. *Cancers*, 2022, 14(1), 208.

Contribution:

Hong-Gui Xu: scale up of prodrugs, synthesis of drugs **2c_c**, **3** and **4**, solubility and LogP determinations, cell free tests and cellular experiments on A2780, BL-2 and SBLF9, data processing, figure design, writing the paper and final corrections.

Viktor Reshetnikov and Steffen Daum: synthesis of prodrugs **2a** to **2d**.

Marit Wondrak, Lisa Eckhardt, and Leoni A. Kunz-Schughart: radiotherapy cell experiments.

Christina Janko, Rainer Tietze, and Christoph Alexiou: experiments on Jurkat cells.

Hannes Borchardt and Achim Aigner: experiments on AsPC1 cells

Wenjie Gong, Michael Schmitt, and Leopold Sellner: experiments on primary cells.

Hülya Gizem Özkan: advice on design of drug **2c_c**.

Andriy Mokhir: project leader, proposing the idea, creating the first draft, and finalizing the manuscript.

Paper 2. An endoplasmic reticulum specific pro-amplifier of reactive oxygen species in cancer cells. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 2021, 60(20), 11158-11162.

Contribution:

Hong-Gui Xu: synthesis of prodrugs **4a**, **4f** and **4g**, solubility and LogP determinations, cell free tests and cellular experiments on A2780 and BL-2, data processing, figure design, writing the paper and final corrections.

Margot Schikora and Miroslav Sisa: synthesis of prodrugs **4b** to **4e**.

Steffen Daum: advice on the synthesis of intermediate **S3**.

Insa Klemt: confocal microscopy, qPCR assay and cellular experiments on SBLF9.

Christina Janko and Christoph Alexiou: experiments on Jurkat cells.

Galyna Bila and Rostyslav Bilyy: in vivo experiments.

Wenjie Gong, Michael Schmitt, and Leopold Sellner: experiments on primary cells.

Andriy Mokhir: project leader, proposing the idea, creating the first draft, and finalizing the manuscript.

Paper 3. 4-Ferrocenylaniline-based ROS-responsive prodrugs with anticancer activity. *Journal of Organometallic Chemistry*, 2022, 964, 122305.

Contribution:

Hong-Gui Xu: synthesis of amino-Fc, cell free tests and cellular experiments, data processing, figure design, writing the paper and final corrections.

Saparmyrat Annamadov: synthesis of prodrugs, LogP and solubility determinations.

Andriy Mokhir: project leader, proposing the idea, creating the first draft, and finalizing the manuscript.

Paper 4. Stable aminoferrocene derivatives inducing production of mitochondrial reactive oxygen species in cancer cells (*Chemistry - A European Journal*, accepted).

Contribution:

Hülya Gizem Özkan and Vanrajsinh Thakor: Most synthesis, cell free tests and cell experiments.

Hong-Gui Xu: synthesis of **3d_Br** and corresponding CV, LogP, ROS generation in cell free and MTT tests, data processing, writing the paper and final corrections.

Galyna Bila and Rostyslav Bilyy: in vivo experiments.

Daria Bida: UV-visible spectroscopy.

Martin Böttcher, Dimitrios Mouggiakakos, and Rainer Tietze: atomic emission spectrometry.

Andriy Mokhir: project leader, proposing the idea, creating the first draft, and finalizing the manuscript.

Paper 5. Hybrids of a 9-anthracenyl moiety and fluorescein as chemodosimeters for the detection of singlet oxygen in live cells. *Organic & Biomolecular Chemistry*, 2019, 17(46), 9883-9891.

Contribution:

Serghei Chercheja and Steffen Daum: synthesis, cell free tests and cellular experiments.

Hong-Gui Xu: scale up of probe **4**, fluorescence microscopy and NMR spectroscopic monitoring.

Frank Beierlein: DFT calculation.

Andriy Mokhir: project leader, proposing the idea, creating the first draft, and finalizing the manuscript.

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Article

Intracellular Amplifiers of Reactive Oxygen Species Affecting Mitochondria as Radiosensitizers

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Simple Summary: Prodrugs that increase the level of reactive oxygen species (ROS) specifically in cancer cells while not affecting normal cells can potentially act as radiosensitizers for side effect free radiotherapy (RT). However, previously known ROS-amplifying prodrugs were found to not be useful for this purpose. Since functional mitochondria are necessary for RT-resistance, we assumed that the problem could be solved by using dual prodrugs as radiosensitizers, both targeting mitochondria and simultaneously inducing ROS. In this paper, we explored this possibility. In particular, we developed an *N*-alkylaminoferrocene-based prodrug (2c) effective at low μ Molar concentrations. Upon conversion to its active form 2c_BA in aqueous solution, it is efficiently taken up by cancer cells. This leads to the decrease of their mitochondrial membrane potential and the amplification of both, intracellular mitochondrial and total ROS generation. We found that 2c_BA acts as an efficient radiosensitizer in human head and neck squamous carcinoma cells in vitro.

Abstract: Radiotherapy (RT) efficacy can be improved by using radiosensitizers, i.e., drugs enhancing the effect of ionizing radiation (IR). One of the side effects of RT includes damage of normal tissue in close proximity to the treated tumor. This problem can be solved by applying cancer specific radiosensitizers. *N*-Alkylaminoferrocene-based (NAAF) prodrugs produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cancer cells, but not in normal cells. Therefore, they can potentially act as cancer specific radiosensitizers. However, early NAAF prodrugs did not exhibit this property. Since functional mitochondria are important for RT resistance, we assumed that NAAF prodrugs affecting mitochondria in parallel with increasing intracellular ROS can potentially exhibit synergy with RT. We applied sequential Cu⁺-catalyzed alkyne-azide cycloadditions (CuAAC) to obtain a series of NAAF derivatives with the goal of improving anticancer efficacies over already existing compounds. One of the obtained prodrugs (2c) exhibited high anticancer activity with IC₅₀ values in the range of 5–7.1 μ M in human ovarian carcinoma, Burkitt's lymphoma, pancreatic carcinoma and T-cell leukemia cells retained

moderate water solubility and showed cancer specificity. 2c strongly affects mitochondria of cancer cells, leading to the amplification of mitochondrial and total ROS production and thus causing cell death via necrosis and apoptosis. We observed that 2c acts as a radiosensitizer in human head and neck squamous carcinoma cells. This is the first demonstration of a synergy between the radiotherapy and NAAF-based ROS amplifiers.

Keywords: *N*-alkylaminoferrocene; cancer; mitochondrion; reactive oxygen species; prodrug; radiotherapy

1. Introduction

Radiotherapy (RT) using ionizing radiation (IR) is a common approach for the treatment of cancer [1,2]. It allows exclusively irradiating tumor areas, while sparing most of the body from the therapy-based toxicity. However, despite technological advances in 3D conformal radiation [3], the damage of the normal tissues located close to the tumor can still occur and may lead to side effects and the evolvement of RT-resistant cancer cells [4]. The former effect limits the power (dose) of the IR applicable in the treatment, whereas the latter decreases the success rate of repetitive therapy cycles. One possibility for the potentiation of RT includes its combination with radiosensitizers: chemotherapeutic drugs capable of enhancing anticancer effects of the IR, e.g., cisplatin, gemcitabine, 5-fluorouracil (5FU) or PARP inhibitors, e.g., veliparib [5–8]. The mechanism of their action relies either on the interaction with genomic DNA or the modulation of DNA metabolism. An alternative approach is based on the IR potentiation by drugs increasing intracellular levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS), e.g., sorafenib [9], L-S-buthionine (BSO) [10], As₂O₃ [11], diisopropylamine dichloroacetate (DADA) [12] and ferrocene derivatives [13,14]. However, despite their high antitumor efficacy, these drugs also affect healthy tissues and cells, which so far precludes potential clinical applications of RT approaches based on ROS-regulation. A promising strategy towards solving this problem could be the use of cancer-targeted prodrugs as radiosensitizers, which are activated only under tumor cell-specific conditions [15]. For example, cancer cells have the higher level of ROS, whereas the level of ROS in normal cells at homeostatic conditions is negligible [16–18]. Known ROS activated prodrugs include *N*-alkylaminoferrocene-based (NAAF)-prodrugs [18–29], pro-DNA alkylators [30,31], hydroxyferrocifens and their analogues [32,33], organochalcogen-based redox catalysts [34] and oligoferrocenes [35]. Unexpectedly, we have found that early NAAF prodrugs [18,19,21] exhibit no radiosensitizing effects (unpublished results) indicating that the intracellular ROS amplification alone is not sufficient to achieve the synergy with RT. Since functional mitochondria are crucially important for radioresistance [36], we hypothesized that NAAF prodrugs, which affect mitochondria of cancer cells additionally to the intracellular ROS amplification, could exhibit radiosensitizing properties. Though mitochondria in cancer cells are deficient and have abnormal membrane potential (MMP, $\Delta\Psi_m = 130\text{--}150\text{ mV}$ [37]), they still fulfill crucial for cancer cells functions including synthesis of nucleosides and ATP and play an important role in gene expression [38]. Therefore, many mitochondria targeting low molecular weight compounds [39,40] as well as nano-systems [41,42] are currently intensely explored as anticancer drugs. Unfortunately, no potent mitochondria-targeting NAAF prodrug was available for testing this hypothesis. In particular, although we have previously demonstrated that prodrug 1 (Figure 1) and its fluorogenic derivatives moderately affect mitochondria of cancer cells [25,28], their anticancer efficacy is very low [25].

Figure 1. (A) Structures of the known prodrug 1 [21,24], its derivatives 2a-d and hydrolyzed at pH 7.4 forms of the prodrugs (1_BA, 2a_d_BA) as well as control 2c_c. (B) Structures of representative NAAF drugs 3 and 4 as well as reference compounds used in this work.

One of the goals of this work was to obtain analogues of 1 with improved anticancer efficacy. This can be achieved by increasing lipophilicity of 1, ideally leading to enhanced passive uptake by cancer cells and increased anticancer efficacy [19,21,24]. However, compounds that are too lipophilic exhibit low solubility in aqueous buffers and are prone to formation of aggregates, which are not cell membrane permeable [24]. It should be possible to find a fine balance between increased lipophilicity and decreased water solubility by preparing focused libraries of prodrugs, where their properties are gradually altered in small steps. However, synthetic possibilities for chemical modification of NAAF prodrugs are restricted by oxidative instability of B-C bonds. For example, we have previously observed that single conjugations of carboxylic acid groups with amino groups in the presence of activating agents based on uronium salts or carbodiimides and Cu⁺-catalyzed alkyne-azide cycloadditions (CuAAC's), conducted in aqueous buffers using Cu²⁺ salts as catalyst precursors, lead to complex product mixtures when conducted with the B-C bond containing derivatives. The problems become more severe when sequential reactions for the attachment of same or different chemical moieties are attempted. In particular, when the product yield in a single reaction is “y” (in %), the yield in the sequential reaction with N steps will be $y^N/100$: e.g., for $y = 60\%$ and $N = 2$, $y^N/100 = 36\%$. Correspondingly, the number of side products will be higher in the sequential reactions. Sequential “click” reactions have not yet been used for synthesis of NAAF prodrugs. Recently, we have found conditions for a CuAAC reaction in non-aqueous buffers compatible with compounds containing B-C bonds. Using the single CuAAC, we have already prepared a series of conjugates of NAAF prodrugs with fluorescent dyes [22,25,28,29] and radio-tracers [27,43]. Here we applied both single (prodrugs 2a, 2b) and, for the first time, double sequential CuAAC reactions (prodrugs 2c, 2d) to generate a small library of derivatives of NAAF prodrug 1 (Figure 1). One of the compounds in this library (2c) turned out to be a substantially more potent mitochondria-targeted and ROS-amplifying prodrug than 1. On the example of 2c, we confirmed for the first time that NAAF prodrugs exhibit radiosensitizing properties *in vitro*. Furthermore, we obtained important new insights on the mechanism of action of mitochondria-targeted NAAF prodrugs.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. General

Commercially available chemicals of the best quality from Sigma–Aldrich (Schnelldorf, Germany) were obtained and used without purification. Golgi-Staining-Green (BODIPY FL C5-ceramide complexed to BSA, catalog: B22650, Invitrogen™) and ER-Tracker-Green (BODIPY™ FL Glibenclamide, catalog: E34251, Invitrogen™) were obtained from ThermoFisher Scientific (Freiburg im Breisgau, Germany). NMR spectra were acquired on a Bruker Avance 300 or a Bruker Avance 400 spectrometer. Electrospray ionization (ESI) or atmospheric pressure photoionization (APPI) mass spectra were recorded on a Bruker ESI MicroTOF II focus or a Bruker maXis 4G. Elemental analysis (C, H and N) was performed in the microanalytical laboratory of the chemical institutes of the Friedrich Alexander University of Erlangen-Nürnberg, Erlangen, Germany. UV-visible spectra were measured on a Cary 100 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies, Frankfurt am Main, Germany) by using quartz glass cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Müllheim, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL. Fluorescence spectra were acquired on a Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer using fluorescence cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL. The fluorescence of live cells was quantified using a Guava easyCyte™ 6-2L flow cytometer from Merck Millipore (Darmstadt, Germany) or CytoFlex flow cytometer from Beckman Coulter, Inc. (Fullerton, CA, USA). The data were processed using MS Excel. The microscopy images were taken with a Zeiss Axio Vert.A1 microscope. For dynamic light scattering measurements, a Zetasizer Nano series ZEN3600 (Malvern Instruments) with a 633 nm He-Ne laser was used with polystyrene cuvettes with a sample volume of 1000 µL (BRAND GmbH, Wertheim, Germany). The purity of the prodrugs used in the biological assays was determined by elemental analysis (C, H and N analysis). According to these data, the purity was greater than 95%.

2.2. Synthesis of Prodrugs and Their Characterization in Cell Free Settings

Previously known prodrugs 1 [23], 5a [18], 5b [22] and 5c [28] (main text, Figure 1) and intermediates S1 [24] and S2 [28] were synthesized as described elsewhere. The synthesis of prodrugs 2a–2d and their characterization (Figures S1–S42, SI (supporting information)) as well as protocols for the determination of n-octanol/water partition coefficients (logP), solubility of the prodrugs and prodrug-induced generation of ROS in cell free settings are described in the supporting information (SI).

2.3. Cells, Cell Culture and Cellular Assays

The human ovarian cancer cell line A2780 was purchased from Sigma–Aldrich. The Burkitt lymphoma cell line BL-2 and T-cell leukemia cell line Jurkat were obtained from DSMZ (Germany). SBLF9 fibroblasts were obtained from the group of PD Dr. B. Frey, Chair of Radiation Therapy, University Hospital Erlangen. The human pancreatic cancer cell line AsPC1 was obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA). The human head and neck squamous cell carcinoma cell line SAS was obtained from the HSRRB (Japan), while FaDu cells represent a subline of FaDu-ATCC HTB-43 cells as described previously [44]. The above cell lines were cultivated following standard protocols from ECACC (93112519), DSMZ (ACC 625), ATCC (HTB-81) and Coriell. Suspension cells were grown to $(0.5–1.5) \times 10^6$ cells/mL and diluted as required. Adherent cells were cultivated to around 80% confluence. Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of cells, MMP, staining of cellular organelles (lysosomes, endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi), cell cycle, total and mitochondrial ROS, intracellular amount of glutathione and description of the study of synergistic effects of prodrug 2c and the ionizing irradiation are described in the SI.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Possible Reasons of Poor Anticancer Activity of Drug 1

To understand why prodrug 1 exhibits weak anticancer activity, we investigated its basic properties in cell free settings. First, we determined its n-octanol/water partition

coefficient (logP) to evaluate the lipophilicity of 1 and its hydrolyzed form 1_BA. The latter compound is formed in aqueous neutral solution of 1 within <2 h. Analogously to other known NAAF-prodrugs [27], the hydrolyzed form is responsible for the biological activity of the prodrug. We found that 1 (logP = 4.87 ± 0.05) and especially 1_BA (logP = 2.83 ± 0.07) show moderate lipophilicity. We have previously observed that some lipophilic NAAF-prodrugs, e.g., 4-(*N*-ferrocenyl-*N*-benzylaminocarbonyloxymethyl)-phenylboronic acid pinacol ester [18,19,21,24], exhibit low reactivity towards ROS due to the formation of aggregates in aqueous solution, where the reactive arylboronic acid (BA) groups are not accessible to ROS. However, this was not the case for prodrug 1. For example, we observed that 1 reacts quickly with H₂O₂ in cell free settings, under formation of the corresponding NAAF, which catalyzes the generation of HO• from H₂O₂. The activity of 1 in the latter reaction was found to be identical to that of the positive control FeSO₄ (Table 1). Thus, in cell free settings, 1 behaves as a very efficient NAAF-prodrug.

Table 1. Selected properties of the prepared prodrugs and the control 1.

Prodrug	logP (Prodrug/Hydrolyzed Prodrug) ⁱ	Solubility ⁱⁱ	ROS Release Efficacy ^{iv}
1	$4.87 \pm 0.05/2.83 \pm 0.07$	67 ± 5 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.99 ± 0.16
2a	$5.27 \pm 0.10/2.92 \pm 0.14$	100 (30)	0.74 ± 0.19
2b	$5.37 \pm 0.10/3.10 \pm 0.12$	100 (30)	0.76 ± 0.19
2c	$5.37 \pm 0.15/3.23 \pm 0.11$	30 (10)	0.35 ± 0.17
2c_c	3.90 ± 0.08	55 ± 5	0.050 ± 0.003
2d	$5.56 \pm 0.14/3.42 \pm 0.14$	30 (10)	0.37 ± 0.13

ⁱ logP: n-octanol/water partition coefficient of the prodrugs and their hydrolyzed forms. Control 2c_c does not have a boronic acid residue, therefore, only one value is shown in the corresponding section of the table.

ⁱⁱ Solubility of the prodrugs after their incubation for 48 h in Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 medium (Biochrom GmbH, Berlin, Germany) supplemented with fetal bovine serum (FBS, 5%), L-glutamine (1%) Penicillin/Streptomycin (1%, Biochrom GmbH, Germany) and containing dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO, 1%, v/v) (SI). The numbers in the brackets correspond to prodrug concentrations leading to aggregate formation (48 h incubation) determined by dynamic light scattering (SI). ⁱⁱⁱ Solubility of prodrug 1 in Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 medium (Biochrom GmbH, Germany) supplemented with fetal bovine serum (FBS, 5%), L-glutamine (1%) Penicillin/Streptomycin (1%, Biochrom GmbH, Germany) and containing dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO, 1%, v/v) was determined as described previously [29]. ^{iv} ROS release efficacy, expressed as relative acceleration of the rate of fluorescence increase ($\lambda_{ex} = 501$ nm, $\lambda_{em} = 523$ nm) in the mixture of 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein (DCFH) and H₂O₂ in aqueous solution buffered at pH 7.4. The ROS release efficacy for a background reaction (no prodrug added) is 0.04 ± 0.02 , in the presence of ferrocene (negative control) -0.06 ± 0.02 , in the presence of drug 3 (derived from prodrug 2a) -0.80 ± 0.19 . The ROS release efficacy in the presence of FeSO₄ was used as a reference: 1.0. Representative original data and detailed experimental conditions are provided in the SI.

Previously, we determined that the efficacy of cellular uptake of prodrug 1 in A2780 cells is ca. 50% of that of the reference NAAF prodrug 4-(*N*-ferrocenyl-*N*-benzylaminocarbonyloxymethyl)-phenylboronic acid pinacol ester [25]. We confirmed the inefficient uptake of 1 by monitoring the increase of both boron and iron amounts in A2780 cells incubated with prodrug 1 by using atomic emission spectrometry (Table S1, SI). Thus, the low anticancer activity of 1 can at least partially be explained by the insufficient prodrug uptake.

3.2. Design, Synthesis and Characterization of the Prodrugs

We prepared a series of analogues of prodrug 1 with substituents of gradually increasing lipophilicity that was expected to improve the passive prodrug uptake. In particular, we replaced a long chain *N*-alkyl substituent in 1 (ClogP = 2.83) with substituents R': benzyl (ClogP = 2.64, 2a), 2-phenylethyl (ClogP = 3.17, 2b), 4-((4-benzyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)methyl)benzyl (ClogP = 3.57, 2c) and 2-(4-((4-benzyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)methyl)phenyl)ethyl (ClogP = 3.95, 2d) (Figure 1). Specifically, 4-(*N*-ferrocenyl-*N*-propargylaminocarbonyloxymethyl)phenylboronic acid pinacol ester (compound S1, SI) was coupled to the corresponding organic azide derivatives under the conditions of the CuAAC reaction as described in detail in the SI. After chromatographic purification, all isolated products 2a–2d were of >95% purity according to the C, H, N-elemental analysis. We also prepared 2c_c, where the ROS-responsive moiety –B(OH)₂ was replaced with a

fragment $-C(O)NMe_2$ (SI). This compound was used as a control, which does not react with ROS as a typical NAAF prodrug.

One of the prodrugs (2a) could be obtained in the crystalline form. We determined its crystal structure by X-ray crystallography (left structure, Figure 2), which confirmed the expected atom connectivity.

Figure 2. Comparison of the molecular structures of prodrug 2a (left structure) and previously published 4-(*N*-ferrocenyl-*N*-propargylaminocarbonyloxymethyl)phenylboronic acid *N,N*-diethanolamine ester (right structure [27]).

We found that hydrogen atoms H1a and H1b of the methylene group are directed towards the ferrocenyl moiety in the crystal structure of 2a. This is reflected in relatively short H1a–Fe (3.27 Å) and H1b–Fe (4.34 Å) distances, which, however, are close to or longer than the sum of van der Waals radii of hydrogen and iron atoms (3.06–3.39 Å [45]). Therefore, no strong intramolecular interactions can be assumed in this case and the realization of this conformation is probably governed by crystal packing effects. In contrast, in the previously reported structure of the related NAAF prodrug 4-(*N*-ferrocenyl-*N*-propargylamino-carbonyloxymethyl)phenylboronic acid *N,N*-diethanolamine ester (right structure, Figure 2) the methylene group is oriented away from the ferrocenyl moiety, leading to greater H1a–Fe (4.29 Å) and H1b–Fe (4.93 Å) distances [27].

3.3. Stability and Solubility of Prodrugs 2a–2d in the Aqueous Neutral Solution and Their Lipophilicity

To identify the active form of prodrugs 2a–2d in aqueous neutral buffers, we investigated their stability in the water rich solvent mixture containing triethylammonium acetate buffer (pH 7.0, 1.5 mM) and CH_3CN (7/3, *v/v*). We observed that even freshly prepared solutions of analytically pure samples of 2a–2d (peaks eluted at 10.2–10.7 min) contain hydrolyzed species corresponding to boronic acid derivatives 2a_BA–2d_BA (peaks eluted at 7.1–7.5 min, 7–14% of the area of all peaks) (Figure S43, SI). After 2 h incubation of these samples, the peaks of 2a_BA–2d_BA become major ones (79–87% of the area of all peaks, Figure S43, SI). These data indicate that to analogously control 1 and the majority of other known NAAF-based prodrugs [27] the active forms of 2a–2d prodrugs are their boronic acid derivatives.

Next, we determined lipophilicity of the prodrugs and their BA-forms as described in the SI. We observed that lipophilicity is gradually increased in the series of the prepared prodrugs and their BA-derivatives, as compared to the parent prodrug 1 and its BA-derivative 1_BA, respectively (Table 1). This result was expected based on the CLogP values of the introduced substituents (see the previous section for the discussion on prodrug design principles).

To estimate solubility of the prodrugs, we diluted their stock solutions in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) 100-fold with Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 medium (Biochrom GmbH, Germany), supplemented with fetal bovine serum (FBS, 5%), L-glutamine (1%) and penicillin/streptomycin (1%, Biochrom GmbH, Germany). The latter medium was selected, since we used it for the cellular assays. The samples were monitored by bright field optical microscopy immediately and 48 h after the dilution. We observed first signs of precipitation at 50 μM for 2a and 2b and at 30 μM for 2c, 2d (Figure S44, SI). The prolonged incubation (48 h) of the prodrugs in the medium improved the solubility of 2a and 2b (first signs of precipitation observed at 100 μM), but not of 2c and 2d (Figure S44, SI). Then we monitored the formation of (not detectable in the previous experiment) aggregated species in prodrug solutions that appeared transparent (concentrations < 50 μM) by using dynamic light scattering. We found that prodrugs 2a and 2b form aggregates at concentrations above 30 μM , whereas in the case of prodrugs 2c and 2d, aggregate formation starts already at concentrations above 10 μM (Figure S45, SI).

3.4. Generation of ROS in the Presence of the Prodrugs in Cell Free Settings

As previously reported [18–22], the NAAF-prodrugs react with ROS like H_2O_2 , first leading to the cleavage of the B-C-bond with the formation of the phenol derivatives (product 2c-1, Figure S49, SI). The latter compounds exist in equilibrium with the corresponding phenolates. The phenolates undergo the spontaneous 1,6-elimination of para-quinone methide (QM) followed by the release of CO_2 with the formation of the *N*-alkylaminoferrocene NAAF drugs (product 2c-2, Figure S46, SI). By using electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS), we confirmed for one representative prodrug 2c that it reacts with H_2O_2 in cell free settings according to this common mechanism (ESI-MS, Figures S46–S48, SI). The NAAF is further oxidized by H_2O_2 or molecular oxygen with the generation of drug NAAF⁺ and highly toxic HO• or/and $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$. Finally, the NAAF⁺ is reduced by glutathione (GSH), thereby closing the catalytic cycle, in which the NAAF acts as a catalyst. We evaluated the formation of HO• or/and $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$ by using 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein (DCFH) as a probe (Table 1, Figure S49, SI). This probe is oxidized to the fluorescent product 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein (DCF) in the presence of HO• or/and $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$. In particular, we found that NAAF drugs 3 (derived from the representative prodrug 2a) and 4 as well as prodrugs 2a and 2b exhibit similar catalytic efficacy in the conversion of H_2O_2 to HO• (Student's *t*-test, Table 1). These data indicate that, under the conditions used in this assay, the prodrugs 2a and 2b are fully activated in the presence of ROS, with formation of the corresponding NAAF drugs. The ROS-generating activity of prodrugs 2c and 2d was found to be ~2-fold lower than that of 2a and 2b ($p < 0.05$, Student's *t*-test). However, it still significantly exceeded that of ferrocene used as a negative control ($p < 0.05$, Student's *t*-test). The lower activity of 2c and 2d correlates with their higher lipophilicity and their correspondingly higher propensity to form aggregates in aqueous solution (Figure S45, SI).

3.5. Anticancer Activity of the Prodrugs towards Different Cell Lines

We investigated the anticancer activity of all prepared prodrugs towards human ovarian cancer A2780 cells, which were selected as representative cell line. After a 96 h incubation time we found all prepared prodrugs to be more toxic in A2780 cells than the parent compound 1 ($p < 0.01$, Student's *t*-test for all data pairs): IC_{50} values were determined to be in the range from 5.3 ± 1.9 (for 2c) to 12 ± 3 μM (for 2b) versus 30 ± 5 μM (for 1) (Table 2 and Table S2, SI).

Table 2. Anticancer effects (IC₅₀) of prodrugs and controls towards different human cancer cell lines.

Prodrug/Control	IC ₅₀ (μM)/Human Cancer Cell Lines ⁱ			
	A2780	BL-2	AsPC1	Jurkat
1	30 ± 5	17 ± 6	-	30 ± 4
2c	4.0 ± 0.5	5.7 ± 2.7	7.1 ± 1.0	5 ± 2
2c_c	6.1 ± 1.5	-	-	-
5b	7 ± 2	5 ± 3	6.7 ± 0.5	7.2 ± 0.1
6	>100	>100	-	>100

ⁱ IC₅₀: a drug concentration, at which 50% viable cells remain in the mixture. A2780: human ovarian cancer cell line (incubation time 96 h); BL-2: human Burkitt's lymphoma cell line (incubation time 96 h); AsPC1: human pancreatic cancer cell line (incubation time 72 h); Jurkat: T-cell leukemia cell line (incubation time 48 h).

This trend was also seen for 2a and 2b at shorter incubation times, whereas 2c and 2d did not reach IC₅₀ under these conditions. The dose-response curves showing the dependence of cell viability on the prodrug concentration are given in Figure S50, SI. Similar results were obtained within prodrug pairs 2a/2b and 2c/2d, while differences between the pairs were found. In particular, increasing concentrations of prodrugs 2a and 2b caused a continuous reduction of the number of viable cells, whereas the effect of 2c and 2d was found to be saturated at 70%, 50% and 43% cell viability after 24, 48 and 96 h, respectively. This saturation can be explained by the tendency of the latter prodrugs to aggregate at >10 μM (Figure S45, SI), assuming that the aggregates are not active in contrast to the monomers. The enhanced anticancer effects of 2c and 2d at the longer incubation times may indicate anti-proliferative properties or time-dependent induction of cell death.

Among the prepared prodrugs, 2c was found to be most potent towards A2780 cells: IC₅₀ = 5.3 ± 1.9 μM (96 h incubation). Therefore, it was selected for further biological studies. The anticancer efficacy of 2c towards A2780 cells is similar to that of the lysosome-targeting 5b [22] (IC₅₀ = 7 ± 2 μM, Student's *t*-test), which is the best currently known NAAF-prodrug in terms of anticancer efficacy in vitro and in vivo as well as cancer cell specificity. A previously reported conjugate 5c [24], consisting of an NAAF-prodrug covalently linked to a triphenylalkylphosphonium residue (TPP) and designed as a mitochondria-targeting prodrug, exhibited similar anticancer efficacy as well: IC₅₀ = 5 ± 2 μM, Student's *t*-test. However, 5c does not act as a typical NAAF prodrug according to the reported data [28]. In contrast, its anticancer efficacy could be interpreted as the direct toxicity of the TPP residue modulated by the NAAF moiety. The fact that cancer cell specificity of 5c was found to be limited precluded further in vivo studies on this compound. Therefore, throughout this paper, biological effects of 2c will be compared with 5b and the parent compound 1, rather than 5c.

We also evaluated the anticancer effects of 2c in other than A2780 cancer cells derived from different tumor moieties, including Burkitt's lymphoma (BL-2 cells, Table S3, SI), pancreatic cancer (AsPC1 cells, Table S4, SI) and T-cell leukemia (Jurkat cells, Table S5, SI). We confirmed that all these cells contain the high level of ROS. Therefore, they were expected to be sensitive to ROS amplifying drugs [18–29]. Due to the slow kinetics of action of 2c observed in A2780 cells (Table S2, SI), incubation times of 48–96 h were selected. Prodrug 2c exhibited anticancer efficacy in all cell lines studied, exceeding that of the parent prodrug 1 (*p* < 0.05, Student's *t*-test, Table 2 and Tables S3–S5, SI). These data indicate 2c as potentially applicable for the treatment of different tumor types.

One possible explanation of the higher activity of 2c as compared to 1 could be the stronger cellular uptake of 2c. According to log*P* values (Table 1), the energy independent or passive uptake of 2c was expected to be higher than that of 1. To confirm this estimation, we determined the uptake efficacy of 2c experimentally by monitoring both boron and iron level increase in A2780 cells incubated with 2c (5 μM). As controls, the cells incubated with a carrier only (DMSO, 1%, *v/v*) or with 1 (5 μM) were used (Table S1, SI). We observed that under the selected conditions the uptake efficacy of 2c is substantially higher than that of 1 (Student's *t*-test, *p* < 0.001).

3.6. The Mechanism of the Anticancer Activity of Prodrug 2c

Encouraged by the favorable properties of 2c (high lipophilicity leading to the efficient intracellular uptake, sufficient solubility in aqueous buffers as well as high to moderate anticancer efficacy in different human cancer cells), we evaluated its mechanism of action. These experiments were conducted in two representative cells lines: Jurkat and A2780. We observed that 2c induces death of both Jurkat (Figure S51, SI) and A2780 cells (Figure S55, SI) mainly via necrosis, whereas apoptosis was found to play a minor role. In Jurkat cells, 2c caused the cell-cycle arrest in the G0/G1 phase (Figure S52, SI) analogously to the parent prodrug 1 [23] and the lysosome-targeting prodrug 5b [22]. However, while the prodrug 1 treatment led to a slight increase of both the MMP (Figure S53, SI) and intracellular GSH amounts (in both cases $p < 0.05$, Student's t -test, Figure S54, SI), prodrug 2c behaved differently. In fact, it caused a decrease in the MMP ($p < 0.01$, Student's t -test, Figure S53, SI) while leaving amounts of intracellular GSH unaffected in Jurkat cells (Figure S54). In A2780 cells, prodrug 2c reduced the MMP as well, dependent on the incubation time: values were determined at 69 ± 11 (1 h incubation) or $30 \pm 5\%$ (24 h incubation) compared to the MMP of untreated cells (Figure 3 and Figure S56, SI). However, no concentration dependency was found in the range of 5 to 30 μM , which is in agreement with the above-discussed formation of inactive aggregates at 2c concentrations $>10 \mu\text{M}$ (Figure S45, SI). In contrast to Jurkat cells, the control 1 was able to reduce MMP in A2780 cells (Figure S56, SI). However, this decrease was again significantly weaker compared to prodrug 2c (e.g., at [prodrugs] = 5 μM and all tested incubation times, $p < 0.05$, Student's t -test, Figure S56, SI).

Figure 3. Effect of prodrugs 2c and 5b on relative organelle-specific staining ($F_t(\text{prodrug})/F_t(\text{carrier})$), with $F: \lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 530 \text{ nm}$. (A) Mitochondria (Mit) staining with Rhodamine 123 (R123); $t = 1, 4, 24 \text{ h}$. (B) Lysosomal staining with Acridine orange (AO); $t = 1 \text{ h}$. (C) Endoplasmic reticulum (ER) staining with ER-Tracker-Green (ERG); $t = 1, 4 \text{ h}$; (D) Golgi (G) staining with Golgi-Staining-Green (GO); $t = 1, 4 \text{ h}$. *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$; ns: non-significant (Student's t -test).

Next, we evaluated effects of 2c on other than mitochondria organelles, including lysosomes (LY), endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and Golgi (GO). In these experiments, we stained the cells with established organelle-specific fluorescent dyes (Acridine orange: LY-specific; ER-Tracker-Green and Golgi-Staining-Green) and monitored the fluorescence changes in response to the treatment with prodrug 2c (Figure 3B–D). We found that the treatment of the cells with 2c affected neither LY nor ER nor GO. In contrast, the known LY-targeting control 5b strongly affected lysosomes already after a short incubation time of 1 h, as expected [22]. The latter prodrug also affected the MMP and the ER, which could be interpreted as a secondary effect caused by the initial 5b-induced disruption of lysosomes. These data thus confirm the high mitochondria-specificity of 2c. Since 2c is an NAAF prodrug, another expected effect would be the amplification of ROS in cells [18–29]. To evaluate whether this is the case, we used three different probes: the nonspecific probe 5-(6-chloromethyl-2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (CM-DCFH-DA) for the measurement of total ROS (tROS), the mitochondria-specific probe Red Mitochondrial Superoxide Indicator (MitoSOX) for the measurement of mitochondrial ROS (mROS) and 7-(diethylamino)coumarin-3-carbohydrazide (DCCCH) for monitoring ROS-induced formation of intracellular carbonyl-derivatives (Figure 4). We observed that 2c-induced tROS was significantly higher than its background levels in both A2780 ($p < 0.01$, Student's *t*-test, Figure 4A) and Jurkat cells ($p < 0.05$, Student's *t*-test, Figure S58, SI). At [prodrug] = 5 μM , the ROS increase in A2780 cells in the presence of 2c was similar to that induced by the parent prodrug 1. Since 2c exhibited substantially higher toxicity towards A2780 cells than 1 (5.3 ± 1.9 vs. 30 ± 5 μM , $p < 0.05$, Student's *t*-test), these data indicated that the tROS is not the major determinant of 2c anticancer efficacy. Interestingly, we found mROS to be significantly increased in A2780 cells treated with 2c as compared to their non-treated counterparts (Figure 4B). In contrast, the LY-targeting prodrug 5b did not affect mROS, whereas the effects of the parent prodrugs 5a and 1 were found to be substantially weaker.

Despite producing mROS and tROS, prodrug 2c did not induce formation of significant amounts of carbonyl derivatives (Figure 4C). The analogous effect was observed for the parent prodrug 1, but was in contrast to that induced by the LY-targeting prodrug 5b. Based in these data, we conclude that the ROS-generating patterns of prodrugs 2c and 5b, including tROS, mROS and intracellular carbonyls, differ strongly from each other, thus indicating different modes of action of the prodrug 2c reported in this paper and the previously described prodrug 5b [22].

3.7. An Active Form of Prodrug 2c in Cells and the Role of Nitric Oxide in the Anticancer Activity of 2c

Despite the fact that 2c is activated in the presence of H_2O_2 as a typical NAAF prodrug (Figure S46, SI), in contrast to the control prodrug 1 as well as LY-targeting prodrug 5b, it does not exhibit high efficacy as a catalyst of ROS formation in cell free settings (Table 1). Furthermore, effects of 2c on intracellular ROS levels are also substantially different from those of NAAF prodrugs 1 and 5b as mentioned above. These differences might indicate that 2c from one side and 1 and 5b from another side act via different mechanisms.

To gain some insights into the mode of action of 2c, we prepared a control compound 2c_c, in which a boronic acid residue was replaced with a resistant to ROS dimethylaminocarbonyl group (Figures 1 and 5). The polarity of the latter group matches that of the $\text{B}(\text{OH})_2$ group, as it was confirmed by similar experimentally determined logP values of 2c_BA and 2c_c: 3.23 ± 0.11 and 3.90 ± 0.08 , respectively (Table 1). Therefore, any major differences in cellular effects of these compounds were not expected to be due to differences in their uptake efficacy. If the activity of 2c relies exclusively on the cleavage of its B-C bond in the presence of ROS with formation of the cytotoxic NAAF drug (Figure 5A), the activity of the control 2c_c would be negligible.

Figure 4. (A) Effects of prodrugs on the intracellular total ROS amount (tROS) in A2780 cells. $F(\text{prodrug})/F(\text{carrier})$: the increase of the mean fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 525 \text{ nm}$) of (CM-DCFH-DA)-loaded A2780 cells incubated with the prodrugs relative to that of the cells incubated with the carrier only (labelled “carrier”). The “carrier” sample was used as a reference. (B) Effects of prodrugs on the intracellular amount of mitochondrial ROS (mROS). $F(\text{prodrug})/F(\text{carrier})$: the increase of the mean fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 578 \text{ nm}$) of the A2780 cells incubated with the prodrugs, as determined using MitoSOX, relative to that of cells incubated with the carrier only (instead of the prodrugs). (C) Monitoring intracellular carbonyl derivatives in A2780 cells. $F(\text{prodrug})/F(\text{carrier})$: the increase of the mean fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 525 \text{ nm}$) in A2780 cells incubated with the prodrugs, as determined using DCCH, relative to that of the cells incubated with the carrier only (instead of the prodrugs). For (A–C). *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$ (Student’s *t*-test with respect to the “carrier” probe: indicated with “reference” on the plot).

Figure 5. (A) An outline of the possible pathway of activation of **2c** in cells: first, hydrolysis occurs with formation of **2c_{BA}**, second, ROS-induced activation occurs with formation of the NAAF drug. ROS-resistant control **2c_c** and **2c** have identical cellular effects (B–D). Therefore, the ROS-induced **2c_{BA}** activation is not operative for prodrug **2c**. Effects of carrier (DMSO, 1%, *v/v*), **2c** (5 μM) and **2c_c** (5 μM) on (B) MMP (Fluorescence = $F_t(\text{prodrug})/F_t(\text{carrier})$, where F : $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 530 \text{ nm}$, r.u. = relative units, probe: R123, incubation time $t = 1, 4, 24 \text{ h}$ as indicated on the plot); (C) total ROS (tROS, same detection parameters as in B, probe: CM-DCFH-DA, $t = 2 \text{ h}$) and (D) mitochondrial ROS (mROS, F : $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 578 \text{ nm}$, probe: MitoSOX, $t = 1, 2 \text{ h}$).

We observed that not to be the case. Anticancer activity of **2c** and **2c_c** towards representative human cancer A2780 cells was observed to be the same: 4.0 ± 0.5 and $6.1 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{M}$, respectively (Student's *t*-test: $p = 0.0829$, Table 2). Further, we investigated effects of **2c_c** on MMP, mROS and tROS in A2780 cells and compared the data with those obtained for **2c** (Figure 5B–D). The effects of **2c** and **2c_c** were found to be practically identical. Thus, these compounds exhibit not only similar anticancer activity, but also have the same mode of action. These data indicate that **2c** is not activated in cells with formation of NAAF drugs, but rather acts as an intact drug **2c_{BA}** (a hydrolyzed form of prodrug **2c**, Figure 5A). The intracellular target molecule of **2c_{BA}** is not known yet. However, it is apparent that this drug strongly affects mitochondria of cancer cells that can explain all other downstream effects: elevated mitochondrial and total ROS, cell death via apoptosis and necrosis.

It is known that nitric oxide (NO) strongly affects mitochondria by decreasing MMP and inducing ROS [46,47] that would be reminiscent with the effect of **2c**. We found that the level of NO in A2780 cells treated with **2c** is higher than that in A2780 cells treated with DMSO (carrier) only ($p < 0.05$, Student's *t*-test, Figure S62, SI). The increased NO may provide a link between the increased ROS and decreased MMP observed in cancer cells in the presence of **2c**.

3.8. Evaluation of Cancer Cell Specificity of the Prodrug 2c

We evaluated the cancer cell specificity of 2c in two different experiments. In the first experiment, we monitored 2c—induced mROS generation in representative cancer (A2780) and normal cells (SBLF9 fibroblasts) (Figure 6). We found that 2c induces only a slight increase of mROS level in SBLF9 cells, whereas the effect is substantially stronger in A2780 cells. The mROS increase in A2780 cells can be fully eliminated by co-incubation of the prodrug with *N*-acetylcysteine (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Effect of carrier (DMSO, 1%, *v/v*) and prodrug 2c (5 μ M) (both incubated with the cells for 24 h) on mROS (stained using MitoSOX probes) in representative normal cells (SBLF9) and cancer cells (A2780). As indicated on the plot, in some cases *N*-acetylcysteine (NAC, 5 μ M) was co-incubated with the carrier and the prodrug. Images obtained for the “carrier” and “2c” probes were compared qualitatively.

In the second experiment, cytotoxicity of the prodrugs towards chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) cells isolated from six patients was determined and compared to that towards mononuclear cells (MNCs) from six healthy donors (Figure 7). The CLL cells are derived from B cells, whereas MNC are a mixture containing B cells, among others. Thus, these primary cancer and normal cells are genetically related to each other. Therefore, this is a good *in vitro* model for estimation of cancer cell specificity of new drugs. Notably, 2c was found to be significantly more toxic in the cancer cells than in the normal cells at concentrations of 3.3 and 10 μ M ($p < 0.001$, Student’s *t*-test).

Concomitantly, IC_{50} of 2c were lower in CLL cells ($6 \pm 2 \mu$ M) compared to MNC cells ($12 \pm 3 \mu$ M, $p < 0.01$, Student’s *t*-test). Other prepared prodrugs (2a, 2b and 2d) exhibited some specificity towards primary CLL cells as well. However, in those cases the effect was not as profound as seen for 2c, thus confirming our selection of 2c as the best compound in the series of the prepared prodrugs.

3.9. Synergy of the NAAF-Prodrugs with Radiotherapy

Since prodrug 2c causes an MMP decrease (Figure 3A) and ROS increase (Figure 4) in cancer cells, we expected that it could exhibit anticancer effects synergistically with IR. To evaluate whether this is the case, we conducted experiments in two representative human head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC) cell lines, SAS and FaDu. This selection was based on the following considerations: HNSCC is the 6th most common cancer and is usually treated by RT as well as chemotherapy (CT)/RT combination therapies, with a relatively unsatisfactory 5-year survival rate of ~50% for patients with advanced disease stage [48,49]. Therefore, the search for new radiosensitizers that are able to increase the responsiveness of HNSCC to RT is warranted.

The anticancer activity of the NAAF-based prodrugs in HNSCC has not been investigated before. Therefore, we first evaluated the effects of prodrug 2c, previously reported reference prodrug 5b as well as control compounds on SAS and FaDu cell viabilities. The effects were measured after relatively short incubation times of 24 and 48 h and compared

to representative normal (retinal pigment epithelial ARPE-19, human fibroblast HF) cells (Tables S6 and S7, Figure S63, SI). We observed that the negative control 6 (ferrocene) and the slowly activated 2c did not reach measurable IC_{50} values under these conditions, whereas the positive non-specific control 7 exhibited high toxicity towards both, cancer and normal cells. Notably, the lysosome-targeting 5b was found to be more toxic in SAS cells than in both studied normal cells under the selected conditions. In contrast, FaDu cells turned out to be substantially more resistant to 5b (Table S6, SI). Despite the fact that 2c did not reach IC_{50} values according to the plots of cell viability versus prodrug concentration, the treatment of HNSCC cells with 2c led to a decrease of the number of viable cells in a concentration dependent manner (Figure S63, SI). Overall, these experiments confirmed that the NAAF-prodrugs 2c and reference prodrug 5b exhibit weak to moderate anticancer activity towards HNSCC, thereby justifying further studies.

Figure 7. Effect of prodrugs 2a–2d on the viability of primary CLL cells and primary MNC's. *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$ (Student's t -test).

For the evaluation of the synergy of IR with the NAAF-prodrugs, we compared effects of the individual effectors and their combinations on the colony formation capacity of SAS and FaDu cells (clonogenic assay). We selected the prodrug concentrations at around IC_{80} -values, as determined in cell culture experiments (Table S8, SI). In both, cell culture-based and clonogenic assays, prodrug 2c was found to be less potent than 5b (Table S9, SI). For example, 25 μ M 2c were able to reduce the growth of colonies of SAS and FaDu cells to $70 \pm 10\%$ and to $20 \pm 8\%$, respectively, whereas a 10-fold lower dose of 5b was already sufficient for the reduction of colony formation of SAS cells ($36 \pm 15\%$) and of FaDu cells ($36 \pm 10\%$). Interestingly, FaDu cells were found to be more sensitive towards both tested

NAAF-prodrugs in the clonogenic assay, which is in contrast to the trend observed in the experiment with cell cultures. Importantly, both NAAF-prodrugs 2c and 5b significantly potentiated the inhibitory effect of the IR on the ability SAS cells lines to form colonies ($p < 0.001$, Student's t -test, Table 3, Figure 8).

Table 3. Statistical comparison (p -values) of irradiation dose–response curves with and without sub-toxic concentrations of the drug candidates.

Prodrug	Concentration (μM)	Radiosensitization ⁱ	p -Values ⁱⁱ	
			SAS	FaDu
2c	10	+/-	<0.001	ns
	25	+	<0.001	<0.001
5b	1	+	<0.001	<0.01
	2.5	+	<0.001	<0.001
6	25	-	ns	ns
7	0.1	+/-	ns	<0.01

ⁱ The radiosensitizing effect was evaluated semi-quantitatively as no radiosensitization (“-”), weak effect or effect in one cell line only (“+/-”), or clear/strong (“+”) radiosensitization. ⁱⁱ p -Values were determined by Mann–Whitney tests including Bonferroni–Holm correction using IBM SPSS Statistics 21; ns = not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 8. Representative data illustrating the synergy of prodrugs 2c and 5b with radiotherapy in SAS and FaDu cells. The graphs show clonogenic survival as a function of the irradiation dose. The data points represent mean values (\pm SD) from $n = 3$ independent experiments and the lines display the clonogenic survival curve fits. ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

The effect in FaDu cells was comparable ($p < 0.001$, Table 3), except that at the lowest tested concentration of 2c (10 μM) the prodrug did not affect the IR-induced inhibition of the colony formation. These data indicate that the NAAF-prodrugs exhibit the synergy with the IR under the optimized conditions. In contrast, ferrocene, which was used as a stable negative control, not reactive with ROS, did not act as a radiosensitizer at the selected conditions. Notably, the positive control 7 did not facilitate the IR effect in SAS cells either, but exhibited some synergy with the IR in FaDu cells ($p < 0.01$, Mann–Whitney test including Bonferroni–Holm correction).

4. Conclusions

We optimized the structure of the previously reported prodrug 1 by replacing the 5-ethoxycarbonylpentyl residue with more hydrophobic rests R'. We thus obtained the prodrugs 2a-d (Figure 1) with the goal of fine-tuning the lipophilicity/cellular uptake efficacy without negatively affecting their solubility in aqueous buffers and cancer cell specificity. The best compound in this small series, 2c, exhibits significant anticancer efficacy in human ovarian carcinoma, human Burkitt's lymphoma, human pancreatic carcinoma and T-cell leukemia cells, with IC₅₀ values in the range of 5–7.1 μM. This is comparable to the lysosome-targeting prodrug 5b and the efficacies are substantially higher compared to 1. We observed that 2c causes the cell cycle arrest in G0/G1 phase and targets mitochondria, but not other organelles of cancer cells (lysosomes, endoplasmic reticulum, Golgi). This is accompanied by the increase of levels of both mitochondrial and total ROS as well as nitric oxide. However, it is not clear which of them is an upstream factor. In contrast to 2c, 5b does not induce an increase of mROS. Furthermore, it causes ROS-mediated formation of intracellular carbonyls, whereas 2c does not exert this effect. These data indicate that 2c and 5b act via different mechanisms and are, therefore, complementary to each other. This also suggests the possibility of synergistic effects between these prodrugs. Since 2c strongly affects mitochondria, mitochondria-driven apoptosis would be the obvious cell death mechanism for 2c. However, it does not seem to be the major route in this case. Necrosis is substantially more prominent. The latter can be caused by excessive ROS production leading to direct disturbance of cellular membrane.

Since mitochondria-targeting drugs often potentiate anticancer effects of radiotherapy, we investigated the radiosensitizing properties of 2c and the control prodrug 5b. The latter compound also affects mitochondria of cancer cells, which is a secondary effect caused by the 5b-induced disruption of lysosomes (Figure 3B). In both cases, we observed substantial synergistic effects with radiotherapy in human head and neck squamous cell carcinoma cell lines in the clonogenic assay. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first demonstration of the radiosensitizing effects of cancer specific ROS-amplifying prodrugs.

Supplementary Materials: The following are available online at <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/cancers14010208/s1>, Figures S1–S42: ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR and high resolution mass spectra (HRMS) of reported intermediates, prodrugs and drugs, Figure S43: HPLC profiles of prodrugs 2a–2d (30 μM) and the control probe incubated in CH₃CN/triethylammonium acetate buffer—pH 7.0, 1.5 mM, 3/7, v/v for 0 and 2 h, Figure S44: Microscopic images (Objective 40×/0.5 Ph0, Eyepiece WF 10×/20 Br. foc.) of solutions/suspensions of prodrugs 2a–2d in RPMI 1640 medium obtained either immediately (labelled “0 h”) or 48 h after mixing all components (labelled “48 h”), Figure S45: Correlation of mean particle size (Z-average diameter) and concentration of prodrugs compounds in RPMI 1640 medium, Figures S46–S48: Structural formulas and exact masses of products identified in the mixtures of 2c with/without H₂O₂ by using high resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrometry, Figure S49: Increase of the fluorescence intensity (λ_{ex} = 501 nm, λ_{em} = 523 nm) upon oxidation of DCFH by H₂O₂ in the presence of FeSO₄, Figure S50: Effects of prodrugs 2a–2d at different incubation times on viability of A2780 cells as determined by using the MTT assay described above, Figure S51: The mechanism of Jurkat cell death in the presence of prodrugs 1 and 2c (incubation time: 48 h), Figure S52: Effect of prodrugs 1 and 2c (48 h incubation) on Jurkat cell cycle, Figure S53: MMP of Jurkat cells after their incubation for 48 h with prodrugs 1 and 2c, Figure S54: Effect of prodrugs 1 and 2c (48 h incubation) on the intracellular amount of GSH in Jurkat cells, Figure S55: Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of A2780 cell lines after 48 h incubation, Figure S56: Effects of the prodrugs on MMP of A2780 cell lines after 1–48 h incubation, Figure S57: Representative flow cytometric histograms used for setting up Figure 3A–D (main text) and Figure 5A. Figure S58: Effects of prodrugs 2c and 5b on the intracellular total ROS amount (tROS) in Jurkat cells. Figure S59. Representative flow cytometric histograms used for setting up Figures 4A and 5C. Figure S60. Representative flow cytometric histograms used for setting up Figures 4B and 5D. Figure S61. Representative flow cytometric histograms used for setting up Figure 4C. Figure S62. Fluorescence of DAF-FM diacetate-loaded A2780 cells treated either with 2c or the carrier. *: *p* < 0.05, Student's *t* test. Figure S63: Representative experimental data showing relative survival as function of drug

concentration in two HNSCC cell lines and two normal cell lines as determined via the MTT assays. Table S1: Relative boron amount in A2780 cells treated with carrier, prodrugs 1 or 2c, Table S2: Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of A2780 cell lines (IC₅₀ values) after different incubation times, Table S3: Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of BL2 cell line (IC₅₀ values) after 48 and 96 h incubation, Table S4: Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of AsPC1 cell lines (IC₅₀ values) after 72 h incubation, Table S5: Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of Jurkat cell lines (IC₅₀ values) after 48 h incubation, Table S6: EC₅₀ values (50% survival) in cancer SAS and FaDu cells determined via the MTT assay after 48 h of exposure to the prodrugs, Table S7: EC₅₀ values (50% survival) in representative normal ARPE-19 and human fibroblasts (HF) cells determined via the MTT assay after 48 h of exposure to the prodrugs, Table S8: EC₂₀ values (80% survival) in cancer SAS and FaDu cells determined via the MTT assay after 24 h and 48 h of exposure to the prodrugs, Table S9: Effects of the prodrugs on the capacity of SAS and FaDu cells to form colonies.

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Institutional Review Board Statement: The study (experiment with CLL cells and MNC’s: sample collection and analysis) was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Heidelberg (S-254/2016).

Informed Consent Statement: Clinical samples from chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) patients (N = 6, CLL cells) and healthy donors (N = 6; peripheral blood mononuclear cells, MNCs) were collected at the University Hospital Heidelberg, Germany. Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Data Availability Statement: All data are available by direct requests to the corresponding author.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Intracellular amplifiers of reactive oxygen species affecting mitochondria as radiosensitizers

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Synthesis

Prodrug 2a Compound **S1** (100.0 mg, 200 μ mol) was dissolved in anhydrous dichloromethane (4 mL). Benzyl azide (53.3 mg, 50 μ L, 400 μ mol) and bromotris(triphenylphosphine)copper(I) (55.9 mg, 60 μ mol) were added under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight at 23° C, followed by the evaporation of dichloromethane in vacuo (10 mbar). The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, methanol/dichloromethane, 2.5/100, v/v, R_f = 0.64) and recrystallization from acetone. The precipitated product was finally washed with cold acetone. The product **2a** was obtained as orange crystals (71.6 mg, 113 μ mol, yield: 57%). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ = 7.8 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 7.36-7.22 (m, 8H), 5.42 (br. s, 2H), 5.18 (s, 2H), 5.02 (s, 2H), 4.66 (br. s, 2H), 4.11 (s, 5H), 4.03 (s, 2H), 1.36 (s, 12H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ = 154.86, 145.58, 138.99, 135.01, 134.51, 129.04, 128.66, 128.00, 127.38, 122.48, 100.58, 83.86, 68.95, 67.54, 64.58, 62.87, 54.09, 46.14, 24.84. High resolution mass spectroscopy (HRMS) using APPI as an ionization method: calcd for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{38}\text{BFeN}_4\text{O}_4$ ($[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$): 633.2336; found m/z : 633.2334. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{37}\text{BFeN}_4\text{O}_4$: C 64.58, H 5.90, N 8.86; found: C 64.67, H 5.44, N 8.51.

Prodrug 2b Compound **S1** (1.00 g, 2 mmol), (2-azidoethyl)benzene (0.59 g, 4 mmol) and

bromotris(triphenylphosphine)-copper(I) (372.7 mg, 400.6 μ mol) were dissolved in dichloromethane (30 mL) and stirred under nitrogen atmosphere at 25° C for twenty four

hours followed by evaporation of dichloromethane in vacuo (10 mbar). The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane/acetone, 95/5, v/v, R_f = 0.48). Pure **2b** was obtained as orange solid (854 mg, 1.32 mmol, yield: 66%). ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ = 7.85 (d, J = 7.9 Hz, 2H), 7.39-7.25 (m, 6H), 7.09 (d, J = 5.5 Hz, 2H), 5.20 (s, 2H), 5.09 (s, 2H), 4.52-4.28 (m, 11H) 3.17 (br. s, 2H), 1.38 (s, 12H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $\text{dms}\text{-}d_6$) δ = 143.98, 139.68, 137.53, 134.51, 134.21, 128.61, 128.34,

127.11, 126.51, 123.6, 100.55, 83.65, 68.74, 66.71, 64.14, 62.38, 50.39, 45.43, 35.76, 24.62. HRMS (APPI): calcd for $C_{35}H_{39}BFeN_4O_4$ ($[M-e]^+$): 646.2415; found m/z : 646.2422. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $C_{35}H_{39}BFeN_4O_4$: C 65.02, H 6.08, N 8.67; found: C 64.68, H 6.29, N 8.88.

Prodrug 2c Intermediate **S2** (300.0 mg, 436.4 μ mol), 3-phenylpropyne (152.1 mg, 1.31 mmol) and bromotris(triphenylphosphine)copper(I) (81.2 mg, 87.3 μ mol) were dissolved in

dichloromethane (15 mL) and stirred under nitrogen atmosphere at 25° C for 24 hours followed by evaporation of dichloromethane in vacuo (10 mbar). The crude product **2c** was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane/acetone, 90/10, v/v, $R_f = 0.44$). The product was obtained as orange solid (260 mg, 323 μ mol, yield: 74%). 1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): $\delta = 7.97$ (br. s, 1H), 7.80 (s, 1H), 7.66 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.35 (d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.29-7.18 (m, 9H), 5.55 (s, 2H), 5.51 (s, 2H), 5.17 (s, 2H), 4.91 (s, 2H), 4.55 (br. s, 2H), 4.06 (s, 2H), 4.00 (t, $J = 2(x2)$ Hz, 2H), 3.95 (s, 2H), 1.28 (s, 12H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CD_3CN) $\delta = 148.23, 146.46, 140.88, 140.81, 137.27, 137.01, 135.65, 129.55, 129.52, 129.47, 129.45, 128.29, 127.23, 123.89, 122.94, 84.94, 69.83, 68.07, 65.37, 63.51, 54.02, 53.87, 40.52, 32.48, 25.22$. HRMS (APPI): calcd for $C_{44}H_{47}BFeN_7O_4$ $[M+H]^+$: 804.3135; found m/z : 804.3129. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $C_{44}H_{46}BFeN_7O_4$: C 65.77, H 5.77, N 12.20 found: C 65.70, H 5.82, N 12.12.

Prodrug 2d Prodrug **2d** was obtained analogously to prodrug **2c** except that 4-

phenylbutyne (136.4 mg, 1.05 mmol) was used in place of 3-phenylpropyne. The purified product was isolated as orange crystals (220 mg, 270 μ mol, yield: 62%). TLC (silica gel, eluent

methanol/ dichloromethane, 2.5/97.5, v/v) $R_f = 0.22$. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, Acetone- d_6): $\delta = 7.74$ (d, $J = 8$ Hz, 4H), 7.51 (s, 1H), 7.41-7.14 (m, 10H), 5.62-5.55 (m, 4H), 5.20 (s, 2H), 4.99 (s, 2H), 4.65 (br. s, 2H), 4.09-4.06 (m, 5H), 3.99-3.98 (m, 2H), 2.93 (s, 4H), 1.34 (s, 12H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 148.02, 146.26, 142.44, 140.89, 137.52, 137.06, 135.76, 132.68, 129.79, 129.46, 129.24, 129.19, 128.21, 126.84, 123.98, 122.46, 102.18, 84.73, 69.77, 67.92, 65.19, 63.52, 53.89, 53.64, 46.53, 36.28, 28.38, 25.30$. HRMS (ESI-TOF): calcd for $\text{C}_{45}\text{H}_{48}\text{BFeN}_7\text{O}_4$ $[\text{M}-\text{e}^-]^+$: 817.3205; found m/z : 817.3212. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{45}\text{H}_{48}\text{BFeN}_7\text{O}_4$: C 66.11, H 5.92, N 11.99; found: C 66.25, H 5.68, N 11.89.

Intermediate S3 A mixture containing 4-(hydroxymethyl)benzoic acid (2000 mg, 13.1 mmol) and 1-[3-(dimethylamino)propyl]-3-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC, 2827 mg, 14.5 mmol) in dichloromethane (50 mL) was stirred for 20 min at 23 °C (active ester intermediate can be monitored by TLC using ethyl acetate as an eluent), followed by adding dimethylamine (2 M in THF, 7.9 mL, 15.8 mmol). After stirring for 10 min, the reaction mixture was concentrated by partial solvent evaporation and purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane/methanol, 25/1, v/v) to give S3 as a colorless oil (750 mg, 4.18 mmol, 32%). TLC (silica gel, dichloromethane/methanol, 10/1, v/v) $R_f = 0.40$. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) $\delta = 7.55 - 7.29$ (m, 4H), 4.78 (s, 2H), 3.86 (s, 1H), 3.19 (s, 6H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) $\delta = 171.93, 143.32, 134.60, 127.08, 126.46, 64.17, 39.69, 35.54$. HRMS (APPI): calcd for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 180.1019; found m/z : 180.1017.

EDC
H
N
S3

Intermediate S4 S3 (32 mg, 0.17 mmol) and ferrocenylcarbonylazide (40 mg, 0.16 mmol) were dissolved under nitrogen atmosphere in anhydrous toluene (3 mL) and heated to 105 °C. The reaction mixture was stirred for a further 2 h at 105 °C. The solvent was removed by evaporation and the crude product was purified by column

ferrocenylcarbonylazide
Toluene, reflux
S4

was removed by evaporation and the crude product was purified by column

chromatography (silica gel, ethyl acetate, $R_f = 0.46$). Pure **S4** was obtained as orange foam (65 mg, 0.16 mmol, yield: 97%). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 8.05$ (s, 1H), 7.63 – 7.29 (m, 4H), 5.18 (s, 2H), 4.56 (s, 2H), 4.10 (s, 5H), 3.93 (t, $J=1.9$, 2H), 2.99 (s, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 171.00$, 154.56, 139.35, 137.58, 128.35, 128.12, 97.73, 69.69, 66.22, 64.62, 61.08, 39.50, 35.20. HRMS (APPI): calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{FeN}_2\text{O}_3$ $[\text{M}-\text{e}]^+$: 406.0974; found m/z : 406.0982.

Intermediate S5 **S4** (300 mg, 0.74 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous DMF (3.7 mL) under a nitrogen atmosphere. Then Cs_2CO_3 (722 mg, 2.22 mmol), CsI (190 mg, 0.74 mmol) were added to the solution. After stirring for 0.5

a nitrogen atmosphere. Then Cs_2CO_3 (722 mg, 2.22 mmol), CsI (190 mg, 0.74 mmol) were added to the solution. After stirring for 0.5

h at 22 °C, propargyl chloride (110 mg, 107 μL , 1.48 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred overnight. After dilution with ethyl acetate and filtration, the solvent was removed and the crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, iso-hexane/acetone, 3/1, v/v). Pure **S5** was obtained as orange oil (260 mg, 0.58 mmol, yield: 79%). TLC (silica gel, dichloromethane/methanol, 20/1, v/v) $R_f = 0.20$. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 7.58 - 7.39$ (m, 4H), 5.26 (s, 2H), 4.60 (s, 2H), 4.57 (d, $J=2.5$, 2H), 4.19 (s, 5H), 4.08 – 4.00 (m, 2H), 2.99 (s, 6H), 2.89 (s, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 170.95$, 158.72, 138.83, 137.74, 128.41, 128.15, 81.39, 73.64, 69.85, 67.64, 65.25, 63.38, 40.31, 39.39, 35.06. HRMS (ESI-TOF): calcd for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{FeN}_2\text{O}_3$ $[\text{M}-\text{e}]^+$: 444.1131; found m/z : 444.1117.

Synthesis of intermediate S6 Intermediate **S6** was obtained analogously to intermediate

S2 except that intermediate **S5** (260 mg, 0.59 mmol) was used in place of **S1** and iso-hexane/acetone (2/1, v/v) was used in place of dichloromethane/acetone (95/5, v/v). The purified product was

obtained as orange solid (178 mg, 0.28 mmol, yield: 48%). TLC (silica gel, iso-hexane/acetone, 1/1, v/v) $R_f = 0.40$. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 7.79$ (s, 1H), 7.60 – 7.21 (m, 8H), 5.61 (s, 2H), 5.22 (s, 2H), 5.01 (s, 2H), 4.66 (s, 2H), 4.43 (s, 2H), 4.08 (s, 5H), 3.99 (t, $J=2.0$, 2H), 3.02 (s, 6H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 170.93$, 154.74, 146.09, 138.78, 137.68, 136.97, 136.91, 129.65, 129.18, 128.58, 128.14, 123.94, 102.08, 69.64, 67.47, 65.08, 63.43, 54.56, 53.79, 46.45, 39.47, 35.15. HRMS (ESI-TOF): calcd for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{32}\text{FeN}_8\text{O}_3$ $[\text{M-e}]^+$: 632.1942; found m/z : 632.1935.

2c_c Control compound **2c_c** was obtained analogously to **2c** except that intermediate

S6 (70 mg, 0.11 mmol) was used in place of **S2** and iso-hexane/acetone (1/1, v/v) was used in place of dichloromethane/acetone (90/10, v/v). The purified

product was obtained as orange solid (48 mg, 0.06 mmol, yield: 58%). TLC (silica gel, iso-hexane/acetone, 1/2, v/v) $R_f = 0.43$. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 8.06$ – 7.03 (m, 15H), 5.57 (s, 2H), 5.55 (s, 2H), 5.20 (s, 2H), 5.01 (s, 2H), 4.75 (s, 2H), 4.12 (s, 5H), 4.07 (s, 2H), 3.99 (s, 2H), 2.98 (s, 6H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 171.00$, 147.98, 146.30, 140.72, 138.82, 137.74, 137.31, 137.07, 129.48, 129.33, 129.27, 129.25, 128.61, 128.17, 127.01, 123.91, 122.87, 70.28, 67.47, 65.51, 63.39, 53.77, 53.65, 46.26, 39.52, 35.19, 32.59. HRMS (ESI-TOF): calcd for $\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{40}\text{FeN}_8\text{O}_3$ $[\text{M-e}]^+$: 748.2567; found m/z : 748.2569. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{40}\text{FeN}_8\text{O}_3$: C 65.78, H 5.39, N 14.97 found: C 65.50 H 5.24 N 14.79.

Intermediate S8 Intermediate **S8** was obtained analogously to **S1** except that N-Boc-

protected aminoferrocene **S7** was used in place of 4-(ferrocenylaminocarbonyloxymethyl)phenylboronic acid pinacol ester. The product was

isolated as orange oil (49 mg, 145 μmol , yield 87%). TLC (silica gel, eluent cyclohexane/acetone, 4/1, v/v) $R_f = 0.64$. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) $\delta = 4.68$ (d, $J = 152.5$, 10H), 2.25 (s, 1H), 1.48 (s, 9H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) $\delta = 81.32$, 71.81,

62.53, 39.49, 28.40. HRMS (ESI-TOF): calcd for $C_{18}H_{21}FeNO_2 [M-e]^+$: 339.0916; found m/z : 339.0921.

Intermediate S9 Intermediate **S9** was obtained analogously to prodrug **2a** except that

intermediate **S8** was used in place of **S1**. The product was isolated as orange powder (469 mg, 990 μ mol, yield 80%). TLC (silica gel, eluent cyclohexane/acetone, 4/1, v/v) R_f = 0.31. 1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 7.85 (s, 1H), 7.45 – 7.27 (m, 5H), 5.64 (s, 2H), 4.90 (s, 2H), 4.64 (s, 2H), 4.07 (s, 5H), 4.00 – 3.92 (m, 2H), 1.44 (s, 9H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 146.63, 137.10, 129.67, 129.08, 128.90, 123.75, 81.14, 69.61, 64.92, 63.20, 54.17, 46.11, 28.46. HRMS (ESI-TOF): calcd for $C_{25}H_{28}FeN_4O_2 [M-e]^+$: 472.1556; found m/z : 472.1555.

for $C_{25}H_{28}FeN_4O_2 [M-e]^+$: 472.1556; found m/z : 472.1555.

3*2HCl Intermediate **S9** (50 mg, 110 μ mol) was grinded to powder and hydrochloric acid

in iso-propanol (5.5 M, 1.7 mL) was added. This operation was conducted under nitrogen. The mixture was stirred at 22-25 $^{\circ}C$ overnight. The obtained product was precipitated. It was filtered

and dried in vacuo (10 mbar). The product was obtained as orange powder (32 mg, 70 μ mol, yield 68%). TLC (silica gel, eluent dichloromethane/methanol, 20/3, v/v) R_f = 0.65. 1H NMR (400 MHz, MeOD) δ = 7.99 (s, 1H), 7.41 – 7.28 (m, 5H), 5.61 (s, 2H), 4.49 (s, 2H), 4.41 – 4.31 (m, 7H), 4.26 – 4.21 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, MeOD) δ = 136.59, 130.03, 129.68, 129.17, 127.17, 93.55, 71.10, 68.61, 64.17, 55.01, 47.82. HRMS (ESI-TOF): calcd for $C_{20}H_{20}FeN_4 [M-e]^+$: 372.1032; found m/z : 372.1032. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $C_{20}H_{22}Cl_2FeN_4$: C 53.96, H 4.98, N 12.59; found: C 54.03, H 5.16, N 12.62.

Intermediate S10 Intermediate **S10** was obtained analogously to intermediate **S8** except

that benzylchloride was used in place of propargylchloride. The product was isolated as orange oil (400 mg, 1.02 mmol, yield 77%). TLC (silica gel, eluent cyclohexane/acetone, 4/1, v/v) R_f

= 0.48. 1H NMR (300 MHz, dms o - d_6) δ = 7.50 – 7.15 (m, 5H), 4.92 (s, 2H), 4.43 (s, 2H),

4.13 (s, 5H), 4.00 – 3.92 (m, 2H), 1.47 (s, 9H). ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ = 140.48, 129.23, 127.55, 127.21, 102.85, 80.95, 69.61, 64.83, 63.07, 53.82, 28.45. HRMS (ESI-TOF): calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{25}\text{FeNO}_2$ $[\text{M}-\text{e}]^+$: 391.1229; found m/z : 391.1230.

4*HCl was obtained analogously to **3*2HCl** except that **S6** was used in place of **S5**. The product was obtained as orange powder (302 mg, 920 μmol , yield 90%). TLC (silica gel, eluent dichloromethane/methanol, 20/3, v/v) R_f = 0.79. ^1H NMR (300 MHz, MeOD) δ = 7.49 – 7.31 (m, 5H), 4.42 – 4.32 (m, 9H), 4.30 – 4.24 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, MeOD) δ = 131.86, 131.64, 130.80, 130.04, 93.83, 71.09, 68.54, 64.28, 57.52. HRMS (ESI-TOF): calcd for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{FeN}$ $[\text{M}-\text{e}]^+$: 291.0705; found m/z : 291.0704. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{ClFeN}$: C 62.32, H 5.54, N 4.28; found: C 62.21, H 5.63, N 4.31.

^1H -NMR, ^{13}C -NMR and high resolution mass spectra (HRMS) of reported intermediates, prodrugs and drugs

Figure S1. ^1H -NMR spectrum of prodrug **2a** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S2. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of prodrug **2a** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S3. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of prodrug **2a**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S4. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of prodrug **2b** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S5. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum of prodrug **2b** in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S6. High resolution APPI mass spectrum of prodrug **2b**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S7. ¹H-NMR spectrum of prodrug **2c** in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S8. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of prodrug **2c** in CD_3CN .

Figure S9. High resolution APPI mass spectrum of prodrug **2c**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S10. ¹H-NMR spectrum of prodrug **2d** in acetone-d₆.

Figure S11. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of prodrug **2d** in acetone-d₆.

Figure S12. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of prodrug **2d**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S13. ¹H-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S3** in CDCl₃.

4xu023178
HX060-B2811B-D

Figure **S14**. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S3** in CDCl₃.

Figure **S15**. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of intermediate **S3**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

4xu023226
HX061-B3011A

Figure **S16**. ¹H-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S4** in acetone-d₆.

4xu023226
HX061-B3011A

Figure **S17**. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S4** in acetone-d₆.

Figure **S18**. High resolution APPI mass spectrum of intermediate **S4**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S19**. ¹H-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S5** in acetone-d₆.

Figure **S20**. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S5** in acetone-d₆.

Figure **S21**. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of intermediate **S5**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

4xu033545
HX094-comb-3rd-col-ish/act-1/1

Figure **S22**. ¹H-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S6** in acetone-d₆.

3xu014338
HX094-B2605-col-F9-13

Figure **S23**. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S6** in acetone-d₆.

Figure **S24**. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of intermediate **S6**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S25**. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of intermediate **2c_c** in acetone- d_6 .

Figure S26. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of compound **2c_c** in acetone-d₆.

Figure S27. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of **2c_c**: upper plot –experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S28**. ¹H-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S8** in CDCl₃. NMR solvent residual peaks are marked with *.

Figure **S29**. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S8** in CDCl₃. NMR solvent residual peaks are marked with *.

Figure **S30**. High resolution APPI mass spectrum of intermediate **S8**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S31**. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of intermediate **S9** in acetone- d_6 . NMR solvent residual peaks are marked with *.

Figure S32. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of intermediate **S9** in acetone- d_6 . NMR solvent residual peaks are marked with *.

Figure S33. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of intermediate **S9**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S34**. ^1H -NMR spectrum of HCl salt of drug **3** ($3 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$) in methanol- d_4 . NMR solvent residual peaks are marked with *.

Figure **S35**. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of HCl salt of drug **3** ($3 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$) in methanol- d_4 . NMR solvent residual peaks are marked with *.

Figure **S36**. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of HCl salt of drug **3** (**3***2HCl): upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S37**. ¹H-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S10** in acetone-d₆. NMR solvent residual peaks are marked with *.

Figure **S38**. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S10** in acetone-d₆. NMR solvent residual peaks are marked with *.

Figure **S39**. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of intermediate **S10**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S40**. ^1H -NMR spectrum of HCl salt of drug **4** (4^*HCl) in methanol- d_4 . NMR solvent residual peaks are marked *.

Figure **S41**. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of HCl salt of drug **4** (4^*HCl) in methanol- d_4 . NMR solvent residual peaks are marked with *.

Figure S42. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of HCl salt of drug **4** (**4***HCl): upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Determination of crystal structure of prodrug **2a**

Crystals of prodrug **2a** were obtained by its re-crystallization from acetone (Figure 1). All details of crystal structure determination were deposited to Cambridge Structural Database (CCDC) under deposition number 1958761.

Evaluation of hydrolysis of prodrugs in the aqueous neutral solution by using HPLC-UV-MS

Stock solutions of prodrugs (**2a-2d**, 3 mM) in DMSO were first prepared. Then they were diluted 100-fold (final concentration: 30 μ M) with CH₃CN/TEAA (triethylammonium acetate buffer - pH 7.0, 1.5 mM, 3/7, v/v). As a control pure DMSO was diluted in the same way. This probe was used to acquire background HPLC traces. After the probes (20 μ L) of these solutions were incubated for 0 or 2 h at 37 °C, they were injected to HPLC coupled to UV-visible detector (detection of absorbance at 254 nm) and electrospray mass spectrometric detector (detection of positively charged ions in the m/z range of 300-1200) and the analytes were separated by using gradients of CH₃CN (containing formic acid, 0.1 %, v/v) in water (containing ammonium formate, 10 mM and formic acid, 0.1 %, v/v) from 15% to 95%. (Figure S43).

Control probe lacking any prodrug (left plot - 0 h, right plot - 2 h)

2a (upper plot - 0 h, lower plot - 2 h)

2c (upper- 0 h, lower - 2 h)

2b (upper - 0 h, lower- 2 h)

2d (upper - 0 h, lower - 2 h)

Figure S43. HPLC profiles of prodrugs **2a-2d** (30 μ M) and the control probe incubated in CH₃CN/triethylammonium acetate buffer - pH 7.0, 1.5 mM, 3/7, v/v for 0 and 2 h.

Determination of n-octanol/water partition coefficients (LogP)

Solutions of references and new prodrugs were prepared by dissolving them in the mixture of dichloromethane/CH₃OH at proper concentrations. Commercially available reverse phase (RP) plates for thin layer chromatography (TLC, Macherey-Nagel, Germany, Alugram Aluminiumfolien RP-18 W/UV₂₅₄, stationary phase thickness: 0.15 mm) were used. The plates were manually spotted with freshly prepared solutions of the analytes at 10 mm distance from the edge of the plate. As the eluent mixture acetonitrile/aqueous 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid (MOPS) buffer (100 mM, pH 7.4) (6/4, v/v) was used. The solvent migration distance was around 4.5 cm. The plates were visually inspected under the UV-light (254 nm) and each zone was clearly marked and its distance was manually measured. All measurements were done in at least triplicate and average values were used in further calculations. All experiments were performed at ambient temperature (22 ± 2 °C). A set of reference compounds was used, for which logP-values were previously reported: perylene (6.25), anthracene (4.50), benzophenone (3.18), phenylboric acid (1.59).^[S1,S2] A calibration plot of R_f versus logP, which was obtained based on these data, was used to determine logP values of new prodrugs (Table 1).

Solubility of drugs in aqueous buffers

Observing prodrug precipitation by using bright field optical microscopy

Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 medium supplemented with FBS (5 %), L-glutamine (1 %), and penicillin/streptomycin (1 %) was filled into 96-well microtiter plates (100 µL for each well) and compounds in DMSO stock solution (1 µL) were added. Each well was monitored by using bright field optical microscopy both immediately after preparing these solutions/suspensions and after 48 h incubation at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5 %). The data obtained are provided in Figure S44.

Figure **S44**. Microscopic images (Objective 40x/0.5 Ph0, Eyepiece WF 10x/20 Br. foc.) of solutions/suspensions of prodrugs **2a-2d** in RPMI 1640 medium taken either immediately (labelled “0 h”) or 48 h after mixing all components (labelled “48 h”). The wells containing the lowest concentration of the prodrug within data columns, where the precipitate was observed, are labelled with red rectangles.

Detection of oligomers in solutions of prodrugs by using dynamic light scattering

Compounds at different concentration (10 μ L) were added to autoclaved microtubes (Eppendorf® microtubes 3810X with lid, polypropylene, 1.5 mL) containing 1 mL cell culture RPMI 1640 medium (the same medium was used in the MTT assay with A2780 cells, 48 h incubation with the drugs). The microtubes were vortexed for around 5 seconds and put into the cell incubator (Galaxy 170S, New Brunswick®). They were allowed standing at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) for 48 h before measurement. Then the samples were transferred to the disposable measuring cuvettes for dynamic light scattering (BRAND® macro-cuvette, polystyrene, 2.5 mL). Each sample was measured 3 times at 25 °C (Figure S45).

Figure S45. Correlation of mean particle size (Z-average diameter) and concentration of prodrugs compounds in RPMI 1640 medium. No prodrug was added to the “blank” sample. The DLS measurement was conducted 48h after preparation of prodrug solutions/suspensions.

Activation of prodrug 2c in the presence of H₂O₂

A freshly prepared solution of **2c** (10 µL, 2.5 mM in DMSO) was added to acetonitrile (CH₃CN, 100 µL). The resulting solution was mixed with water (897 µL) followed by the addition of either H₂O₂ (2.5 µL, 30% (w/w) in H₂O) or water (2.5 µL, negative control). These solutions were kept at 22 °C for 5 minutes. Then they were diluted with CH₃CN (1 mL) and analyzed by high resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrometry (Figures S46-S48).

Figure S46. Structural formulas and exact masses of products identified in the mixtures of **2c** with/without H₂O₂ by using high resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrometry (Figures S50, S51).

Figure **S47**. ESI-TOF mass spectra of prodrugs **2c** incubated for 5 minutes either in the absence of H₂O₂ or in its presence. Other experimental conditions are as described above. Expanded regions of the spectra shown in this figure are provided below in Figure S48.

Figure **S48**. Expanded regions of the ESI-TOF mass spectra of mixtures of **2c** with H_2O_2 provided in Figure S47.

Prodrug-induced generation of ROS in cell free settings

2',7'-Dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA, 4.9 mg) was dissolved in DMF (100 μL) and mixed with aqueous NaOH (0.1 M, 900 μL). The resulting mixture was incubated for 30 min at 22 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the dark to obtain a stock solution of 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein (DCFH, 10 mM). Next, DCFH (1 μL) was added to the solution containing MOPS buffer (100 mM, pH 7.4), N,N,N',N'-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, 10 mM) and glutathione (GSH, 5 mM) (1 mL, final concentration of DCFH 10 μM). The reaction mixture was heated to 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and H_2O_2 (1 μL , final concentration 10 mM) was added. The reaction was monitored by fluorescence spectroscopy: $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 501 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 523 \text{ nm}$. After around 5 min, prodrugs (1 mM in DMF, 10 μL) or positive control FeSO_4 (1 mM in water, 10 μL) were added, and the fluorescence monitoring was continued until the fluorescence signal growth was stalled after approximately 100 to 300 min. A representative kinetics of ROS release in the presence of prodrugs is given in Figure S49. The data are presented in Table 1 as relative acceleration of the rate of the fluorescence increase, where the rate of the fluorescence increase obtained in the presence of positive control FeSO_4 was set to 1 (reference).

Figure **S49**. Increase of the fluorescence intensity ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 501 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 523 \text{ nm}$) upon oxidation of DCFH by H_2O_2 in the presence of FeSO_4 . Experimental details are provided in the description above. The time point of the FeSO_4 addition is indicated with a black

colored arrow. After the initial lagging period, the oxidation reactions reach their maximum rates (indicated with a solid line for “iron sulfate” sample), which are provided in Table 1.

Accumulation of prodrugs in A2780 cells

A2780 cells (around 150 cells/ μL , 40 mL) were seeded in T175 flasks (Greiner, Germany) in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin and incubated for 3-4 days at 37°C in the chamber filled with 5% CO_2 . Next, a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin was added to replace old medium. Prodrugs (5 mM, 400 μL in DMSO, final concentration: 5 μM) or carrier (DMSO, 400 μL , final concentration: 1% v/v) were added into the bottles and the cells were further incubated at 37°C for 4 h. The cells were washed with DPBS (2 x 10 mL) and trypsinated (trypsin/EDTA, 0.025%/0.01%, v/v, 2 mL). After the cells were harvested and centrifuged (5 min, 1000 rpm) in 50 mL falcon tube, the cell pellet was re-suspended in DPBS (1 mL), the suspension - transferred to 1.5 mL EP tube and centrifuged one more time (2 min, 2000 rpm). The obtained cell pellet was shaken with concentrated HNO_3 (65%, 100 μL) in an Eppendorf Thermomixer for 10 min at 95° C, 600 rpm. After cooling down, water (900 μL) was added. The insoluble components were separated by centrifugation (30 min, 13000 rpm) and the supernatant was analyzed by atomic emission spectrometry (AES) for the detection of B, Zn and Fe. The standard solutions for the AES were from Agilent or/and Bernd Kraft.

Table **S1**. Relative boron amount in A2780 cells treated with carrier, prodrugs **1** or **2c**.

	Relative boron amount ⁱ	Relative iron amount ⁱ
carrier	1.0 \pm 0.5	1 \pm 0
1	2.0 \pm 0.1	1.4 \pm 0.1
2c	15 \pm 1	5.0 \pm 0.1

ⁱ Zn amount was used as an internal standard.

Determination of viability of cells in the presence of prodrugs and controls

A2780 and BL-2 cells The medium was removed, and the cells were washed two times with DPBS, trypsinated, and resuspended in RPMI 1640 medium (A2780) supplemented with 5% FBS (for 24 h and 48 h assay) or 10% FBS (for 96 h assay), 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin.

A2780 cells: This suspension was spread in the wells of a 96-well microtiter plate (25000 cells for A2780 per well per 100 μ L) and left standing at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) for overnight. Stock solutions of prodrugs of different concentrations (1 μ L, solvent dmsO, final concentrations in wells were 2, 5, 10, 30, 50 μ M) were added to the wells and incubated for specific periods of time. Four experiments were conducted for each concentration of the prodrug. Finally, 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT, 20 μ L of the solution prepared by dissolving MTT (5 mg) in DPBS buffer (1 mL)) was added to each well, incubated for 3 h, treated with sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) solution (90 μ L, 10% solution in 0.01 M aqueous HCl), and incubated overnight. Afterward, the intensity of the absorbance at 590 nm was measured. MTT is converted in live cells to blue dye with the absorbance maximum λ_{max} at 590 nm. The absorbance at 690 nm was taken as a baseline value. The baseline corrected absorbance at 590 nm ($A_{(590 \text{ nm})} - A_{(690 \text{ nm})}$) was applied to calculate the relative number of viable cells. IC₅₀ values were determined by fitting the experimental data expressing the number of viable cells (% , Y-axis) versus drug concentration (μ M, X-axis) with a line curve and the X-axis value corresponding to 50% viability was considered as IC₅₀ value according to the line curve (Figure S50, Table S2).

BL-2 cells: The cells were centrifuged, the medium was removed, and the cells were washed two times with DPBS and re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% (48 h incubation) or 10% FBS (96 h incubation), 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. This suspension was spread in the wells of a 96-well microtiter plate (50000 cells per well per 100 μ L). Other steps were identical to those was described in determination of viability of adherent cells (given above) (Table S3).

Figure **S50**. Effects of prodrugs **2a-2d** at different incubation times on viability of A2780 cells as determined by using the MTT assay described above. Incubation times are indicated next to prodrug codes.

Table **S2**. Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of A2780 cell lines (IC_{50} values) after different incubation times.

Compound	IC_{50} (μM)		
	24 h	48 h	96 h
1	-	32 ± 3	30 ± 5
2a	23.7 ± 0.6	16.2 ± 1.8	10.5 ± 0.7
2b	24.7 ± 0.6	18.5 ± 1.3	12.0 ± 3.0
2c	≥ 30	≥ 30	4.0 ± 0.5
2d	≥ 30	≥ 30	8.3 ± 1.5
3	-	>50	-
4	-	>50	-
5b	-	7 ± 2	7 ± 2
5c	10 ± 3	5 ± 2	5 ± 2
6 (Fc-H, negative control)	>100	>100	>100
7 (positive control)	3.5 ± 0.1	3.3 ± 0.3	2.2 ± 0.8

Table **S3**. Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of BL2 cell line (IC₅₀ values) after 48 and 96h incubation.

Compound	IC ₅₀ (μM)	
	48 h	96 h
1	35 ± 2	16.9 ± 6.1
2c	40.1 ± 6.4	5.7 ± 2.7
5b	5 ± 2	5 ± 3
5c	5 ± 1	-
6	>100	>100
7	~1	2 ± 1

AsPC1 cells The cells (20.000/well) were seeded in a 12-well plate and incubated for 24 h. Afterwards, the medium was changed and the cells were further incubated for 72 h with medium containing different concentrations of compounds **2c** and **5b**. Viable cells were determined based on the morphological parameters by using flow cytometry (Table S4).

Table **S4**. Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of AsPC1 cell lines (IC₅₀ values) after 72 h incubation.

Compound	IC ₅₀ (μM)
2c	7.1 ± 1.0
5b	6.7 ± 0.5

Jurkat cells The cells were counted in MUSE Cell Analyzer using MUSE® Count & Viability Assay Kit (Merck-Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA) and adjusted to a density of 1.0 x 10⁵/ml in RPMI 1640 medium (with 10% FCS and 1% glutamine). 9.000 cells per well per 90 μL were seeded into 96 well culture plates. The 30 mM prodrug stock solutions in DMSO were diluted to 300 μM, 100 μM, 30 μM and 10 μM in cell culture medium and 10 μL of the dilutions was pipetted to the cells, receiving final test concentrations of 30 μM, 10 μM, 3 μM and 1 μM. Every concentration was tested in triplicates. Cells with corresponding amounts of DMSO served as negative controls. After 48 h cells were mixed and 25 μL of

the cell suspension was incubated with 200 μL of freshly prepared staining solution, consisting of AnnexinA5-Fitc (1 μL), 1,1',3,3,3',3'-hexamethylindodicarbocyanine iodide (DiIC1(5), 0.4 μL) (both from ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), propidium iodide (PI, 67 ng) and monobromobimane (MBB, 33 μM , both from Sigma-Aldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany) per 1 ml Ringer's solution (Fresenius Kabi AG, Bad Homburg, Germany). Cells were incubated for 20 min at 4°C and then analyzed in Gallios cytofluorometer™ (Beckman Coulter, Fullerton, CA, USA). Fitc and propidium iodide were excited at 488 nm; Fitc fluorescence was recorded on the FL1 sensor (525/38 nm band pass, BP) and propidium iodide fluorescence was detected on FL3 sensor (620/30 nm BP), DiIC1(5) fluorescence was excited at 638 nm and detected on FL6 sensor at 675/20 nm BP, and monobromobimane fluorescence was excited at 405 nm and detected on FL9 sensor at 430/40 nm BP. To eliminate any fluorescence bleed-through, electronic compensation was used. Data were analyzed employing Kaluza™ software Version 1.2 (Beckman Coulter, Fullerton, CA, USA) and processed in Microsoft Excel (Figures S51-S54, Table S5). Cells negative for Annexin A5-Fitc and propidium iodide were considered viable. IC₅₀ values were determined by fitting the % values of Ax-PI- cells versus drug concentration with a sigmoidal curve using GraphPad Prism software. Reduced glutathione (an intracellular thiol) can be detected by monobromobimane, a dye that becomes fluorescent after non-enzymatic binding to thiols.^[S3] For analysis of amount of mitochondrial membrane potential or reduced glutathione the mean fluorescence index (MFI) was determined from viable cells by gating on Ax-PI- events.

Table **S5**. Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of Jurkat cell lines (IC₅₀ values) after 48 h incubation.

Compound	IC ₅₀ (μM)
1	30 \pm 4
2c	5 \pm 2
5b	7.2 \pm 0.1
5c	20 \pm 2
6	>100

Figure **S51**. The mechanism of Jurkat cell death in the presence of prodrugs **1** and **2c** (incubation time: 48 h). Ax-/PI-: viable cells; Ax+/PI-: apoptotic cells; PI+: necrotic cells. Detailed experimental description is provided above.

Figure **S52**. Effect of prodrugs **1** and **2c** (48 h incubation) on Jurkat cell cycle. ***: $p < 0.001$; ns: non-significant (Student's t test). Detailed experimental description is provided above.

Figure **S53**. Mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP) of Jurkat cells after their incubation for 48 h with prodrugs **1** and **2c**. *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ns: non-significant (Student's t test). Detailed experimental description is provided above.

Figure **S54**. Effect of prodrugs **1** and **2c** (48 h incubation) on the intracellular amount of GSH in Jurkat cells. *: $p < 0.05$; ns: non-significant (Student's t test). Detailed experimental description is provided above.

Study of the mechanism of death of A2780 cells induced by prodrug **2c** and controls

A2780 cells were seeded into 96 well culture plates at the same cell concentration and in the same medium as applied for the above described MTT assay (48 h incubation with the prodrugs). The next day, stock solutions of prodrugs of different concentrations (1 μ L, solvent DMSO, final concentrations in wells were 5, 10 and 30 μ M) or carrier only (DMSO, 1 μ L, final concentration 1 %, v/v) were added to the wells and incubated in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%). After 48 h supernatants were transferred into 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes and 100 μ L of DPBS was added to transfer supernatant residue into tube. Trypsin (0.25%, 50 μ L) was then added to well to detach the cells. All supernatants in Eppendorf tubes were combined back into wells. After gently pipetting up and down, 50 μ L of cell solutions was transferred into a new Eppendorf tube and incubated with 200 μ L of staining solution, consisting of Annexin A5-Fitc (5 μ L) and propidium iodide (PI, 330 ng) per 1 mL buffer (conc. 1X). The cells were incubated for 20 min at 22°C in dark and then put on ice followed by analysis using flow cytometry ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 530 \text{ nm}$ for Annexin A5-

Fitc and $\lambda_{em} = 664$ nm for PI). The cells negative for Annexin (Ax-) and propidium iodide (PI-) were considered viable. The cells positive for Annexin (Ax+) and negative for PI (PI-) were considered apoptotic. The cells positive for PI (PI+) were considered necrotic. (N=3, Figure S55).

Figure S55. Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of A2780 cell lines after 48 h incubation. Viable cells are indicated as Ax-/PI-, apoptotic as Ax+/PI- and necrotic as PI+.

Effect of prodrugs and controls on cellular organelles in A2780 cells: lysosomes (LY), endoplasmic reticulum (ER), Golgi (G) and mitochondria (Mit) (Figures 3, S56)

A2780 cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin in a 24-well microtiter plate (total volume 0.5 mL) at a density of 200 cells/ μ L one day before the experiment. On the day of the experiment, prodrugs (“LY/ER/G”-experiments: stock solution - 3 mM, 5 μ L, final concentration: 30 μ M; “Mit”-experiment: stock solutions - 0.5, 1 and 3 mM, 5 μ L, final concentrations: 5, 10, 30 μ M) or carrier only (DMSO, 1%, v/v) were added to cells and incubated for 1, 4 and 24 h in a dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5 %) at 37 °C. The cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with HBSS (Hanks' Balanced Salt solution, 500 μ L). Stock solutions of different dyes (5 μ L) were added: concentrations of the stock solutions were 4 mg/L for Acridine orange (AO), 10 mg/L for Rhodamine 123 (R123), 1 μ M for ER-Tracker-Green (ERG) and 10 μ M for Golgi-Staining-Green (GO). AO, R123, ERG were

dissolved in DMSO, whereas GO was dissolved in H₂O. Final concentrations of solutions were 40 µg/L for AO, 100 µg/L for R123, 0.01 µM for ERG and 0.1 µM for GO. The cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C for 20 min. Afterwards the supernatant was removed, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer twice and detached from the culture dish using trypsin/EDTA (0.025%/0.01%, v/v, 200 µL). Next, the cells were re-suspended in fresh medium. Finally, the fluorescence of live cells (the number of total events was 5000, λ_{ex} = 488 nm, λ_{em} = 530 nm) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (N=3, Figure 3, S56).

Figure **S56**. Effects of the prodrugs on mitochondria membrane potential (MMP) of A2780 cell lines after 1-48 h incubation. *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$, Student's t test. Non-labelled data are not significantly different ($p \geq 0.05$) from the corresponding reference (labelled on the plot).

reference
2c

Figure 3 A

Figure 3 B

Figure 3 C

Figure 3 D

2c
2c_c

Figure 5 A

Figure **S57**. Representative flow cytometric histograms used for setting up Figures 3A-D (main text) and 5A.

Monitoring total intracellular ROS (tROS)

A2780 cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin in a 24-well microtiter plate (total volume 0.5 mL) at a density of 200 cells/ μL one day before the experiment. On the day of the experiment, the cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with HBSS (Hanks' Balanced Salt solution, 500 μL). CM-DCFH-DA (5-(6-)chloromethyl-2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate, Thermo- Fisher) solution (0.1 mM in DMSO, 5 μL) was added (final concentration 1 μM) and the cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled with CO_2 (5%) at 37 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 min. Afterwards the supernatant was removed, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (500 μL) was added followed by addition of prodrugs (5 μL of stock solutions in DMSO, final concentration of prodrugs 5, 10 and 30 μM) or carrier only (DMSO, 5 μL , final concentration 1 %, v/v) and incubation for 2 h in the dark chamber filled with CO_2 (5%) at 37 $^\circ\text{C}$. Next, the cells were detached from the culture dish using trypsin/EDTA (0.025%/0.01%, v/v, 200 μL). The cells were re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (200 μL). Finally, the fluorescence of live cells ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 525 \text{ nm}$) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (Figure 4A, 5C). Intracellular ROS release in Jurkat cells was monitored analogously (Figure S58).

Figure S58. Effects of prodrugs **2c** and **5b** on the intracellular total ROS amount (tROS) in Jurkat cells. OY-axis "Fluorescence": the increase of the mean fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488$

nm, $\lambda_{em} = 525$ nm) of (CM-DCFH-DA)-loaded Jurkat cells incubated with the prodrugs for 1 h relative to that of the cells incubated with the carrier only. *: $p < 0.05$; ***: $p < 0.001$ (Student's t test with respect to the "carrier" probe: indicated with "reference" on the plot).

Figure 4 A

Figure 5 C

Figure **S59**. Representative flow cytometric histograms used for setting up Figures 4A and 5C.

Monitoring mitochondrial ROS (mROS)

A2780 cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin in a 96-well microtiter plate (total volume 0.1 mL) at a density of 250 cells/ μ L one day before the experiment. On the day of the experiment, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (100 μ L) was added followed by addition of compounds (1 μ L of stock solutions in DMSO, final concentration of the prodrugs was 5, 10 μ M and 30 μ M) or carrier only (DMSO, 1 μ L, final concentration 1 %, v/v) and incubation for 1 or 2 h in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C. After that, the cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with HBSS (Hanks' Balanced Salt solution, 50 μ L) containing MitoSOX (Red Mitochondrial Superoxide Indicator, Thermo-Fisher, Catalog number M36008, final concentration 5 μ M obtained by adding 0.5 μ L of the 0.5 mM stock solution of MitoSOX in DMSO to the HBSS)

and the cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C for 20 min. Next, the cells were detached from the culture dish using trypsin/EDTA (0.025%/0.01%, v/v, 50 µL). The cells were re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (100 µL). Finally, the fluorescence of live cells ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 578 \text{ nm}$) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (Figure 4B, 5D).

Figure 4 B

Figure 5 D

Figure **S60**. Representative flow cytometric histograms used for setting up Figures 4B and 5D.

Monitoring intracellular carbonyl derivatives

A2780 cells were seeded into 24 well culture plates at the same cell concentration and in the same medium as applied for the assay for monitoring tROS described above. The next day, stock solutions of prodrugs of different concentrations (5 µL of stock solutions in DMSO, final concentration of prodrugs 5 and 10 µM; control **7** 2 and 5 µM) or carrier only (DMSO, 5 µL, final concentration 1 %, v/v) were added to the wells and incubated in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%). After 24 h, the cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with HBSS (Hanks' Balanced Salt solution, 500 µL). 7-(Diethylamino)coumarin-3-carbohydrazide (DCCH) solution (8 mM in DMSO, 5 µL) was added (final concentration 80 µM) and the cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled

with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C for 2 h. Next, the cells were detached from the culture dish using trypsin/EDTA (0.025%/0.01%, v/v, 200 µL). The cells were re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (200 µL). Finally, the fluorescence of live cells ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 530 \text{ nm}$) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (Figure 4C).

Figure 4 C

Figure **S61**. Representative flow cytometric histograms used for setting up Figure 4C.

Generation of nitric oxide in A2780 cells

A2780 cells were seeded into 96 well culture plates at the same cell concentration and in the same medium as applied for the assay for monitoring mROS described above. On the day of the experiment, the cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with HBSS (100 µL). DAF-FM diacetate (4-Amino-5-Methylamino-2',7'-Difluorofluorescein Diacetate, Catalog number: D23844, Thermo-Fisher) solution (0.5 mM in DMSO, 1 µL) was added (final concentration 5 µM) and the cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C for 20 min. Afterwards the supernatant was removed, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (100 µL) was added followed by addition of prodrug or carrier only (DMSO, 1 µL, final concentration 1 %, v/v) and incubation for 2 h in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C. Next, the cells were detached from the culture dish using trypsin/EDTA (0.025%/0.01%, v/v, 50 µL).

The cells were re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (100 μ L). Finally, the fluorescence of live cells (λ_{ex} = 488 nm, λ_{em} = 530 nm) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (Figure S62).

Figure **S62**. Fluorescence of DAF-FM diacetate-loaded A2780 cells treated either with **2c** or the carrier. *: $p < 0.05$, Student's t test.

Effect of prodrug 2c on mitochondrial reactive oxygen species in representative cancer (A2780) and normal cells (SBLF9 fibroblasts) (Figure 6)

A2780 cells were seeded in of RPMI 1640 medium (500 μ L) supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin on a 35 mm imaging dish (μ - Dish 35 mm, high, ibidi GmbH, Germany) at a cell density of 80 cells/ μ L and allowed to attach to the surface of the dish for overnight. Next, N-acetylcysteine (NAC, 0.5 μ L, 5 mM in water, final concentration: 5 μ M) in fresh medium (0.5 mL, RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin) was added to replace old medium and incubated for 24 h at 37 $^{\circ}$ C and 5% CO_2 . Then prodrug (5 μ L, 0.5 mM in DMSO, final concentration: 5 μ M) or carrier (DMSO, 5 μ L, 1%, v/v) were added and incubated for 2 h under same conditions. The cells were washed with DPBS (2 x 2 mL) and MitoSOX (5 μ L, 0.5 mM in DMSO, final concentration: 5 μ M) in Hanks' Balanced Salt solution (0.5 mL) was added, followed by incubating for 20 min 37 $^{\circ}$ C and 5% CO_2 .

Afterwards, the cells were washed with DPBS and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (1 mL) was added. The fluorescence images were taken with a Zeiss Axio Vert.A1 fluorescence microscope (λ_{ex} : 538-562 nm; λ_{em} : 570-640 nm; Objective: 40x/1.30 Oil DIC).

For SBLF9 the same procedure was applied except that Ham's F-12K (Kaighn's)-Medium supplemented with 15 % FBS, 2 % non-essential amino acid mix, and 1 % penicillin/streptomycin was used for cell seeding and incubation with the prodrug or the carrier. A cell density of 40 cells/ μL was used.

Determination of viability of primary cancer (CLL) and normal (MNC) cells in the presence of prodrugs

Clinical samples from chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) patients (N=6, CLL cells) and healthy donors (N=6; peripheral blood mononuclear cells, MNCs) were collected at the University Hospital Heidelberg, Germany. Informed consent was obtained in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Sample collection and analysis was approved by the ethics committee of the University of Heidelberg (S-254/2016). Blood was separated by a Ficoll gradient (GE Healthcarey), and cells were cryopreserved. Drug sensitivity screening was performed in 384-well format (Greiner Bio One) with 10 different prodrug concentrations (30, 10, 3.3, 1.1, 0.37, 0.123, 0.041, 0.014, 0.005 and 0.002 μM) and 4×10^4 cells per well. Cells were cultured in RPMI-1640 (Invitrogen) supplemented with penicillin/streptomycin (Invitrogen), L-glutamine (Invitrogen) and 10% pooled and heat inactivated AB-type human serum (Sigma-Aldrich). Cell viability was assessed by quantification of ATP (CellTiter Glo®, Promega) 48 hours after drug application. Luminescence was measured on a Tecan Infinite F200 Microplate Reader. Viability was calculated as % of solvent (DMSO) treated control. Representative plots of cell viability versus prodrug concentration are provided in Figure 7.

Study of synergy of prodrugs with radiotherapy for SAS and FaDu cells

Optimization of concentration of prodrugs and controls / MTT assay

The MTT assay was also applied to assess the impact of various drugs (0.01-100 μM) on the viability of the two human head and neck squamous carcinoma cell (HNSCC) lines SAS and FaDu as well as retinal pigment epithelial ARPE-19 cells and human fibroblasts (HF). Cells were seeded into 96-well plates at concentrations of 4000 and 2000 cells per well, respectively, for the 24 h and 48 h treatment intervals, and were pre-cultured for 24 h before exposure to the drugs. All drug dilutions were prepared from 20 mM stock solutions in DMSO. The final DMSO concentration was set to 0.5% in all samples including control. After completion of the treatment, the wells were processed according to the routine MTT protocol as described above; the formazan absorbance was then measured on a Biotek Epoch Microplate Spectrophotometer at 590 nm and corrected for the background signal at 620 nm. $N \geq 3$ independent experiments were performed for each drug candidate, cell type and treatment interval. Cell survival was recorded as function of the drug concentration, and dose-response curves were fitted with the Boltzmann equation where appropriate. We calculated the half-maximal response (EC_{50}) as well as the EC_{20} (80% survival) according to the line curve (see Tables S6-S8). EC_{20} -values were used as a basis to select the compound-specific non-toxic drug concentrations for combination with radiotherapy. Figure S63 representatively documents the cell survival data for the 48 h exposure time.

Table **S6**. EC_{50} values (50% survival) in cancer SAS and FaDu cells determined via the MTT assay after 48 h of exposure to the prodrugs.

Compound	Cytotoxicity Assay (MTT) – 50% cell survival (EC_{50} in μM)			
	SAS		FaDu	
	24h	48h	24h	48h
2c	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)
5b	18.7 ± 4.7	5.8 ± 0.8	26.3 ± 3.4	19.8 ± 0.3
6	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)
7	1.7 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.3	1.5 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1

ⁱ ND= not detectable.

Table **S7**. EC₅₀ values (50% survival) in representative normal ARPE-19 and human fibroblasts (HF) cells determined via the MTT assay after 48 h of exposure to the prodrugs.

Compound	Cytotoxicity Assay (MTT) – 50% cell survival (EC ₅₀ in μM)			
	ARPE-19		human fibroblasts (HF)	
	24h	48h	24h	48h
2c	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)
5b	40.4 \pm 2.5	26.6 \pm 8.3	35.5 \pm 14.9	20.8 \pm 4.6
6	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)
7	2.0 \pm 0.4	1.7 \pm 0.2	1.7 \pm 0.2	1.6 \pm 0.3

ⁱ ND= not detectable.

Table **S8**. EC₂₀ values (80% survival) in cancer SAS and FaDu cells determined via the MTT assay after 24 h and 48 h of exposure to the prodrugs.ⁱ

Compound	80% cell survival (EC ₂₀ in μM)			
	SAS		FaDu	
	24h	48h	24h	48h
2c	ND (>50)	10.4 \pm 6.8	ND (>50)	18.0 \pm 5.1
5b	7.0 \pm 1.5	2.4 \pm 1.3	11.5 \pm 1.3	7.3 \pm 1.5
6	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)	ND (>50)
7	1.2 \pm 0.1	1.0 \pm 0.5	0.8 \pm 0.2	0.9 \pm 0.1

ⁱ ND= not detectable.

Figure **S63**. Representative experimental data showing relative survival as function of drug concentration in two HNSCC cell lines and two normal cell lines as determined via the MTT assays upon 48 h of exposure to various aminoferrocene-based prodrugs (mean values \pm SD from $N \geq 3$ independent experiments are documented); where possible, dose-response curves were fitted with a Boltzmann equation.

Optimization of concentration of prodrugs and controls / clonogenic assay

The clonogenic survival assay is a classical approach to monitor radioresponse and drug-induced radiosensitization in cancer cells. We therefore initially determined whether the supposedly non-toxic drug concentrations defined for combinatorial treatment testing affect single cell colony formation capacity. For this purpose, exponentially growing SAS and FaDu cells were dissociated, single cell suspensions were prepared in standard DMEM and seeded in 6-well plates at

defined low density (150-300 cells in 1 ml per well). After 8 h of incubation to allow cell adherence, 50% of the supernatant was exchanged by media containing the respective prodrugs at 2x concentration and exposed for 48 h. Treatment was then terminated by medium removal, and cells were allowed to grow for a period of ≥ 5 -6 cell divisions estimated from the cell line-specific doubling times of the respective untreated controls (~ 7 days for SAS and ~ 10 days for FaDu cells). Control cells were always handled in parallel to the treated cells and thus exposed to the corresponding DMSO concentration(s). After the defined growth intervals, cells were fixed, stained and colonies of > 50 cells were manually counted at low magnification to calculate plating efficiencies as the number of counted colonies relative to the number of seeded cells. Drug effect on clonogenic survival was then estimated by normalizing the colony formation of control cells to 1 (Table S9).

The colony formation assay was also applied for monitoring radioresponse. Here, increasing numbers of single cells relative to the irradiation dose (0-10 Gy) were seeded into 6-well plates (150-2400 SAS cells/well and 300-4800 FaDu cells/well). Cells were treated with the drugs upon attachment as described. The total period of drug exposure was 48 h, and single dose irradiation was carried out 24 h after addition of the compounds. X-ray was performed at room temperature with a YxlonY.TU 320 system (Yxlon.international, 200 kV, 0.5 mm Cu filter) and a dose rate of ~ 1.3 Gy/min. Drug exposure was terminated by medium exchange and cultures were then incubated for the additional time period highlighted earlier. Plating efficiencies were assessed and normalized for each treatment arm to the respective unirradiated control. Data were reproduced (N=3 each with n=3 wells per experiment and treatment condition). The relative clonogenic cell survival (= survival fraction, SF) was then plotted as function of the irradiation dose, and clonogenic survival curves were fitted employing the linear quadratic model as described elsewhere.^[S4] All results are summarized in Table S9.

Table **S9**. Effects of the prodrugs on the capacity of SAS and FaDu cells to form colonies; data are given relative to untreated control cells (= relative clonogenic survival) and are documented as means \pm SD from N=3 independent experiments.

Compound	Concentration (μ M)	Relative clonogenic survival	
		SAS	FaDu
2c	10	0.78 \pm 0.13	0.86 \pm 0.13
	25	0.70 \pm 0.10	0.20 \pm 0.08
5b	0.5	0.96 \pm 0.06	0.71 \pm 0.07
	1	0.76 \pm 0.06	0.75 \pm 0.11
	2.5	0.36 \pm 0.15	0.36 \pm 0.10
6	25	0.88 \pm 0.10	0.99 \pm 0.08
7	0.1	0.94 \pm 0.12	0.97 \pm 0.10

N=3; \sum n=9

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Prodrugs

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An Endoplasmic Reticulum Specific Pro-amplifier of Reactive Oxygen Species in Cancer Cells

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Abstract: The folding and export of proteins and hydrolysis of unfolded proteins are disbalanced in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) of cancer cells, leading to so-called ER stress. Agents further augmenting this effect are used as anticancer drugs including clinically approved proteasome inhibitors bortezomib and carfilzomib. However, these drugs can affect normal cells, which also rely strongly on ER functions, leading, for example, to accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). To address this problem, we have developed ER-targeted prodrugs activated only in cancer cells in the presence of elevated ROS amounts. These compounds are conjugates of cholic acid with N-alkylaminoferrrocene-based prodrugs. We confirmed their accumulation in the ER of cancer cells, their anticancer efficacy, and cancer cell specificity. These prodrugs induce ER stress, attenuate mitochondrial membrane potential, and generate mitochondrial ROS leading to cell death via necrosis. We also demonstrated that the new prodrugs are activated in vivo in Nemeth-Kellner lymphoma (NK/Ly) murine model.

According to estimation of European Cancer Information System (ECIS) in the European Union 1.3 millions of people will die from cancer and over 2.7 million of new cases (excluding non-melanoma skin cancer) will be diagnosed in 2020.^[1] Treatment of this disease is complicated, since cancer and normal cells are related and, correspondingly, precise targeting/killing of the former cells without affecting of the latter ones is a challenging and not yet fully solved problem. In particular, currently available, clinically approved chemo-

therapeutics exhibit dose-limiting side effects, which adversely and sometimes irreversibly affect the quality of life of patients.^[2] Cancer cells can be addressed specifically by making use of their unique features, for example, the presence of some overexpressed receptors,^[3] altered glycolysis,^[4] and elevated amounts of reactive oxygen species (ROS = H₂O₂, O₂^{•-} and HO[•]).^[5,6] The endoplasmic reticulum (ER) has been recognized as an especially attractive target due to the following reasons.^[7] In cancer cells the balance between folding/transport of proteins and degradation of misfolded proteins is disturbed that leads to the so called ER stress. Further potentiation of the stress by chemical agents induces cancer cell death, whereas normal cells initially lacking the ER stress withstand the drug effect. Though some cancer cell selectivity can be achieved, side effects are also expected. They include, but not limited to induction of moderate ER stress in normal cells leading to unfolded protein response (UPR), elevation of intracellular amounts of ROS and disbalance of Ca²⁺ homeostasis. All these factors contribute to genome instability that stimulate carcinogenesis.^[8]

Herein we addressed this problem by the development of ER targeting prodrugs **4a-g**, which are activated only in cancer cells, but remain inactive in normal cells (Scheme 1, Scheme 2). These compounds are based on N-substituted aminoferrrocene (AF) drugs. After their formation in cells these drugs cycle between reduced (AF) and oxidized (AF⁺) forms catalyzing the formation of highly reactive ROS O₂^{•-} (from O₂) and HO[•] (from H₂O₂) that leads to cell death.^[9]

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Scheme 1. The mechanism of activation of AF-based prodrugs and state-of-the-art in the targeting of these prodrugs to organelles in cancer cells.

Scheme 2. Structures of AF prodrugs targeting ER (**4a-g**) and control compounds.

These and other ferrocene-based biologically active compounds were described in several recent reviews.^[10] The AF's are protected in prodrugs **4** with a 4-(carbonyloxymethyl)-phenylboronic acid pinacol ester group.^[9] The latter group is labile under oxidative conditions and was, therefore, expected to be cleaved especially well within the ER of cancer cells, which is known to have more oxidative environment than the cytoplasm.^[11]

Our research group has substantial experience with AF-based prodrugs. We have previously investigated their mode of action^[9,12] and developed compounds targeting lysosomes (LY)^[13] and mitochondria (Mit)^[14] in cancer cells (Scheme 1). However, ER specific AF-prodrugs were not available before this work. P. Cloetens, G. Jaouen and S. Bohic have recently reported on anticancer osmocenyl-tamoxifen prodrugs, which are accumulated in endomembrane system of breast cancer MDA-MB-231 cells including, apart from ER, nuclear envelope, endosomes and lysosomes.^[15] Another example of an ER-targeting prodrug is disulfiram. Its mode of action

relies on the activation by binding of Cu ions in cells. Apart from inducing ER stress via proteasome inhibition and ROS production,^[16] it affects other targets including inhibition of aldehyde dehydrogenase (ALDH) and the STAT3 signaling pathway,^[17] modulation of DNA-topoisomerases and methyltransferases as well as glutathione S-transferase.^[18] Thus, the known anticancer prodrugs are not ER specific.

Previously reported ER-carriers are usually hydrophobic structures, for example, cyanine dye DiOC6, hexyl rhodamine B, polyethylene glycol (PEG), long alkyl chains, derivatives of p-methylphenylsulfonamides.^[19] Since water solubility of AF-prodrugs is limited ($\leq 50 \mu M$),^[9,12-14] their further modification with the known ER-carriers would with high probability lead to non-soluble in water compounds. Therefore, we searched for alternative modifiers. We selected bile acids, since along with their hydrophobic core, they carry polar groups (alcohol or carbonyl), which could provide for water solubility. To find the best modifier, we introduced a series of bile acid fragments (substituent R, Scheme 2) to obtain prodrugs **4a-4e** as described in the supporting information (SI). We were pleased to observe that all prepared prodrugs are soluble at least up to $50 \mu M$ in aqueous solution (Table S1, SI). All prodrugs affect the viability of Burkitt's lymphoma BL-2 cells (Table S2, SI), selected as a representative cancer cell line. Derivatives of cholic (**4a**, $IC_{50} = 9 \pm 2 \mu M$) and dehydrocholic acid (**4e**, $IC_{50} = 9 \pm 2 \mu M$) are most potent in this series. They exhibit a stronger anticancer effect than the non-targeted control **1**^[9] ($IC_{50} = 34 \pm 3 \mu M$, $p < 0.001$) and the Mit-targeting prodrug **3**^[14] ($IC_{50} = 35 \pm 2 \mu M$, $p < 0.001$) reaching the potency of the best previously reported LY-targeting prodrug **2**^[13] ($IC_{50} = 5 \pm 2 \mu M$). Based on these data and due to its easier synthesis, prodrug **4a** was selected for more detailed studies.

As previously established, prodrugs containing arylboronic acid pinacol ester are hydrolyzed in aqueous buffered at pH 7 solutions within ≤ 1 h.^[20] Therefore, the active form of **4a** will be the boronic acid **4a_BA**. We determined n-octanol/water partition coefficient ($\log P$) of **4a_BA** to be substantially higher (5.9 ± 0.2 , Table S3, SI) than that of parent prodrug **1_BA** (2.7 ± 0.2). The high lipophilicity of **4a_BA** was expected to facilitate its accumulation in the ER.^[19]

To investigate the mechanism of **4a** activation in the presence of H_2O_2 , we applied electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectrometry (MS). We confirmed that **4a** is first hydrolyzed in aqueous solution forming **4a_BA**. In the presence of H_2O_2 AF-drug **4a_2** is formed (Figures S29–S34, SI), which can donate an electron to H_2O_2/O_2 leading to formation of ferrocenium **4a_2⁺** and highly toxic $HO^{\bullet}/O_2^{\bullet-}$. We confirmed experimentally formation of $HO^{\bullet}/O_2^{\bullet-}$ in mixtures of **4a** and H_2O_2 by using 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein (DCFH) (Figure S35, Table S4, SI). In particular, we found that **4a** accelerates the rate of DCFH oxidation by 3.2-fold with respect to the rate of its spontaneous oxidation by H_2O_2 . All together these data indicate that **4a** is activated as outlined in Scheme 1 similarly to other known AF-prodrugs.^[9,12-14]

Further, we confirmed that apart from BL-2 cells prodrug **4a** exhibits anticancer activity towards other cancer cell lines including ovarian cancer A2780 ($IC_{50} = 5.4 \pm 0.7 \mu M$) and T-

cell leukemia Jurkat ($IC_{50} = 18 \pm 1 \mu\text{M}$). The anticancer activity of LY-targeting prodrug **2**^[13] is similar towards A2780 cells ($IC_{50} = 7 \pm 2 \mu\text{M}$) and higher towards Jurkat cells ($IC_{50} = 7.2 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{M}$, $p < 0.001$), whereas that of Mit-targeting **3**^[14] is substantially lower for both cell lines ($p < 0.001$, Tables S5, S6, SI). For Jurkat cells we observed that **4a** induces cell death mainly via necrosis and partially via apoptosis (Figure S36A, SI) that was reproduced for A2780 cells (Figure S37, SI). Since necrotic cells are usually immunogenic, it is possible that the initial direct anticancer effect of **4a** will be facilitated by the action of immune system in vivo. We observed that the anticancer activity of **4a** in Jurkat cells is decreased in the presence of the ROS inhibitor N-acetylcysteine (NAC)^[21] (Figure S36B, SI). These data confirm that ROS is involved in the intracellular activation of **4a**.

Next, we investigated the mechanism of action of **4a** in cells. In the first experiment, we incubated A2780 cells with prodrug **4a** as well as controls **1** and **2** for time periods between 1–24 h followed by their staining with organelle-specific dyes (ER: ER-tracker-green, ERTgrn; LY: acridine orange, AO; Golgi: Golgi-Staining-Green, GO; Mit: rhodamine 123, R123) and evaluation of their fluorescence by using flow cytometry (Figure 1). The fluorescence intensity of the cells treated with medium only (carrier) was used as a reference. We observed that non-targeted control **1** weakly affects the ER-specific fluorescence at 1 h incubation (but not at 4 h incubation) and does not affect the LY-, Golgi- and Mit-specific fluorescence at both 1 and 4 h incubation times. A weak decrease of the Mit-specific fluorescence was observed at the highest incubation time of 24 h. As expected, LY-targeted **2** strongly reduces the LY-specific fluorescence of the cells. Additionally, it also affects ER and especially Mit that can be a follow up effect after the initial lysosomal disruption as previously reported.^[13] The effect of **4a** on the ER-specific

fluorescence of the cells for both 1 and 4 h incubation times was found to be strongest within the studied series of the prodrugs ($p < 0.001$, Figure 1A). Using confocal microscopy we observed that the ER tracker dye is leaking into the nuclei and the cytoplasm of a large proportion of **4a**-treated cells indicating that **4a** induces the ER disruption (Figure S38). In contrast to **2**, prodrug **4a** does not affect the LY-specific signal (Figure 1B), but at the early incubation time (1 h) decreases slightly the Golgi-specific fluorescence and does not affect the Mit-specific fluorescence. At the later incubation times the effects on Golgi and Mit become stronger. These data indicate that the ER is a primary site of action for **4a** (the strong effect is seen already at 1h-incubation), whereas the effects on Golgi and Mit are secondary (≥ 4 h incubation is needed to observe strong effects).

By using quantitative PCR, we observed that the expression of mRNA of CCAAT-enhancer-binding protein homologous protein (CHOP), which is a marker of the ER stress,^[22] is significantly increased in **4a**-treated A2780 cells ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, neither unspecific **1** nor LY-targeting **2** affected the expression of the CHOP-mRNA (Table S7, SI). These data indicate that **4a** exhibits its anticancer activity via the induction of the ER stress.

Next, we evaluated the ability of **4a** to modulate the oxidative stress in cells (Figure 2A,B). We observed that this prodrug increases the total intracellular ROS amount (tROS)

Figure 1. Effect of prodrugs and controls on relative organelle-specific staining ($F_i(\text{prodrug})/F_i(\text{carrier})$), where F is emission at 525 nm ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488$ nm). Incubation times with prodrugs (1, 4, or 24 h) are indicated on the plots. A) ER staining with ERTgrn. B) LY staining with AO. C) Golgi staining with GO. D) Mit staining with R123. References are indicated with “ref”. The experimental data were compared by using Student’s t test: $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), $p < 0.001$ (***), $p \geq 0.05$ (ns).

Figure 2. A) Increase of the mean fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 530$ nm) of 5-(6-(6-chloromethyl)-2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (CM-DCFH-DA)-loaded cells incubated with **4a** for 2 h (A2780 and BL-2 cells) or 1 h (Jurkat cells). B) Increase of the mean fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 585$ nm) of A2780 cells incubated with **4a** for 2 h followed by MitosoxTM for 20 min. C–K) Images of A2780 cells stained with **4g** (C–E), ERTred (F–H), and a mixture of **4g** and ERTred (I–K). Fluorescent channels: $Ch1$ (green)— $\lambda_{\text{ex}}: 335$ – 383 nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}}: 420$ – 470 nm (detection of **4g**); $Ch2$ (red)— $\lambda_{\text{ex}}: 538$ – 562 nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}}: 570$ – 640 nm (detection of ERTred).

in all studied cell lines significantly. However, the overall magnitude of the tROS increase was substantially lower than that found for LY-targeting **2**.^[13] In contrast, we observed the strong dose-dependent increase of mitochondrial ROS (mROS) in A2780 cells treated with **4a**, whereas control **2** did not affect mROS at any concentration tested (0–30 μM). Thus, the mode of action of **4a** (the induction of ER stress, the increase of mROS) is distinct from that implicated for all previously known AF-prodrugs.^[9,12–14,20]

To find out whether **4a** is directly accumulated in ER or induces its effects on the ER indirectly, we prepared its fluorogenic analogue **4g** containing a fluorescent dye 7-hydroxycoumarin (*SI*). We confirmed that **4g** and **4a** are analogues. For example, they have similar solubility in aqueous solution (Table S1, *SI*), lipophilicity (Table S3, *SI*) and exhibit similar anticancer activity towards A2780 cells ($\text{IC}_{50} = 6.2 \pm 2.4$ vs. $\text{IC}_{50} = 5.4 \pm 0.7$ μM correspondingly).

Prodrug **4g** is practically not fluorescent due to photo-induced electron transfer (PET) from the ferrocene moiety to the dye. Analogously to **4a**, it is converted to AF-drug **4g.2⁺** in the presence of H_2O_2 (Figure S29, S30) that is accompanied by the strong (up to 50-fold) fluorescence increase (Figure S39). We found that **4g** is accumulated and activated in A2780 cells leading to formation of fluorescent products (most probably **4g.2⁺**) that could be monitored by flow cytometry (Figure S40, Table S9). By using fluorescence microscopy we confirmed that the fluorescent product derived from **4g** is accumulated in ER (Figure 2C–K). This is evident from the efficient overlap (Pearson's R value = 0.85, Figure S41, *SI*) of the signal of the fluorescent product **4g.2⁺** derived from **4g** (green color) and the signal of ER-specific stain ERTred (red color, Figure 2K). It should be mentioned that previously reported fluorogenic versions of LY-targeting **2**^[13] and Mit-targeting **3**^[14] are substantially less active than their unlabeled counterparts. These compounds are suitable for the study of the mechanism of prodrug action, but not as therapeutic agents. In contrast, **4g** is the first truly teranostic AF-based prodrug.

To evaluate the cancer cell specificity of the ER-targeting AF-prodrugs, we conducted two complementary experiments. For the first one we selected a pair of genetically related primary cancer (chronic lymphocytic leukemia: CLL) and normal cells (mononuclear cells: MNC's). MNC's is a mixture of cells containing primary B cells, which are parent for CLL cells. We observed that **4a** is significantly more toxic towards CLL cells ($\text{IC}_{50} = 5.6 \pm 0.7$ μM) than normal MNC's ($\text{IC}_{50} = 18.3 \pm 7.5$ μM , $p < 0.05$) (Figure S42, *SI*). Furthermore, by using fluorescence microscopy we confirmed that **4g** (the fluorogenic analogue of **4a**) is activated only in cancer (A2780), but not in normal (SBLF9 fibroblasts) cells (Figure S43, *SI*). We selected the SBLF9 cells as representative normal cells, since they are adherent and, therefore, better suitable for the fluorescence microscopy than the non-adherent MNC's.

Finally, we evaluated the activation of **4g** in vivo in C57/BL6N mice with Nemeth-Kellner lymphoma (NK/Ly), which grow in the form of ascites (*SI*). First, we took ascite probes from untreated mice (time point 0) as a reference. Then prodrug **4g** at the dose of 40 mg kg^{-1} was injected i.p. every

Figure 3. A) Photograph of ascite suspensions isolated from C57/BL6N mice carrying NK/Ly and treated with **4g** for 3 days. B) Increase of the mean fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 340\text{--}380$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 435\text{--}485$ nm) of ascites isolated from the C57/BL6N mice treated with **4g** for 0, 3 h and 3 days: circles: individual data, horizontal bars: means of the individual data. Student's t test: ** – $p < 0.01$; *** – $p < 0.001$; the untreated sample was used as a reference. C) Bright-field images of ascites isolated from the C57/BL6N mice treated with **4g** for 3 days. D, E) Fluorescence image of the same cells as in (C): $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 290\text{--}410$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 415\text{--}465$ nm (D) and $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 530\text{--}570$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 570\text{--}650$ nm (E). F) Overlay of images shown in (D) (green color) and (E) (red color). G–J) Controls; the same as (C–F) for untreated ascites.

day for 3 days. Ascite probes were taken 3 h and 3 days after the beginning of the treatment. The cell suspensions appeared yellow indicating the prodrug uptake (Figure 3A). Furthermore, the fluorescence of ascites ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 360/20$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 460/25$ nm) was quantified by using a fluorescence plate reader (*SI*). We observed the significant ($p < 0.01$ for 3 h incubation and $p < 0.001$ for 3 days incubation) time-dependent fluorescence increase in the treated animals compared to the non-treated ones (Figure 3B) that is in agreement with the activation of **4g** in vivo. These results were confirmed by imaging of the live ascites by using vital fluorescence microscopy (3 days incubation, Figure 1C–J). In particular, we imaged the cells at two settings (Ch1 and Ch2), which allowed detecting the products of **4g** activation (Ch1: $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 290\text{--}410$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 415\text{--}465$ nm) and the ER-tracking dye ERTred (Ch2: $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 530\text{--}570$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 570\text{--}650$ nm, added to the isolated ascites shortly before the measurements). For the ascites from the treated group we observed an intense signal in the Ch1 indicating the **4g** activation. The latter signal overlaps with that in the Ch2 indicating that **4g** is accumulated and activated in the ER of the ascites in vivo. As expected, no signal in the Ch1 was observed in the ascites isolated from the control (untreated) group. These data are in agreement with our in vitro studies (Figure 2C–K).

In summary, we successfully prepared cholic acid-conjugated AF-prodrug **4a** as well as its fluorogenic version **4g**, which is the first reported teranostic AF-prodrug. We demonstrated fast (≤ 1 h incubation) accumulation and activation of these prodrugs in the ER of cancer cells that leads to the significant ER stress (upregulation of CHOP-mRNA) and the production of both mitochondrial and total ROS. We have confirmed the excellent cancer cell specificity of prodrugs **4a/4g** and demonstrated that **4g** is efficiently activated in vivo in the NK/Ly murine model. The prodrugs **4a/4g** described in this paper and the previously reported LY-targeting **2**^[13] exhibit comparable anticancer effects. However, due to different mechanisms of action, these drugs are

complementary to each other. We assume that **4a/4g** may find applications in cases when **2** is not suitable. Furthermore, the simultaneous use of these prodrugs would be an interesting option due to the possible synergistic effects between them.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords: aminoferrocene · cancer · endoplasmic reticulum · prodrugs · reactive oxygen species

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Supporting Information

An Endoplasmic Reticulum Specific Pro-amplifier of Reactive Oxygen Species in Cancer Cells

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General Information

Commercially available chemicals of the best quality from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany) were obtained and used without purification. Golgi-Staining-Green (BODIPY FL C5-ceramide complexed to BSA, catalog: B22650, Invitrogen™), ER-Tracker-Green (BODIPY™ FL Glibenclamide, catalog: E34251, Invitrogen™), ER-Tracker-Red (BODIPY® TR Glibenclamide, catalog: E34250, Invitrogen™), MitoSOX™ Red (mitochondrial superoxide indicator, catalog: M36008, Invitrogen™) and Dead Cell Apoptosis Kit (Molecular Probes™ V13245) were obtained from Fisher Scientific. NMR spectra were acquired on a Bruker Avance 300 or a Bruker Avance 400 spectrometer. Electrospray ionization (ESI) or atmospheric pressure photoionization (APPI) mass spectra were recorded on a Bruker ESI MicroTOF II focus or a Bruker maXis 4G. UV-visible spectra were measured on a Cary 100 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies) by using quartz glass cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL. Fluorescence spectra were acquired on a Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer using fluorescence cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL. The fluorescence of live cells was quantified using a Guava easyCyte™ 6-2L Flow cytometer from Merck Millipore or CytoFlex from Beckman Coulter, Inc. The data were processed using the inCyte™ software package from Merck Millipore. The microscopy images were taken with a Zeiss Axio Vert.A1 microscope. The purity of the prodrugs used in the biological assays was determined by elemental analysis (C, H, and N analysis). This analysis was performed in the microanalytical laboratory of the chemical institutes of the Friedrich-Alexander-University of Erlangen-Nürnberg, Erlangen, Germany. According to obtained data, the purity of all new compounds was greater than 95%.

Synthesis

Previously known prodrugs **1**, **2** and **3** (main text, Scheme 1) were synthesized as described elsewhere.¹⁻⁴

Intermediate **S1**

AF-prodrug **1** (100 mg, 0.22 mmol) was dissolved in N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 0.65 mL) and cesium carbonate (212 mg, 0.65 mmol) and tetrabutylammonium iodide (TBAI, 40 mg, 0.11 mmol) were added. The mixture obtained was stirred for 0.5 h at 23 °C followed by adding 1,3-bis(chloromethyl)benzene (228 mg, 1.3 mmol). The mixture was stirred overnight. DMF was distilled from the yellow mixture by using rotary evaporator at 60 °C. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, eluent: dichloromethane, $R_f = 0.66$). Pure intermediate **S1** was obtained as yellow oil (60 mg, 0.10 mmol, yield: 45%). ^1H NMR (300 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 7.73$ (d, $J=7.4$, 2H), 7.54 – 7.12 (m, 6H), 5.27 (d, $J=15.4$, 2H), 5.02 (s, 2H), 4.69 (d, $J=8.3$, 2H), 4.54 – 4.31 (m, 2H), 4.12 (s, 5H), 4.04 – 3.91 (m, 2H), 1.33 (s, 12H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 155.28, 140.95, 140.68, 139.27, 135.75, 129.86, 128.33, 128.14, 127.69, 127.44, 102.51, 84.69, 69.89, 68.02, 65.24, 63.40, 54.29, 46.96, 25.34$. HRMS (ESI): calcd for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{35}\text{BClFeNO}_4$ ($[\text{M-e}]^+$): 599.1692; found m/z : 599.1691.

Prodrug **4a**

Cholic acid (122 mg, 0.30 mmol) and cesium carbonate (97.8 mg, 0.30 mmol) were suspended in DMF (0.3 mL) and stirred for 30 min. Intermediate **S1** (60 mg, 0.10 mmol) dissolved in DMF (0.3 mL) was added. The mixture was stirred for 15 h at 60 °C. DMF was distilled from the yellow mixture by at 60 °C *in vacuo* (0.01 mbar). The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, ethyl acetate, $R_f = 0.29$). The oily product was dissolved in ethyl acetate (1 mL) and precipitated by adding iso-hexane (10 mL) under stirring. The precipitate was filtered and dried *in vacuo* (0.01 mbar) to obtain prodrug **4a** as light yellow powder (54 mg, 0.06 mmol, yield: 56%). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) $\delta = 7.73$ (s, 2H), 7.51 – 7.03 (m, 6H), 5.20 (s, 2H), 5.08 (s, 2H), 4.96 (s, 2H), 4.39 (s, 2H), 4.11 (s, 5H), 4.02 – 3.96 (m, 2H), 3.94 (s, 1H), 3.81 (d, $J=2.3$, 1H), 3.39 (dt, $J=15.2$, 5.4, 1H), 2.50 – 0.91 (m, 46H, overlapped with water peak), 0.88 (s, 3H), 0.66 (s, 3H). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, Pyridine- d_5) $\delta = 8.05$ (d, $J=7.0$, 2H), 7.40 (d, $J=6.5$, 4H), 5.62 (d, $J=5.3$, 1H), 5.40 (s, 2H), 5.38 (d, $J=4.3$, 1H), 5.33 (d, $J=3.2$, 1H), 5.26 (s, 2H), 5.16 (s, 2H), 4.67 (s, 2H), 4.22 (s, 6H), 4.11 (s, 1H), 4.02 (s, 2H), 3.76 (d, $J=4.9$, 1H), 3.14 (d, $J=11.5$, 1H), 2.94 (d, $J=3.9$, 1H), 2.76 (d, $J=7.2$, 1H), 2.58 – 2.23 (m, 3H), 2.20 – 0.91 (m, 36H), 0.80 (s, 3H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) $\delta = 174.35$, 155.43, 140.04, 139.68, 137.41, 135.34, 129.29, 127.54, 127.27, 126.52, 126.47, 102.00, 84.41, 73.48, 72.38, 69.56, 68.92, 68.03, 66.38, 65.04, 63.20, 54.40, 47.64, 46.99, 42.34, 42.14, 40.29, 40.13, 35.79, 35.24, 31.84, 31.48, 31.20, 28.84, 27.99, 27.07, 25.23, 23.72, 22.87, 17.72, 12.83. HRMS (ESI+): calcd for $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{74}\text{BFeNO}_9$ ($[\text{M}-\text{e}]^+$): 971.4801; found m/z : 971.4796. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{74}\text{BFeNO}_9$: C 69.21, H 7.68, N 1.44; found: C 69.13, H 7.52, N 1.32.

Prodrugs **4b-4e** were prepared analogously to **4a** according to the following general procedure

Bile acid (1.5 eq.) and cesium carbonate (3 eq.) were dissolved/suspended in DMF (0.268 mmol of bile acid per 4 mL DMF) and stirred for 30 min at 23 °C under argon atmosphere. Then intermediate **S1** (1 eq) dissolved in DMF (0.134 mmol/mL) was added dropwise and the mixture was stirred overnight at 40 °C under argon atmosphere. The mixture was filtered, DMF was evaporated under high vacuum (0.01 mbar) and the residual crude product was purified on preparative TLC plates (dichloromethane/MeOH – 9:1, v/v) to afford yellow solid products in 40-60% yield.

Prodrug 4b (a derivative of deoxycholic acid)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 0.70 (s, 3H), 0.95 (s, 3H), 1.02 (d, J = 6.4 Hz, 3H), 1.38 (s, 12H), 0.87-2.49 (m, steroid fingerprint), 3.39 (d, J = 4.4 Hz, 1H), 3.51 (d, J = 4.4 Hz, 1H), 4.01-4.04 (m, 2H), 4.16 (s, 5H), 4.50 (bp, 2H), 5.06 (s, 2H), 5.13 (s, J = 2.7 Hz, 2H), 5.29 (s, 2H), 7.28-7.45 (m, 6H), 7.71-7.79 (m, 2H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 13.84, 18.27, 24.48, 25.99, 27.93, 28.89, 29.03, 32.04, 32.51, 32.63, 35.05, 35.72, 36.89, 37.01, 37.78, 38.17, 43.88, 48.09, 48.30, 49.52, 65.85, 66.98, 70.52, 72.44, 73.70, 85.33, 127.71, 128.31, 130.27, 136.38, 138.81, 141.06, 141.62, 174.72 ppm. MS (ESI+): calcd for $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{74}\text{BFeNO}_8$ ($[\text{M}-\text{e}]^+$): 955.4857; found 955.4860. Elemental analysis: calcd. for $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{74}\text{BFeNO}_8 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (%): C, 69.07, H, 7.87, N, 1.44, found: C, 69.21, H, 8.10, N, 1.36.

Prodrug 4c (a derivative of chemodeoxycholic acid)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 0.70 (s, 3H), 0.95 (s, 3H), 0.96 (d, J = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 1.38 (s, 12H), 0.88-2.48 (m, steroid fingerprint), 3.20 (d, J = 3.2 Hz, 1H), 3.37 (s, 1H), 4.00-4.04 (m, 2H), 4.16 (s, 5H), 4.50 (s, 2H), 5.05 (s, 2H), 5.14 (s, J = 3.3 Hz, 2H), 5.29 (s, 2H), 7.29-7.48 (m, 6H), 7.74-7.82 (m, 2H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 12.98, 19.48, 22.17, 24.14, 25.03, 25.98, 29.6, 32.44, 1, 32.44, 32.61, 34.40, 36.64, 36.70, 36.92, 37.19, 41.24, 41.44, 41.57, 43.61, 43.98, 51.98, 57.55, 65.86, 67.02, 68.85, 70.52, 72.86, 85.33, 122.70, 127.75, 128.33, 128.70, 130.27, 136.38, 138.78, 141.05, 141.62, 174.68 ppm. MS (ESI+): calcd for $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{74}\text{BFeNO}_8$ ($[\text{M}-\text{e}]^+$): 955.4857; found 955.4861. Elemental analysis: calcd. for $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{74}\text{BFeNO}_8 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (%): C, 69.07, H, 7.87, N, 1.44, found: C, 69.40, H, 8.10, N, 1.57.

Prodrug 4d (a derivative of lithocholic acid)

^1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 0.70 (s, 3H), 1.38 (s, 12H), 0.91-2.48 (m, steroid fingerprint), 3.53 (s, 1H), 4.00-4.04 (m, 2H), 4.16 (s, 5H), 4.50 (s, 2H), 5.05 (s, 2H), 5.14 (s, J = 4.6 Hz, 2H), 5.29 (s, 2H), 7.29-7.47 (m, 6H), 7.73-7.82 (m, 2H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 13.21, 19.46, 22.33, 24.68, 25.66, 25.98, 28.05, 28.82, 29.59, 32.23, 32.37, 32.55, 36.10, 36.80, 37.05, 37.49, 38.22, 41.76, 42.09, 43.80, 44.24, 57.54, 58.07, 65.84, 67.01, 70.52, 72.39, 85.32, 127.71, 128.35, 128.69, 130.27, 136.39, 138.74,

141.06, 141.65, 174.66 ppm. MS (ESI+): calcd for $C_{56}H_{74}BFeNO_7$ ($[M-e]^{+}$): 939.4908; 939.4912. Elemental analysis: calcd. for $C_{56}H_{74}BFeNO_7$ (%): C, 71.57, H, 7.94, N, 1.49, found: C, 71.44, H, 8.22, N, 1.35.

Prodrug **4e** (a derivative of dehydrocholic acid)

1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 0.70 (s, 3H), 1.38 (s, 12H), 0.81-3.21 (m, steroid fingerprint), 4.02 (s, 2H), 4.16 (s, 5H), 4.50 (s, 2H), 5.05 (s, 2H), 5.14 (s, J = 3.7 Hz, 2H), 5.29 (s, 2H), 7.29-7.50 (m, 6H), 7.72-7.82 (m, 2H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 12.84, 19.93, 22.73, 25.97, 26.00, 26.41, 29.06, 32.24, 32.77, 36.65, 37.02, 37.55, 37.76, 40.02, 44.14, 46.34, 46.42, 47.40, 48.22, 50.13, 53.41, 58.25, 65.84, 67.01, 70.51, 75.54, 85.32, 127.74, 128.34, 130.25, 136.37, 138.72, 141.04, 141.61, 174.55, 209.70, 210.17, 212.82 ppm. MS (ESI+): calcd for $C_{56}H_{68}BFeNO_9$ ($[M-e]^{+}$): 965.4336; found: 965.4342. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $C_{56}H_{74}BFeNO_9 \cdot xH_2O$: C, 68.37, H, 7.17, N, 1.42, found: C, 68.64, H, 7.31, N, 1.48.

Intermediate **S3**

N,N,N-Triethylamine (Et₃N, 1.81 g, 2.48 mL, 17.87 mmol) followed by methanesulfonyl chloride (MsCl, 2.05 g, 1.38 mmol) were added to a solution of compound **S2** (1.26 g, 7.77 mmol, synthesized by using a protocol reported elsewhere⁵) in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (35 mL) under nitrogen atmosphere. Then reaction mixture was heated at 45 °C for 16 h, water (250 mL) was added and the resulting mixture was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (2 x 200 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, cyclohexane/ethyl acetate 18:1) to give a yellowish liquid (1.30 g, 85%). TLC (silica gel, eluent cyclohexane/ethyl acetate 10:1, R_f = 0.57). 1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 7.51 – 7.45 (m, 2H), 7.43 – 7.38 (m, 1H), 4.55 (s, 4H), 3.11 (s, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃)

$\delta = 138.50, 132.18, 129.14, 123.38, 82.56, 78.37, 45.25$. HRMS (APPI+): calcd for $C_{10}H_9Cl_2$ ($[M-e]^+$): 199.0076; found m/z : 199.0078.

Intermediate **S4**

Intermediate **S4** was obtained analogously to **S1** except that reagent **S3** (259 mg, 1.3 mmol) was used in place of 1,3-bis(chloromethyl)benzene. The purified product was isolated as orange solid (50 mg, 80 μ mol, yield: 36%). TLC (silica gel, eluent dichloromethane, $R_f = 0.66$). 1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 7.74$ (d, $J=7.0$, 2H), 7.57 – 7.17 (m, 5H), 5.25 (s, 2H), 5.01 (s, 2H), 4.69 (s, 2H), 4.46 (s, 2H), 4.14 (s, 5H), 4.04 – 3.95 (m, 2H), 3.69 (s, 1H), 1.33 (s, 12H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 155.15, 141.28, 140.74, 139.76, 135.66, 131.53, 130.60, 128.15, 128.06, 123.78, 102.40, 84.57, 83.64, 79.77, 69.80, 67.99, 65.19, 63.20, 53.84, 46.05, 25.20$. HRMS (ESI+): calcd for $C_{34}H_{35}BClFeNO_4$ ($[M-e]^+$): 623.1692; found m/z : 623.1696.

Prodrug **4f**

Prodrug **4f** was obtained analogously to **4a** except that **S4** (63 mg, 0.10 mmol) was used in place of **S1**. The purified product was isolated as orange solid (61 mg, 61 μ mol, yield:

61%). TLC (silica gel, eluent ethyl acetate, $R_f = 0.32$). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) $\delta = 7.74$ (d, $J=3.7$, 2H), 7.54 – 6.91 (m, 5H), 5.20 (s, 2H), 5.05 (s, 2H), 4.92 (s, 2H), 4.37 (d, $J=4.0$, 2H), 4.12 (s, 5H), 4.00 (s, 2H), 3.94 (t, $J=2.7$, 1H), 3.87 – 3.74 (m, 1H), 3.48 – 3.34 (m, 1H), 3.16 (s, 1H), 2.51 – 2.07 (m, 4H), 2.05 – 0.90 (m, 40H), 0.88 (s, 3H), 0.66 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) $\delta = 174.21, 154.85, 140.31, 139.92, 137.84, 135.40, 130.74, 130.01, 127.62, 126.96, 123.18, 102.89, 84.42, 83.60, 78.22, 73.40, 72.38, 70.26, 69.66, 68.87, 68.16, 65.73, 65.57, 63.12, 54.47, 47.67, 47.02, 42.47, 42.14, 40.40, 40.18, 35.76, 35.73, 35.20, 31.76, 31.45, 31.27, 28.93, 27.97, 27.21, 25.24, 23.70, 22.91, 17.72, 12.85$. HRMS (ESI+): calcd for $\text{C}_{58}\text{H}_{74}\text{BFeNO}_9$ ($[\text{M}-\text{e}]^+$): 995.4801; found m/z : 995.4797. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{58}\text{H}_{74}\text{BFeNO}_9$: C 69.95, H 7.49, N 1.41; found: C 69.84, H 7.57, N 1.39.

Prodrug **4g**

Prodrug **4f** (100 mg, 0.10 mmol), coumarin derivative **S5** (42.1 mg, 0.20 mmol, synthesized by protocol reported elsewhere⁶) and CuI (5.8 mg, 0.03 mmol) were suspended in DMF (1 mL) and shaken overnight at 23 °C. Ethyl acetate (10 mL) was added and the precipitate was filtered off. All volatiles were removed from the filtrate obtained using rotary evaporator at 60 °C. The residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel using ethyl acetate as eluent yielding brown solid (80 mg, 67%). TLC (silica gel, eluent ethyl acetate, $R_f = 0.16$). ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) $\delta = 9.35$ (s, 1H), 8.83 (s, 1H), 8.51 (s, 1H), 7.93 (s, 1H), 7.74 (d, $J=7.0$, 2H), 7.59 (s, 1H), 7.48 (d, $J=8.6$, 1H), 7.33 (s, 2H), 7.13 (s, 1H), 7.01 (d, $J=2.1$, 1H), 6.83 (dd, $J=8.6, 2.1$, 1H),

5.25 (d, $J=15.1$, 3H), 5.18 – 4.93 (m, 3H), 4.56 (s, 2H), 4.38 – 4.05 (m, 6H), 4.03 (s, 1H), 3.80 (d, $J=2.4$, 1H), 3.60 (dt, $J=11.5$, 4.5, 1H), 2.41 (dt, $J=28.0$, 17.9, 5H), 2.13 – 0.92 (m, 42H), 0.89 (s, 3H), 0.69 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ = 174.54, 163.04, 157.41, 155.13, 147.60, 140.62, 139.91, 138.45, 135.40, 134.76, 131.42, 130.95, 127.67, 125.72, 123.92, 123.67, 121.34, 119.73, 115.77, 111.25, 103.43, 103.14, 84.43, 73.84, 72.75, 70.36, 69.22, 68.28, 65.81, 65.71, 63.30, 54.47, 47.82, 46.84, 42.07, 41.93, 40.02, 39.56, 36.62, 35.64, 35.31, 35.21, 32.57, 31.70, 31.07, 28.89, 28.17, 26.88, 25.24, 23.82, 22.67, 17.67, 12.79. HRMS (ESI+): calcd for $\text{C}_{67}\text{H}_{79}\text{BFeN}_4\text{NaO}_{12}$ ($[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$): 1221.5029; found m/z : 1221.5030. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{67}\text{H}_{79}\text{BFeN}_4\text{O}_{12}$: C 67.12, H 6.64, N 4.67; found: C 66.92, H 6.96, N 4.51.

^1H -NMR, ^{13}C -NMR and high resolution (HR) mass spectra (MS) of reported intermediates and prodrugs

Figure S1. ^1H -NMR spectrum of intermediate **S1** in Acetone-d_6 .

Figure S2. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of intermediate **S1** in Acetone-d₆.

Figure S3. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of intermediate **S1**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S4. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of prodrug **4a** in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S5. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of prodrug **4a** in Pyridin-d_5 .

4xu016140
HX040-B1212-3c-conc-13C-scan4096

Figure S6. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of prodrug **4a** in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S7. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of prodrug **4a**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S8. ¹H-NMR spectrum of prodrug **4b** in Acetone-d₆.

Figure S9. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of prodrug **4b** in Acetone-d₆.

Figure S10. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of prodrug **4c** in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S11. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum of prodrug **4c** in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S12. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of prodrug **4d** in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S13. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum of prodrug **4d** in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S14. ¹H-NMR spectrum of prodrug **4e** in Acetone-d₆.

Figure S15. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of prodrug **4e** in Acetone-d₆.

3xu009291
HX051-B2405

Figure S16. ^1H -NMR spectrum of **S3** in CD_3Cl .

4xu018601
HX051-B1305

Figure S17. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of **S3** in CD_3Cl .

Figure **S18**. High resolution APPI mass spectrum of **S3**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S19**. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of **S4** in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S20. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of **S4** in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S21. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of **S4**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S24. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of prodrug **4f**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S25. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of prodrug **4g** in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S26. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of prodrug **4g** in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S27. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of prodrug **4g**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Screening of all prepared prodrugs

(a) Study of solubility of the prodrugs in aqueous buffers

Compounds were dissolved in DMSO at concentrations of 10 mM, 5 mM, 3 mM, 1.5 mM and 1 mM. These solutions (10 μ L) were transferred to quartz cuvettes with Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 medium (Biochrom GmbH, Germany) supplemented with fetal bovine serum (FBS, 5%), L-glutamine (1%) and Penicilin/Streptomycin mixture (1%, Biochrom GmbH, Germany) (990 μ L, further medium) to obtain solutions/suspensions of compounds at final concentrations of 100 μ M, 50 μ M, 30 μ M, 15 μ M, and 10 μ M. The absorbance at 789 nm ($A_{789 \text{ nm}}$) of the resulting mixtures was measured at ambient temperature (22 ± 2 °C) and plotted as a function of the concentration of the compounds. Mixtures exhibiting $A_{789 \text{ nm}}$ less than 2 times of $A_{789 \text{ nm}}$ observed for the control (true) solution containing DMSO (10 μ L) and the above defined medium (990 μ L) appeared transparent and were considered as true solutions. Those with $A_{789 \text{ nm}}$ higher than 2 times of the control appeared milky were considered to be suspensions (Table S1).

Table **S1**. Solubility of compounds in the RPMI 1640 medium.

Prodrug	Solubility (μ M)
4a	63 ± 6
4b	≥ 50
4c	≥ 50
4d	≥ 50
4e	≥ 50
4f	57 ± 3
4g	82 ± 4

(b) Determination of viability of BL-2 cells in the presence of the prodrugs

BL-2 cells were centrifuged, the medium was removed, and the cells were washed two times with DPBS and resuspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/ streptomycin. This suspension was spread in the wells of a 96-well microtiter plate (50000 cells per well per 100 μ L) and left standing at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) for overnight. Stock solutions of prodrugs of different concentrations (1 μ L, solvent dmsO, final concentrations in wells were 2, 5, 10, 30, 50 μ M)

were added to the wells and incubated for specific periods of time. Four experiments were conducted for each concentration of the prodrug. Finally, 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT, 20 μ L of the solution prepared by dissolving MTT (5 mg) in DPBS buffer (1 mL)) was added to each well, incubated for 3 h, treated with sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) solution (90 μ L, 10% solution in 0.01 M aqueous HCl), and incubated overnight. Afterward, the intensity of the absorbance at 590 nm was measured. MTT is converted in live cells to blue dye with the absorbance maximum λ_{max} at 590 nm. The absorbance at 690 nm was taken as a baseline value. The baseline corrected absorbance at 590 nm ($A_{(590 \text{ nm})} - A_{(690 \text{ nm})}$) was applied to calculate the relative number of viable cells. IC_{50} values were determined by fitting the experimental data expressing the number of viable cells (% , Y-axis) versus drug concentration (μ M, X-axis) with a line curve and the X-axis value corresponding to 50% viability was considered as IC_{50} value according to the line curve (Table S2).

Table **S2**. Effects of the selected prodrugs on the viability of BL-2 cell line (IC_{50} values) after 48 h incubation.

Compound	IC_{50} (μ M)
2	5 ± 2
3	35 ± 2
4a	9 ± 2
4b	14 ± 3
4c	46 ± 3
4d	31 ± 4
4e	5 ± 2
6	~ 1
7	>100

A detailed study of prodrug 4a and controls

(a) Determination of n-octanol/water partition coefficients (LogP)

Solutions of references and new prodrugs were prepared by dissolving them in the mixture of dichloromethane/CH₃OH at proper concentrations. Commercially available reverse phase (RP) plates for thin layer chromatography (TLC, Macherey-Nagel, Germany, Alugram Aluminiumfolien RP-18 W/UV₂₅₄, stationary phase thickness: 0.15 mm) were used. The plates were manually spotted with freshly prepared solutions of the analytes at 10 mm distance from the edge of the plate. As the eluent mixture acetonitrile/aqueous 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid (MOPS) buffer (100 mM, pH 7.4) (6/4, v/v) was used. The solvent migration distance was around 4.5 cm. The plates were visually inspected under the UV-light (254 nm) and each zone was clearly marked and its distance was manually measured. All measurements were done in at least triplicate and average values were used in further calculations. All experiments were performed at ambient temperature (22 ± 2 °C). A set of reference compounds was used, for which logP-values were previously reported: perylene (6.25), anthracene (4.50), benzophenone (3.18), phenylboric acid (1.59).⁷ A calibration plot of R_f versus logP, which was obtained based on these data, was used to determine logP values of new prodrugs (Figure S28, Table S3).

Figure **S28**. Correlation of LogP values and R_f values for the reference compounds. Dash line: a linear fit of the experimental data. This calibration plot was used for the determination of LogP values of new prodrugs from their R_f values.

Table **S3**. LogP values for ER-targeting prodrugs.^a

Compound	LogP value
4a -BE	> 6.25
4a -BA	5.90 ± 0.17
4g -BE	> 6.25
4g -BA	5.70 ± 0.07

^a BE: parent prodrugs; BA: boronic acid derivatives formed from parent prodrugs in aqueous solution.

(b) Monitoring of H₂O₂-induced activation of prodrugs **4a and **4g** using mass spectrometry**

A freshly prepared solution of **4a** or **4g** (10 μL, 2.5 mM in DMSO) was added to acetonitrile (CH₃CN, 100 μL). The resulting solution was mixed with water (896 μL) followed by the addition of either H₂O₂ (2.5 μL, 30% (w/w) in H₂O) or water (4 μL, negative control). These solutions were kept at 22 °C for 5 minutes. Then they were diluted with CH₃CN (1 mL) and analyzed by high resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrometry (Figures S29-S34).

Figure **S29**. Structural formulas and exact masses of products identified in the mixtures of **4a** or **4g** with/without H₂O₂ by using high resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrometry (Figures S30-S34).

Figure **S30**. ESI-TOF mass spectra of prodrugs **4a** and **4g** incubated for 5 minutes either in the absence of H₂O₂ or in its presence. Other experimental conditions are as described above. Expanded regions of the spectra shown in this figure are provided below in Figures S31-S34.

Figure S31. Expanded regions of the ESI-TOF mass spectra of mixtures of **4a** with H₂O₂ provided in Figure S30.

Figure S32. Expanded regions of the ESI-TOF mass spectra of **4a** provided in Figure S30.

Figure S33. Expanded regions of the ESI-TOF mass spectra of mixtures of **4g** with H₂O₂ provided in Figure S30.

Figure **S34**. Expanded regions of the ESI-TOF mass spectra for **4g** provided in Figure **S30**.

Drug-induced generation of ROS in cell free settings

2',7'-Dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA, 4.9 mg) was dissolved in DMF (100 μ L) and mixed with aqueous NaOH (0.1 M, 900 μ L). The resulting mixture was incubated for 30 min at 22 $^{\circ}$ C in the dark to obtain a stock solution of 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein (DCFH, 10 mM). Next, DCFH (1 μ L) was added to the solution containing MOPS buffer (100 mM, pH 7.4), N,N,N',N'-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, 10 mM) and glutathione (GSH, 5 mM) (1 mL, final concentration of DCFH 10 μ M). The reaction mixture was heated to 37 $^{\circ}$ C and H₂O₂ (1 μ L, final concentration 10 mM) was added. The reaction was monitored by fluorescence spectroscopy: λ_{ex} = 501 nm, λ_{em} = 523 nm. After around 5 min, prodrugs (1 mM in DMF, 10 μ L) were added, and the fluorescence monitoring was continued for 180 min (Table S4).

Figure **S35**. Increase of the fluorescence intensity $((dF/dt)_0, \lambda_{ex} = 501 \text{ nm}, \lambda_{em} = 523 \text{ nm})$ of aqueous solutions of DCFH, H_2O_2 in the presence of prodrug **4a** or in its absence (background). The arrow indicates the time point of addition of the prodrug. Red straight lines indicate initial (linear) fluorescence growth, which is characterized by parameter $(dF/dt)_0$ (Table S4). Other experimental conditions are described in detail above.

Table **S4**. Maximal increase of the fluorescence intensity $((dF/dt)_0, \lambda_{ex} = 501 \text{ nm}, \lambda_{em} = 523 \text{ nm})$ upon oxidation of DCFH by H_2O_2 in the presence of prodrugs and controls.

Compound	Inclination value: $(dF/dt)_0$, min^{-1}	Relative rate increase / p-value (Student's t test)
4a	0.31 ± 0.10	$3.2 / 0.0304 (*)^i$
4g	0.21 ± 0.09	$2.2 / 0.1110 \text{ (ns)}$
2	1.67 ± 0.27	$17.1 / 0.0006 (***)$
FeSO_4^{ii}	2.82 ± 0.59	$28.9 / 0.0013 (**)$
FcH (7) ⁱⁱⁱ	0.05 ± 0.00	$0.5 / 0.1575 \text{ (ns)}$
background ⁱⁱⁱ	0.10 ± 0.05	1 (reference)

ⁱ *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$.

ⁱⁱ Positive control.

ⁱⁱⁱ Ferrocene and DMF: negative controls.

(d) Cells and Cell Culture

Human ovarian cancer cell line A2780 was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Burkitt lymphoma cell line BL-2 and T-cell leukemia cell line Jurkat were obtained from DSMZ (Germany). SBLF9 primary human fibroblasts were isolated via skin biopsy after local anesthesia from a healthy 20-year-old Caucasian male and subsequently cultivated in F-12 Medium supplemented with 15 % fetal bovine serum, 2 % non-essential amino acids and 1 % penicillin/streptomycin.⁸ Suspension cells were grown to $(0.5-1.5) \times 10^6$ cells/mL and diluted as required. Adherent cells were cultivated to around 80% confluence.

(e) Determination of viability of A2780 and Jurkat cells in the presence of the prodrugs

A2780 cells (MTT assay, Table S5). The medium was removed, and the cells were washed two times with DPBS, trypsinated, and resuspended in RPMI 1640 medium (A2780) supplemented with 5% FBS (for 48 h assay) or 10% FBS (for 96 h assay), 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. This suspension was spread in the wells of a 96-well microtiter plate (25000 cells for A2780 per well per 100 μ L). Other steps were identical to those described in determination of viability of non-adherent cells (given above).

Table **S5**. Effects of the selected prodrugs on the viability of A2780 cell lines (IC_{50} values) after 48 or 96 h incubation.

Compound	IC_{50} (μ M) 48 h incubation	IC_{50} (μ M) 96 h incubation
2	7 ± 2	7 ± 2
3	32 ± 3	30 ± 5
4a	5.4 ± 0.7	6.6 ± 0.9
4g	6.2 ± 2.4	-
5	43 ± 4	35 ± 2
6^a	3.3 ± 0.3	2.2 ± 0.8
7^b	>100	>100

^a Ferric chloride/8-hydroxyquinoline complex, 1/2, eq/eq (positive control).

^b Ferrocene (negative control).

Jurkat cells (Table S6). The cells were counted in MUSE Cell Analyzer using MUSE[®] Count & Viability Assay Kit (Merck-Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA) and adjusted to a density of 1.0×10^5 /mL in RPMI 1640 medium (with 10% FCS and 1% glutamine). 9,000 cells per well per 90 μ L were seeded into 96 well culture plates. The 30 mM prodrug stock solutions in DMSO were diluted to 500 μ M, 250 μ M, 120 μ M and 60 μ M in cell culture medium and 10 μ L of the dilutions was pipetted to the cells, receiving final test concentrations of 50 μ M, 25 μ M, 12 μ M and 6 μ M. Every concentration was tested in triplicates. These experiments were conducted either in the presence of N-acetylcysteine (NAC, 1 μ M) or in its absence. Cells with corresponding amounts of DMSO served as negative controls. After 48 h cells were mixed and 25 μ L of the cell suspension was incubated with 200 μ L of freshly prepared staining solution, consisting of Annexin A5-Fitc (1 μ L) (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and propidium iodide (PI, 67 ng) (Sigma-Aldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany) per 1 mL Ringer's solution (Fresenius Kabi AG, Bad Homburg, Germany). Cells were incubated for 20 min at 4°C and then analyzed in Gallios cytometer[™] (Beckman Coulter, Fullerton, CA, USA). Fitc and propidium iodide were excited at 488 nm; Fitc fluorescence was recorded on the FL1 sensor (525/38 nm band pass, BP) and propidium iodide fluorescence was detected on FL3 sensor (620/30 nm BP). To eliminate any fluorescence bleed-through, electronic compensation was used. Data were analyzed employing Kaluza[™] software Version 1.2 (Beckman Coulter, Fullerton, CA, USA) and processed in Microsoft Excel. Cells negative for Annexin A5-Fitc (Ax-) and propidium iodide (PI-) were considered viable. Cells positive for Annexin A5-Fitc (Ax+) and negative for PI (PI-) were considered apoptotic. Cells positive for both Annexin A5-Fitc (Ax+) and PI (PI+) were considered necrotic. IC₅₀ values were determined by fitting the % values of Ax-PI- cells versus drug concentration with a sigmoidal curve using GraphPad Prism software (Figure S36).

NAC inhibits effects of **4a**. For example, 26 ± 4 % Jurkat cells remain viable after their incubation with **4a** (25 μ M) for 48 h. In contrast, the number of viable cells is significantly higher (41 ± 3 %, $p < 0.01$) when the cells are incubated with **4a** (25 μ M) and NAC (1 μ M) for the same time. Furthermore, NAC reduces the number of necrotic cells from 69.7 ± 17.1 % (-NAC) to 56.1 ± 2.1 % (+NAC, $p < 0.01$).

Figure **S36**. **A**: Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of Jurkat cell lines after 48 h incubation. Viable cells are indicated as Ax- / PI-, apoptotic – as Ax+ / PI- and necrotic – as Ax- / PI-. **B**: Modulation of anticancer effect of prodrug **4a** (25 μM) with N-acetylcysteine (NAC, 1 μM). Detailed description of this experiment is provided above. The data were compared by using Student's t test: $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), $p \geq 0.05$ (non-significant, ns).

Table **S6**. Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of Jurkat cell lines (IC_{50} values) after 48 h incubation.

Compound	IC_{50} (μM)
2	7.2 ± 0.1
3	30 ± 4
4a	18 ± 1
7	>100

(f) Study of the mechanism of death of A2780 cells induced by prodrug 4a

A2780 cells were seeded into 96 well culture plates at the same cell concentration and in the same medium as applied for the above described MTT assay. The next day, stock solutions of prodrugs of different concentrations (1 μ L, solvent DMSO, final concentrations in wells were 1, 5, 10 and 25 μ M) and carrier (DMSO, 1%) were added to the wells and incubated in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%). After 48 h supernatants were transferred into 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes and 100 μ L of DPBS was added to transfer supernatant residue into tube. Trypsin (0.25%, 50 μ L) was then added to well to detach the cells. All supernatants in Eppendorf tubes were combined back into wells. After gently pipetting up and down, 50 μ L of cell solutions was transferred into a new Eppendorf tube and incubated with 200 μ L of staining solution, consisting of Annexin (5 μ L) and propidium iodide (PI, 330 ng) per 1 mL buffer (conc. 1X) form kit. Cells were incubated for 20 min at 22°C in dark and then put on ice followed by analyzed by Guava flow cytometer (λ_{ex} = 488 nm, λ_{em} = 525 nm for Annexin and λ_{em} = 664 nm for PI). Cells negative for Annexin (Ax-) and propidium iodide (PI-) were considered viable. Cells positive for Annexin (Ax+) and negative for PI (PI-) were considered apoptotic. Cells positive for PI (PI+) were considered necrotic. (N=3, Figure S37).

Figure S37. Effects of the prodrugs on the viability of A2780 cell lines after 48 h incubation. Viable cells are indicated as Ax-/PI-, apoptotic as Ax+/PI- and necrotic as PI+.

(g) Effect of prodrugs and controls on cellular organelles: lysosomes (LY), endoplasmic reticulum (ER), Golgi (G) and mitochondria (Mit)

A2780 cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin in a 24-well microtiter plate (total volume 0.5 mL) at a density of 200 cells/ μ L one day before the experiment. On the day of the experiment, prodrugs (3 mM, 5 μ L, final conc. 30 μ M) or DMSO (carrier, 1%, v/v) were added to cells and incubated for 1 h, 4 h and 24 h in a dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5 %) at 37 °C. The cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with HBSS (Hanks' Balanced Salt solution, 500 μ L). Stock solutions of different dyes (5 μ L) were added: concentrations of the stock solutions were 4 mg/L for Acridine orange (AO), 10 mg/L for Rhodamine 123 (R123), 1 μ M for ER-Tracker-Green (ERG) and 10 μ M for Golgi-Staining-Green (GO). AO, R123, ERG were dissolved in DMSO, whereas GO was dissolved in H₂O. Final concentrations of solutions were 40 μ g/L for AO, 100 μ g/L for R123, 0.01 μ M for ERG and 0.1 μ M for GO. The cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C for 20 min. Afterwards the supernatant was removed, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer twice and detached from the culture dish using trypsin (0.025%)/EDTA (0.01 %) (200 μ L). Next, the cells were re-suspended in fresh medium. Finally, the fluorescence of live cells (the total number of events was 5000, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 525$ nm) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (N=3). The decrease of organelle-specific fluorescence of cells was interpreted as organelle disruption in the presence of prodrugs (Figure 1).

(h) Investigation of the effect of **4a** and on the ER-staining using confocal microscopy

A2780 cells were seeded in 500 μ L of RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin on a 35 mm imaging dish (μ - Dish 35 mm, high, ibidi GmbH, Germany) at a cell density of 80 cells/ μ L and allowed to attach to the surface of the dish for overnight. Then the cells were washed with DPBS (2 x 2 mL) and compound **4a** (10 μ L, 3 mM in DMSO) was added to fresh medium (2 mL, RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin)

and incubated for 1 h or 4 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Then the cells were washed with PBS (2 x 2 mL) and Hoechst 33342 (2 µL, 1 mg/mL in DMSO) was added to fresh medium (2 mL) followed by incubating for 20 min 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Afterwards, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (1 mL) was added. Fluorescence images were taken with a Zeiss Spinning Disk Axio Observer Z1 with Plan-Apochromat 63x/1.40 oil objective in spinning disc confocal mode using the EVOLVE 512 EMCCD camera, Channel 1 (green): λ_{ex} : 355 nm; λ_{em} : 450/50; Channel 2 (red): λ_{ex} : 561 nm; λ_{em} : 595/50 . Fluorescent signals were overlapped with DIC images, examples are shown in Figure S38. After 1 h treatment with **4a** a portion of cells showed reduced fluorescent signal for the ER-tracker-RED dye (left column). Presumably, the ER in these cells is still intact, and **4a** is quenching the dye. In another portion of cells (represented by the image in the middle column), the signal of the ER dye is overlapping partially with the one of Hoechst, indicating that the ER is disrupted so that the dye is leaking into the nucleus. In another portion of cells (right column) the ER-tracker-RED signal fills out the whole cytosol also indicating a disruption of the ER structure and a leakage of the dye. After 4 h **4a** treatment, there is low (left column) or very low (right column) ER-tracker-RED signal detectable or the cells are completely disrupted as shown in the middle column.

Figure **S38**. Staining of A2780 cells with ER-tracker-RED and Hoechst 33342 upon 1 h or 4 h treatment with **4a** or carrier. Fluorescent channels: Channel 1 green, λ_{ex} : 355 nm; λ_{em} : 450/50 nm (detection of Hoechst in nuclei); Channel 2 (red): λ_{ex} : 561 nm; λ_{em} : 595/50 nm (detection of BODIPY in ER-tracker-RED).

(i) Confirmation of the induction of ER-stress by qPCR

To confirm the induction of ER-stress upon **4a** treatment, the expression of the ER-stress marker C/EBP homologous protein (CHOP) was relatively quantified by qualitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR). Therefore, A2780 were seeded in 6-well plates with a cell concentration of 200 cells/ μ L and allowed to attach to the surface of the dish for overnight. The next day, cells were washed with DPBS once and compounds **1**, **2**, **4a**, or a positive control at the indicated concentrations were added to fresh medium (2 mL, RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, 1% penicillin/streptomycin and 1 % DMSO) and incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ and incubated for 24 h. To isolate RNA from cell samples, the cultivation medium was removed, the cells washed twice with DPBS and 1 mL/well TRI reagent® was added. After 5 min incubation at room temperature, the cell lysate was transferred into 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes and frozen at -20 °C. After de-freezing, the aqueous phase of the samples was extracted by adding 200 μ L chloroform followed by centrifugation at 12,000 g for 15 min. The aqueous phase was mixed with 400 μ L of ice-cold Ethanol and transferred onto Zymo-Spin IC Columns. The samples were subsequently centrifuged for 1 min at 8,000 rcf and 4 °C. The eluate was discarded. The RNA on the column was washed with first 500 μ L of 3 M sodium acetate buffer (pH=5.2) and secondly with 500 μ L of 75 % ethanol in water, by solvent addition, subsequent centrifugation as above and

eluate removal. Finally, 500 μL of 100 % ethanol was added and the samples centrifuged for 3 min at 10,000 rcf to dry the column. The RNA was eluted by adding 25 μL of RNase-free water that was pre-warmed to 65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, incubation for 5 min at RT and subsequent centrifugation for 2 min at 8,000 rcf. To transcribe the isolated RNA into cDNA, 1 μg RNA in 12.5 μL RNase-free water was incubated with 1 μL of Random Hexamer Primer at 65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 min. Subsequently, 0.5 μL reverse transcriptase, 4 μL RT 5x buffer and 2 μL were added per sample. Finally, the reverse transcription protocol (10 min at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; 60 min at 42 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; 10 min at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; forever at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) was run at the Dual Block Gradient PCR Thermal Cycler. For the relative quantification of the genes of interest, 5 μL of LightCycler® 480 SYBR® Green Master was mixed with 1 μL of a primer pair and 4 μL of the 1:10 diluted cDNA and subjected to the LightCycler® 480. The applied primer sequences were GTACCTATGTTTCACCTCCTCG; TGG AATCTGGAGAGTGAGGG for CHOP and TGGGCAAGAACACGATGATG; TGAGGTCCTCCTTGGTGAACA for the housekeeping gene RPLP0. The reaction mixtures were initially heated at 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 min, followed by 45 cycles, which consisted of 10s at 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 30 s 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and 10 s at 72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The data were normalized to the Ct value of the RPLP0 mRNA in the same sample. For the evaluation of the fold change, the $2^{-\Delta\text{Ct}}$ value was calculated. The $2^{-\Delta\text{Ct}}$ value of untreated cells was set to 100. Three independent experiments were performed and the mean \pm SD calculated (Table S7).

Table **S7**. Study of the effect of prodrug **4a** and controls on the expression of CHOP-mRNA in A2780 cells.

Compound (concentration)	$2^{-\Delta\text{Ct}}$ (N=3)	p-value in Student's t-test
Carrier	152.14 \pm 25.89	Reference
Prodrug 1 (10 μM)	186.89 \pm 67.723	0.453
Prodrug 1 (20 μM)	229.39 \pm 51.41	0.0807
Prodrug 2 (1 μM)	198.64 \pm 44.16	0.1907
Prodrug 2 (3 μM)	284.36 \pm 34.07	0.0059
Prodrug 4a (5 μM)	1096.13 \pm 487.19	0.0285
Positive control (2 μM)	1212.54 \pm 139.87	0.0002
Positive control (3 μM)	1835.23 \pm 509.53	0.0046

(i) Prodrug-induced production of intracellular ROS

Total intracellular ROS

A2780 cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin in a 24-well microtiter plate (total volume 0.5 mL) at a density of 200 cells/ μ L one day before the experiment. On the day of the experiment, the cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with DPBS (500 μ L). CM-DCFH-DA (5-(6-)chloromethyl-2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate, Thermo-Fisher) solution (0.1 mM in DMSO, 5 μ L) was added (final concentration 1 μ M) and the cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C for 15 min. Afterwards the supernatant was removed, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (500 μ L) was added followed by addition of compounds / positive and negative controls (5 μ L of stock solutions in DMSO, final concentration of prodrugs, positive control and negative control was 30 μ M and 100 μ M respectively) or carrier only (DMSO, 5 μ L, final concentration 1 %, v/v) and incubation for 2 h in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C. Next, the cells were detached from the culture dish using trypsin (0.025 %)/EDTA (0.01%) (200 μ L). The cells were re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (200 μ L). Finally, the fluorescence of live cells (λ_{ex} = 488 nm, λ_{em} = 530 nm) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (Figure 2A).

Assays with BL-2 and Jurkat cells were conducted analogously, except that the incubation of Jurkat cells with prodrug **4a** was shortened to 1h. At longer incubation time (2, 4h) the fluorescence signal of the ROS probe is strongly diminished that might indicate transport of the probe out of Jurkat cells (Figure 2A).

Mitochondrial ROS

A2780 cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin in a 24-well microtiter plate (total volume 0.5 mL) at a density of 200 cells/ μ L one day before the experiment. On the day of the experiment, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5%

FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (500 μ L) was added followed by addition of compounds (5 μ L of stock solutions in DMSO, final concentration of prodrug was 10 μ M and 30 μ M) or carrier only (DMSO, 5 μ L, final concentration 1 %, v/v) and incubation for 2 h in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C. After that, the cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with HBSS (Hanks' Balanced Salt solution, 500 μ L). MitoSOX (Red Mitochondrial Superoxide Indicator, Thermo-Fisher, Catalog number: M36008) solution (5 mM in DMSO, 0.5 μ L) was added (final concentration 5 μ M) and the cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C for 20 min. Next, the cells were detached from the culture dish using trypsin (0.025 %)/EDTA (0.01%) (200 μ L). The cells were re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (200 μ L). Finally, the fluorescence of live cells ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 585 \text{ nm}$) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (Figure 2B).

(k) Confirmation of localization and activation of **4g** in ER

*Effect of ROS on fluorescence of prodrug **4g** in cell free settings*

Prodrug **4g** (10 μ L, 0.5 mM in DMSO) was mixed with acetonitrile (100 μ L) and phosphate buffered saline solution (PBS= 10 mM phosphate, 154 mM NaCl, pH 7.4, 890 μ L) to obtain its 5 μ M solution, followed by adding water (10 μ L) or H₂O₂ (30 % (w/w) in H₂O, 10 μ L or 100 μ L) to reach the final concentrations of 0, 0.1 M and 1 M for H₂O₂. Monitoring of the fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 361 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 479 \text{ nm}$) of this solution at 37 °C was conducted for 120 min (Figure S39, Table S8).

Figure **S39**. Increase of the fluorescence intensity ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 361 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 479 \text{ nm}$) of the solution of prodrug **4g** either in the presence of absence of H_2O_2 . Other experimental conditions are as described above.

Table **S8**. Maximal increase of the fluorescence intensity ($(dF/dt)_0$, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 361 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 479 \text{ nm}$) upon activation of prodrug **4g** by H_2O_2 .

Conc. of H_2O_2 (M)	Inclination value of $(dF/dt)_0$, min^{-1}
0	0.005 ± 0.004
0.1	5.4 ± 1.1
1	14.5 ± 1.8

Study of uptake of prodrug **4g** in A2780 cells

A2780 cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin in a 24-well microtiter plate (total volume 0.5 mL) at a density of 200 cells/ μL one day before the experiment. On the day of the experiment, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (500 μL) was added followed by addition of compounds (5 μL of stock solutions in DMSO, final concentration of prodrug was 5 μM , 10 μM and 25 μM respectively) or carrier only (DMSO, 5 μL , final concentration 1 %, v/v) and incubation for 2 h in the dark chamber filled with CO_2 (5%) at 37 °C. Next, the cells were detached from the culture dish using trypsin (0.025 %)/EDTA (0.01%) (200

μL). The cells were re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (200 μL). Finally, the fluorescence of live cells ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 450 \text{ nm}$) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (Figure S40, Table S9).

Figure **S40**. Accumulation of **4g** in A2780 cells by quantification of the intracellular fluorescence of the product derived from the reaction of **4g** with ROS.

Table **S9**. Accumulation of **4g** in A2780 cells.

Conc. of 4g (μM)	Mean fluorescence of viable cells (F, a.u.)	F/F(0)
0 (dms0)	7914 \pm 107	1
5	114565 \pm 22764	14.5
10	130021 \pm 24085	16.4
25	164056 \pm 30674	20.7

*Colocalization of **4g** with ER-tracker red using fluorescence microscopy*

A2780 cells were seeded in 500 μL of RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin on a 35 mm imaging dish (μ - Dish 35 mm, high, ibidi GmbH, Germany) at a cell density of 80 cells/ μL and allowed to attach to the surface of the dish for overnight. Then the cells were washed with DPBS (2 x 2 mL) and compound **4g** (10 μL , 3 mM in DMSO) was added to fresh medium (1 mL, RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin) and incubated for 2 h at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5% CO_2 (the final concentration of **4g** was 30 μM) Then the cells were washed with PBS (2 x 2 mL) and ER-tracker Red

(1 μL , 0.1 mM in DMSO) was added to Hanks' Balanced Salt solution (1 mL) followed by incubating for 20 min 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5% CO_2 . Afterwards, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (1 mL) was added. The fluorescence images were taken with a Zeiss Spinning Disk Axio Observer Z1 with Plan-Apochromat 63x/1.40 oil objective in spinning disc confocal mode using the EVOLVE 512 EMCCD camera and the filtersets with excitation (λ_{ex}) and emission (λ_{em}) wavelengths: λ_{ex} : 355 nm; λ_{em} : 450/50; λ_{ex} : 561 nm; λ_{em} : 629/62 . Z-stacks were recorded and orthogonal images, as well as Pearson's R value calculations were generated using the Fiji/ImageJ software (Figure 2C-K, S41).

Figure **S41**. Images of A2780 cells (top left image: X,Y scan; top right and bottom images: two Z-scans) stained with mixtures containing ER-tracker-RED and **4g** (30 μM) as described above. Fluorescent channels: (Ch1, green), λ_{ex} : 335-383 nm; λ_{em} : 420-470 nm (detection of CM in **4g**); (Ch2, red), λ_{ex} : 538-562 nm; λ_{em} : 570-640 nm (detection of BODIPY in ER-tracker-RED). The images were generated by merging Ch1 and Ch2 channels by using the Fiji/ImageJ software.

(I) Confirmation of cancer cell specificity of prodrugs 4a/4g

Viability of primary cancer (CLL) cells and normal cells (MNC's) in the presence of 4a

Clinical samples from chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) patients (N=6, CLL cells) and healthy donors (N=6; peripheral blood mononuclear cells, MNCs) were collected at the University Hospital Heidelberg, Germany. Informed consent was obtained in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Sample collection and analysis was approved by the ethics committee of the University of Heidelberg (S-254/2016). Blood was separated by a Ficoll gradient (GE Healthcare), and cells were cryopreserved. Drug sensitivity screening was performed in 384-well format (Greiner Bio One) with 10 different prodrug concentrations (40, 20, 10, 5, 2.5, 1.25, 0.625, 0.313, 0.156, 0.078 μM) and 4×10^4 cells per well. Cells were cultured in RPMI-1640 (Invitrogen) supplemented with penicillin/streptomycin (Invitrogen), L-glutamine (Invitrogen) and 10% pooled and heat inactivated AB-type human serum (Sigma-Aldrich). Cell viability was assessed by quantification of ATP (CellTiter Glo®, Promega) 48 hours after drug application. Luminescence was measured on a Tecan Infinite F200 Microplate Reader. Viability was calculated as % of solvent (DMSO) treated control (Figure S42).

Figure **S42**. Effect of prodrug **4a** on viability of primary cancer CLL cells and primary normal MNC cells.

Investigating cancer-specificity of 4g by fluorescence microscopy

A2780 cells were seeded in 500 μ L of RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin on a 35 mm imaging dish (μ - Dish 35 mm, high, ibidi GmbH, Germany) at a cell density of 80 cells/ μ L and SBLF9 fibroblasts were seeded in 500 μ L of Ham's F-12K (Kaighn's)-Medium supplemented with 15 % FBS, 2 % non-essential amino acid mix, and 1 % penicillin/streptomycin at a cell density of 50 cells/ μ L and allowed to attach to the surface of the dish for overnight. Then the cells were washed with DPBS (2 x 2 mL) and compound 4g (20 μ L, 1 mM in DMSO) was added to fresh medium (2 mL, RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin) and incubated for 2 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Then the cells were washed with DPBS (2 x 2 mL) and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (1 mL) was added. The fluorescence images were taken with a Zeiss Axio Vert.A1 fluorescence microscope using excitation / emission 335-383 / 420-470 nm for detection of the coumarin dye (CM) released from the 4g in cells. Objective: 40x/1.30 Oil DIC (Figure **S43**).

Figure **S43**. Staining A2780 and SBLF9 cells with fluorogenic prodrug **4g**. Fluorescence detection: (Ch1, green), λ_{ex} : 335-383 nm; λ_{em} : 420-470 nm.

In vivo experiment

Ethics

Studies involving animals, including housing and care, method of euthanasia, and experimental protocols were approved by the Ethical committee of Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical University, protocols 20200525/4; 20180226/2, all experiments were designed to comply with principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement).

NK/Ly tumor

NK/Ly lymphoma were obtained from established cell lines, maintained in the Animal house of Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical University (Lviv, Ukraine) by repetitive inoculation of NK/Ly cell grown in ascites of black C57/BL6N mice. Tumors were transplanted in ascitic form by the intra-abdominal (growth as ascites) of aliquots of ascites containing 1 million of NK/Ly cells into C57/BL6N mice.

Mice

Black C57/BL6N mice were bred at Animal house of Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical University (Lviv, Ukraine). Animal were kept in clean environment, with water and food available ad libitum. Totally 12 animals were used in the study.

Upon tumor inoculation mice were weighted before and every next day during the experiment. At days 10-14 after inoculation, when animal weight increased by >15% and signs of ascetic tumor growth were visible, mice were treated with the studied compounds. For this reason 100 μ L of suspension of Cremophor/EtOH/drug (1/1/4, w/w/w) were injected intraperitoneally. At the indicated time ascites (~0.1 mL) were removed in sterile conditions with syringe and were washed twice in HBSS. The cell suspension of 1 to 4×10^6 cells/mL were used in experiments. The cells were re-suspended in 150 μ L of HBSS solution and placed in black 96-well immunoplates. Florescence was detected using Perkin Elmer BioAssay reader HST700 (Waltham, USA) with excitation of 360/20nm and emission 460/25nm filters.

Fluorescent microscopy was performed with an Olympus BX51 fluorescent microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) equipped with OmegaFilters filter set (OmegaFilters, Brattleboro, USA) and 60x 0.9NA water immersion objective as described.⁹

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4-Ferrocenylaniline-based ROS-responsive prodrugs with anticancer activity

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ABSTRACT

Ferrocene derivatives often exhibit anticancer activity. For example, our group has developed aminoferrocene-based (AF) prodrugs, which are activated in the presence of reactive oxygen species (ROS), present in large quantities in cancer cells. The activation reaction leads to formation of AF's, whose redox potential is shifted by 300–400 mV to negative values as compared to the parent AF prodrugs. Correspondingly, these drugs are very electron rich and can, therefore, act as catalysts of generation of highly toxic hydroxyl radicals ($\text{HO}\bullet$) from H_2O_2 . That contributes to the cytotoxicity of AF prodrugs. Unfortunately, AF's are chemically very unstable. Therefore, their lifetime in cells is < 1 h that limits the anticancer activity of the AF prodrugs. In this paper we report on new 4-ferrocenylaniline-based (4-FcAn) prodrugs. These are activated in the presence of ROS thereby releasing 4-FcAn. We confirmed that 4-FcAn is more electron rich than the corresponding prodrug ($\Delta E_{1/2} = 86$ mV) and can generate $\text{HO}\bullet$ from H_2O_2 analogously to AF. Furthermore, we observed that (a) 4-ferrocenylanilines are substantially more stable (>6 h) than AF's and (b) the corresponding prodrugs are substantially more active than the structurally related AF prodrugs. We found that, analogously to AF prodrugs, the new prodrugs exhibit their anticancer activity via generation of ROS in cancer cells.

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1. Introduction

Ferrocene is a unique organometallic compounds, which combines high chemical stability and reversible redox properties [1]. Ferrocene and its derivatives can donate electrons to naturally occurring substrates, e.g. H_2O_2 and molecular oxygen O_2 , leading to formation of highly toxic hydroxyl radicals $\text{HO}\bullet$ and super oxide anion radical $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$. The latter species can oxidize biomolecules, e.g. thiol rich proteins, membrane components and nucleic acid, thereby leading to cell death [2,3]. This property of ferrocene has been used to design anticancer therapeutics of several types. For example, redox potentials of optimized oligoferrocenes are lower than those of corresponding monomeric drugs due to electronic communication between the organometallic moieties. That makes these drugs efficient generators of ROS in cancer cells [4]. The activity of aminoferrocene-based (AF) prodrugs relies on generation of electron rich aminoferrocene (AF) drugs in cancer cells [5–7]. These catalyze ROS formation in cancer cells, thereby exhibit-

ing strong anticancer activity. Several other related ferrocene-based drugs were reviewed elsewhere [2,3].

Alternatively, ferrocene in ferrocene-phenol hybrid prodrugs can mediate irreversible intramolecular oxidation of C–H bonds with formation of strongly electrophilic quinone methide derivatives as exemplified by hydroxyferrocifens and their analogues [8,9].

Our group develops since 2005 anticancer AF prodrugs (e.g. p1 [10] and p2 [11] in Scheme 1).

These prodrugs are activated in the presence of elevated ROS levels present in cancer cells [5–7,10,11]. Since the intracellular ROS level in most normal cells at homeostasis is very low, the AF prodrugs stay inactive in these cells. Upon the activation, the AF prodrugs generate AF drugs in cancer cells, which can catalyze generation of highly toxic $\text{HO}\bullet$ thereby killing the cells. The latter electron transfer reaction to H_2O_2 is very efficient. However, its full potential is not explored due to the instability of the AF drugs under oxidative conditions leading to their very short lifetime in cancer cells: < 1 h. The estimation is based on the model experiment in cell free settings. In particular, upon the oxidation of AF's, these drugs lose the cyclopentadienyl ligands and release iron ions [10,11]. The latter ions can be efficiently scavenged by endogenous Fe ligands leading to inhibition of the toxic effect of AF's [10].

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Scheme 1. Activation of known AF prodrugs p1 and p2 as well as new 4-FcAn-prodrugs p3 and p4 in the presence of ROS. The scheme illustrates that oxidized AF's (e.g. d1⁺ and d2⁺) are less stable than oxidized 4-FcAn's (e.g. d3⁺ and d4⁺).

Herein we addressed this problem by replacing the AF part in the AF prodrugs with 4-ferrocenylaniline (4-FcAn, [Scheme 1](#)). Our hope was that 4-FcAn will be more stable than AF, but still sufficiently electron rich to donate an electron to H₂O₂. We confirmed that 4-FcAn fulfills both of these conditions. We found that prodrugs based on 4-FcAn increase the level of both total ROS and mitochondrial ROS in representative cancer cells (human ovarian cancer A2780 cells) thereby leading to their death. Their anticancer activity towards A2780 cells is substantially higher than that of the parent, structurally related AF-prodrugs.

2. Experimental

2.1. General

Commercially available chemicals of the best quality from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany) were obtained and used without purification. MitoSOXTM Red (mitochondrial superoxide indicator, catalog: M36008, InvitrogenTM) was obtained from Fisher Scientific. NMR spectra were acquired on a Bruker Avance 300 or a Bruker Avance 400 spectrometer. Electrospray ionization (ESI) or atmospheric pressure photoionization (APPI) mass spectra were recorded on a Bruker ESI MicroTOF II focus or a Bruker maXis 4 G. UV-visible spectra were measured on a Cary 100 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies) by using quartz glass cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL. Fluorescence spectra were acquired on Varioskan Lux Plate Reader (Thermo Fischer) with a sample volume of 200 μ L. The fluorescence of live cells was quantified using a Flow CytoFlex cytometer from Beckman Coulter, Inc. HPLC column from Macherey-Nagel

REF 760,311.20 (stationary phase EC50/2 NUCLEODUR C18 HTec; particle size 5 μ m, length 50 mm) was used for HPLC. The purity of the prodrugs used in the biological assays was determined by elemental analysis (C, H, and N analysis). This analysis was performed in the microanalytical laboratory of the chemical institutes of the Friedrich-Alexander-University of Erlangen-Nürnberg, Erlangen, Germany. According to the obtained data, the purity of all new compounds was greater than 95%.

2.2. Synthesis ([Scheme 2](#))

Intermediates 2 [12], 3 [13], control prodrugs p1 [10], p2 [11] and drug d1*HCl [14] were obtained by known protocols.

Prodrug p3. 4-Ferrocenylbenzoic azide (4.51 g, 13.6 mmol) was added to an oven-dried flask (under nitrogen atmosphere). The solids were dissolved in anhydrous toluene (3 mL/mmol) and to this stirring solution 4-(hydroxymethyl)phenylboronic acid pinacol ester (6.35 g, 27.1 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was then heated to reflux and stirred for 2 h. After cooling to 22 °C, the reaction mixture was transferred to a round-bottom flask and all volatiles were removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified *via* silica gel column chromatography (cyclohexane:acetone / 4:1 / v/v). The obtained crude product was recrystallized from acetone to give product p3 as a red-orange solid (5.10 g, 9.49 mmol, 70%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone) δ [ppm] 7.76 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 7.57 - 7.47 (m, 2H), 7.45 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 5.22 (s, 1H), 4.72 - 4.66 (m, 1H), 4.32 - 4.26 (m, 1H), 4.02 (s, 3H), 1.34 (s, 5H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, Acetone) δ 205.42, 205.22, 205.02, 170.00, 153.37, 140.23, 137.20, 134.73, 133.62, 127.19, 126.99, 126.33, 118.36, 85.40, 83.68, 69.31, 68.55, 65.96, 65.74, 59.64, 40.94, 29.52, 29.33, 29.14, 28.94, 28.75, 28.56, 28.37, 24.31, 24.05, 23.55, 20.46, 19.93, 16.92, 14.07, 13.61, 7.27. HRMS (APPI): calcd. for C₃₀H₃₂BFeNO₄ [M + H]⁺: 537.1768; found: 537.1790. Elemental analysis: calcd. for C₃₀H₃₂BFeNO₄: C, 67.07; H, 6.00; N, 2.61. found: C, 67.01; H, 6.31; N, 2.72.

Prodrug p4. The prodrug p3 (500 mg, 0.931 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 3.0 mL) and Cs₂CO₃ (910 mg, 2.79 mmol) and CsI (242 mg, 0.931 mmol) was added in one portion at 22 °C. After 15 min, propargyl chloride (73.0 mg, 0.977 mmol) was added in one portion. The mixture was left stirring for 48 h. When the reaction was complete (monitored by TLC) DMF was removed in vacuo and dichloromethane (DCM) was added. The obtained suspension was filtered, and DCM from the filtrate was removed in vacuo. The remaining crude material was subjected to column chromatography (cyclohexane:acetone / 3:1 / v/v). The fractions with the product were evaporated and dried in vacuo overnight to give the product p4 (341 mg, 0.593 mmol, 64%) as yellowish powder. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone) δ 7.72 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.61 - 7.55 (m, 1H), 7.32 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 5.20 (s, 1H), 4.79 - 4.73 (m, 1H), 4.51 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 4.37 - 4.30 (m, 1H), 4.03 (s, 3H), 1.31 (s, 7H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, Acetone) δ 205.42, 205.22, 205.02, 170.00, 153.37, 140.23, 137.20, 134.73, 133.62, 127.19, 126.99, 126.33, 118.36, 85.40, 83.68, 69.31, 68.55, 65.96, 65.74, 59.64, 40.94, 29.52, 29.33, 29.14, 28.94, 28.75, 28.56, 28.37, 24.31, 24.05, 23.55, 20.46, 19.93, 16.92, 14.07, 13.61, 7.27.

Scheme 2. Outline of synthesis of prodrugs p3 and p4. Reaction conditions: (a) 4-aminobenzoic acid, NaNO₂, HCl; (b) 1. ethyl chloroformate, NEt₃, 2. NaN₃; (c) 4-hydroxymethylphenylboronic acid pinacol ester; (d) propargylchloride, CsI, Cs₂CO₃.

Table 1

Maximal increase of the fluorescence intensity ((dF/dt)₀, λ_{ex} = 501 nm, λ_{em} = 523 nm) upon oxidation of DCFH by H₂O₂ in the presence of drugs, prodrugs and controls.

Compound	Inclination value: $\nu_0 = (dF/dt)_0$ (min ⁻¹)	Relative rate increase
p1	78.7 ± 5.4	13.9
p2	82.4 ± 3.0	14.5
d3	28.5 ± 3.8	5.0
p3	18.4 ± 2.4	3.2
p4	11.7 ± 1.9	2.1
FeSO ₄	89.3 ± 2.2	15.7
Ferrocene (1)	5.6 ± 0.7	1.0
background	5.7 ± 0.3	1.0 (reference)

Fig. 1. A: Change of absorbance at 562 nm in time of solutions containing methanol (blue trace), d1 (10 μM, red trace) and drug d3 (10 μM, back trace) dissolved in methanol / PBS (phosphate buffered saline, 10 mM, pH 7.4) / ammonium acetate buffer, 100 mM, pH 7.4) (v/v/v) containing ferrozine (1 mM). The spectra (shown in Figs. S5, S1) were acquired at 23.5 ± 1.5 °C. B: Photos of cuvettes taken for fresh samples (time=0) and samples at the end of the experiment (time= 6 h).

HRMS (APPI): calcd. for C₃₃H₃₅BFeNO₄ [M + H]⁺: 576.2003; found: 576.2006. Elemental analysis: calcd. for C₃₀H₃₂BFeNO₄: C, 68.90; H, 5.96; N, 2.43. Found: C, 69.20; H, 6.15; N, 2.29.

2.3. Determination of stability of representative drugs by quantification of released Fe²⁺

Drug d1·HCl was freshly synthesized before this experiment [14]. Drug d3 was prepared as previously described [15]. This experiment is based on our previous study of stability of AF prodrugs by monitoring Fe²⁺ release [16].

In cuvettes, stock solutions of the drugs (10 μL, 1 mM, in MeOH) or carrier (10 μL, MeOH) was mixed with MeOH (490 μL), phosphate buffered saline (PBS buffer, 400 μL, pH 7.4, 10 mM) and ferrozine solution (100 μL, 10 mM, in ammonium acetate buffer (100 mM)), followed by measurement of UV-visible spectra at 23.5 ± 1.5 °C at periodic time intervals over 6 h (Fig. S5). The increase of absorbance at 562 nm was used to quantify Fe²⁺ ions. The amount of these ions reflect the degree of decomposition of the drugs (Fig. 1, Table 1).

2.4. CV measurements

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was measured on a C-3 cell stand device from BASi® company. Drugs (~1 mM) and tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF₆, 0.1 M; supporting electrolyte) were dissolved in acetonitrile (3 mL) and degassed with nitrogen flow for 5 min with stirring prior to the measurement. Ag/AgCl reference electrode, Pt counter electrode and glassy carbon (GC) working electrode were used. Scan rate was 50 mV/s. The measurements were conducted at 23 °C.

2.5. Monitoring generation of ROS in cell free settings

2',7'-Dichlorofluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA, 4.9 mg) was dissolved in 100 μL DMF and mixed with 0.1 M NaOH (900 μL). This mixture was incubated on a shaker for 30 min at 25 °C in the dark to obtain 10 mM 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein (DCFH) stock solution. Next, 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid buffer (MOPS buffer 100 mM, pH: 7.4) containing N,N,N',N'-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, 10 mM), glutathione (GSH, 5 mM) and H₂O₂ (10 mM) was prepared. Finally, DCFH was diluted in this buffer to 10 μM as final concentration. After adding 200 μL of above solution to each well, monitoring of the fluorescence was started at 37 °C (λ_{ex}: 501 nm, λ_{em}: 523 nm). After 10 min, the compound (2 μL, 1 mM in DMF) was added to have final concentration of 10 μM. DMF (2 μL) and FeSO₄ (2 μL, 1 mM in DMF) were used as controls. The measurement was conducted for 300 min (Table 1).

2.6. Determination of n-octanol/water partition coefficient (logP)

Solutions of references and new prodrugs were prepared by dissolving them in the mixture of dichloromethane/CH₃OH. Commercially available reverse phase (RP) plates for thin layer chromatography (TLC, Macherey-Nagel, Germany, Alugram Aluminiumfolien RP-18 W/UV254, stationary phase thickness: 0.15 mm) were used. The plates were manually spotted with freshly prepared solutions of the analytes at 10 mm distance from the edge of the plate. As the eluent, a mixture acetonitrile/aqueous 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid (MOPS) buffer (100 mM, pH 7.4) (5/5, v/v) was used. The solvent migration distance was around 4.5 cm. The plates were visually inspected under the UV-light (254 nm) and each zone was clearly marked and its distance was manually measured. All measurements were done in at least triplicate and average values were used in further calculations. All experiments were performed at ambient temperature (22 ± 2 °C). A set of reference compounds was used, for which logP-values were previously reported: perylene (6.25), anthracene (4.50), benzophenone (3.18), and naphthol (2.85). A calibration plot of R_f versus logP, which was obtained based on these data, was used to determine logP values of new prodrugs (See Figs. S6, S1). Determined logP values: d3 - 3.97 ± 0.10; p3 - 5.67 ± 0.12; p4 - 5.57 ± 0.11. The latter two values correspond to hydrolyzed prodrugs p3 and p4 (see the Section 2.7). The parent pinacol esters p3 and p4 are very hydrophobic (logP > 6). Their logP values cannot be accurately determined using our approach.

2.7. Evaluation of hydrolysis of prodrugs in the aqueous neutral solution by using HPLC-UV-MS

Stock solutions of prodrugs (p2 and p4, 0.5 or 3 mM) in DMSO were first prepared. Then they were diluted 100-fold (final concentration: 5 or 30 μM) with TEAA (triethylammonium acetate buffer - pH 7.0, 1.25 mM). As a control, pure DMSO was diluted in the same way. This probe was used to acquire background HPLC trace.

Table 2
Effects of the prodrugs/controls on the viability of A2780 cell lines (IC₅₀ values) after 48 h incubation.

Drug/Control	IC ₅₀ (μM)
p1	32.2 ± 3.5
p2	14.6 ± 1.8
d3	19.6 ± 1.2
p3	13.8 ± 1.0
p4	8.3 ± 0.9
FeHQ (positive control) ^a	3.4 ± 0.4
Ferrocene (negative control)	>50

^a Ferric chloride/8-hydroxyquinoline complex (1/2).

After the probes (20 μL) of these solutions were incubated at 37 °C for 1 h at 37 °C and at 700 rpm shaking, they were injected to HPLC coupled to UV-visible detector (detection of absorbance at 254 nm) and electrospray mass spectrometric detector (detection of positively charged ions in the *m/z* range of 300–1200 Da) and the analytes were separated by using gradients of CH₃CN (containing formic acid, 0.1%, v/v) in water (containing ammonium formate, 10 mM and formic acid, 0.1%, v/v) from 15% to 95%. (Figs. S6, S1).

2.8. Determination of viability of A2780 cells in the presence of the prodrugs

Cells and cell culture: Human ovarian cancer cell line A2780 was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and cultivated to around 80% confluence.

MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay

The medium was removed, and the cells were washed two times with DPBS, trypsinated, and resuspended in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. This suspension was spread in the wells of a 96-well microtiter plate (25,000 cells per well per 100 μL) and left standing at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) for overnight. Stock solutions of prodrugs/controls of different concentrations (1 μL, solvent DMSO, final concentrations in wells were 5, 10, 30, 50 μM for prodrugs, 5, 2, 1 μM for positive control and 50 μM for negative control) were added to the wells and incubated for 48 h. Three experiments were conducted for each concentration of the prodrug. Finally, MTT (20 μL of the solution prepared by dissolving MTT (5 mg) in DPBS buffer (1 mL)) was added to each well, incubated for 3 h, treated with sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) solution (90 μL, 10% solution in 0.01 M aqueous HCl), and incubated overnight. Afterward, the intensity of the absorbance at 590 nm was measured. MTT is converted in live cells to the blue dye with the absorbance maximum λ_{max} at 590 nm. The absorbance at 690 nm was taken as a baseline value. The baseline corrected absorbance at 590 nm (A(590 nm) - A(690 nm)) was applied to calculate the relative number of viable cells. IC₅₀ values (the concentration of a compound, at which 50% of cells remain viable) were determined for each tested compound and control (Table 2).

2.9. Prodrug-induced production of intracellular ROS

Total intracellular ROS

A2780 cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin in a 96-well microtiter plate (total volume 100 μL) at a density of 250 cells/μL one day before the experiment. On the day of the experiment, the cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) (500 μL). CM-DCFH-DA (5-(6-chloromethyl-2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate, Thermo-Fisher) solution (0.1 mM in DMSO, 1 μL) was

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammetry of ferrocene, prodrugs p3 and p4 as well as drug d3. Solvent: acetonitrile. Supporting electrolyte: TBAPF₆. Scanning rate: 50 mV/s. Electrodes: Ag/AgCl reference electrode, Pt counter electrode and glassy carbon (GC) working electrode. Temperature: 23 °C.

added (final concentration 1 μM) and the cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C for 15 min. Afterwards the supernatant was removed, the cells were washed with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (100 μL) was added followed by addition of compounds / positive and negative controls (1 μL of stock solutions in DMSO, final concentration of prodrugs was 10 and 30 μM) or carrier only (DMSO, 1 μL, final concentration 1%, v/v) and incubation for 2 h in the dark chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) at 37 °C. Next, the cells were detached from the culture dish using trypsin/EDTA (0.025%/0.01%, v/v, 50 μL). The cells were re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (100 μL). Finally, the fluorescence of live cells (λ_{ex} = 488 nm, λ_{em} = 530 nm) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (Fig. 5A).

Mitochondrial ROS

A2780 cells were seeded in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin in a 96-well microtiter plate (total volume 100 μL) at a density of 250 cells/μL one day before the experiment. On the day of the experiment,

Fig. 3. A: Oxidation of non-fluorescent DCFH probe with hydroxyl radicals with formation of fluorescent product DCF. B: Increase of the fluorescence intensity ($(df/dt)_0$, $\lambda_{ex} = 501$ nm, $\lambda_{em} = 523$ nm) of aqueous solutions of DCFH and H_2O_2 in the presence of different iron compounds (as indicated in the plot). The arrow indicates the time point of addition of the iron compounds. Black straight lines indicate initial (linear) fluorescence growth, which is characterized by parameter $(df/dt)_0$ (Table 1).

the cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (100 μ L) was added followed by addition of compounds (1 μ L of stock solutions in DMSO, final concentration of prodrug was 10 μ M) or carrier only (DMSO, 1 μ L, final concentration 1%, v/v) and incubation for 2 h in the dark chamber filled with CO_2 (5%) at 37 $^{\circ}C$. After that, the cells were washed twice with DPBS buffer and the medium was replaced with HBSS (Hanks' Balanced Salt solution, 100 μ L). MitoSOX (Red Mitochondrial Superoxide Indicator, Thermo-Fisher, Catalog number: M36008) solution (0.5 mM in DMSO, 1 μ L) was added (final concentration 5 μ M) and the cells were incubated in the dark chamber filled with CO_2 (5%) at 37 $^{\circ}C$ for 20 min. Next, the cells were detached from the culture dish using trypsin/EDTA (0.025%/0.01%, v/v, 50 μ L). The cells were re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (100 μ L). Finally, the fluorescence of live cells ($\lambda_{ex} = 488$ nm, $\lambda_{em} = 585$ nm) in the suspensions was determined by using flow cytometry (Fig. 5B).

3. Results and discussion

We investigated stability of an N-unsubstituted 4-FcAn derivative d3 in aqueous solution at neutral pH under aerobic conditions and compared it to that of AF under identical conditions (Fig. 1). We used a highly sensitive photochromic reaction of ferrozine with Fe^{2+} ions, which are released in the result of decomposition of d3 and AF. In this assay a stable red Fe^{2+} complex is formed, which absorbs light at 562 nm. We observed that AF is quickly decomposed under the selected conditions, whereas d3 remained stable over the whole duration of the experiment – 6 h (Fig. 1).

Further, we observed that 4-aminophenyl fragment shifts the redox potential of 4-FcAn d3 by -76 mV with respect to unmodified ferrocene (Fig. 2). This fact indicates that d3 is a better donor of electrons than ferrocene. However, the cathodic shift induced by the 4-aminophenyl moiety is substantially smaller than that induced by an NH_2 group in previously reported aminoferrocene AF: -300 mV [10]. To find out whether d3 is able to catalyze formation of $HO\bullet$ from H_2O_2 , we utilized 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein (DCFH) as a probe. This probe is colorless and non-fluorescent.

In the presence of $HO\bullet$ it forms strongly fluorescent fluorescein derivative DCF (Fig. 3A, Table 1). We observed that d3 accelerates the reaction of DCFH oxidation 5-fold with respect to its spontaneous decomposition (background). However, it is still 2.8–3.1 fold less reactive than known prodrug p1 and a positive control ($FeSO_4$) (Table 1). All these data indicate that FcAn exhibits substantially higher stability than AF that is probably due to its lower propen-

Fig. 4. Effect of prodrugs p1-p4 after 48 h incubation on the viability of human cancer ovarian A2780 cells, determined by the MTT assay. Representative curves are shown. IC_{50} values (the concentration of a compound, at which 50% of cells remain viable) for all studied compounds are provided in Table 2.

sity to oxidation under aerobic conditions. However, it is still sufficiently electron rich to be able to donate an electron to H_2O_2 with formation of $HO\bullet$.

Encouraged by these results we prepared two representative prodrugs p3 and p4 of FcAn, which are analogues of known AF prodrugs p1 and p2, respectively. Their synthesis is outlined in Scheme 2. In particular, known intermediate 3 was converted to the corresponding isocyanate by refluxing in toluene, followed by coupling of 4-hydroxymethylphenylboronic acid pinacol ester with formation of prodrug p3. The latter compound was alkylated in the presence of CS_2CO_3 and CsI with propargyl chloride to obtain prodrug p4. The compounds obtained were characterized by 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy, high resolution atmospheric pressure photoionization (APPI) mass spectrometry and elemental (C, H, N) analysis. Their purity was found to exceed 95%.

Solubility of both prodrugs p3 and p4 was found to be at least 30 μ M in phosphate buffered saline (PBS, 10 mM, pH 7.4), whereas it is increased up to 50 μ M in RPMI medium. Upon dissolution of these compounds in PBS, pinacol ester groups are hydrolyzed within < 1 h (Figs. S6, S1). AF prodrugs behave similarly as previously reported [17]. Due to the quick hydrolysis of the pinacol esters, boronic acids should be active forms of prodrugs p3 and p4. We found that boronic acids of both prodrugs are quite lipophilic: $\log P(p3) = 5.67 \pm 0.12$; $\log P(p4) = 5.57 \pm 0.11$. In contrast, drug d3 is substantially less lipophilic: $\log P(d3) = 3.97 \pm 0.10$. These data

Fig. 5. A: Effects of prodrugs on the intracellular total ROS amount (tROS) in A2780 cells. $F(\text{drug})/F(\text{carrier})$: the increase of the mean fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 525 \text{ nm}$) of (CM-DCFH-DA)-loaded A2780 cells incubated with the prodrugs relative to that of the cells incubated with the carrier only (labelled "carrier"). The "carrier" sample was used as a reference. B: Effects of prodrugs on the intracellular amount of mitochondrial ROS (mROS). $F(\text{drug})/F(\text{carrier})$: the increase of the mean fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 578 \text{ nm}$) of the A2780 cells incubated with the prodrugs, as determined using MitoSOX, relative to that of cells incubated with the carrier only (instead of the prodrugs).

indicate that the passive uptake of both prodrugs is more efficient than that of drug d3, which is an additional advantage of converting FcAn drugs to their prodrugs.

Finally, we investigated cytotoxic effects of prodrugs p3 and p4 on representative cancer cells: human ovarian cancer A2780 cells (Fig. 4, Table 2).

We observed that p3 is more active than its AF analogue p1 ($IC_{50} = 13.8 \pm 1.0$ for p3 versus 32.2 ± 3.5 for p1, $p < 0.001$, Student's t-test). The same trend was found for the prodrug pair p4 and p2 ($IC_{50} = 8.3 \pm 0.9$ for p4 versus 14.6 ± 1.8 for p1, $p < 0.01$, Student's t-test). Both prodrugs are more active than drug d3 ($p < 0.01$, Student's t-test) that is in agreement with higher lipophilicity and higher expected uptake of both prodrugs. We found that both prodrugs p3 and p4 increase the level of total ROS (Fig. 5A) and mitochondrial ROS (Fig. 5B) in A2780 cells. The strength of the increase of the ROS levels correlates with cytotoxic effects of p3 and p4 (compare data in Table 1 and Fig. 5). These data indicate that the cytotoxicity of both new prodrugs is caused by the induction of oxidative stress in cells. Though it is not yet clear how the prodrugs induce ROS production in cells, it is sensible to suggest that they act as catalysts of H_2O_2 activation as it is shown in Scheme 1. This possibility is supported by the fact that these prodrugs are efficient catalysts of $HO\cdot$ production from H_2O_2 in cell free settings (Fig. 3B, Table 1).

4. Conclusions

In the preliminary studies we confirmed that 4-ferrocenylaniline 4-FcAn is stable over long time ($>6 \text{ h}$) in aqueous buffers at aerobic conditions and can donate an electron to H_2O_2 forming $HO\cdot$. In contrast, aminoferrocene AF decomposes within $<1 \text{ h}$ under the same conditions. Based on these data, we expected that 4-FcAn-based ROS activated prodrugs can outperform previously reported AF-based prodrugs due to the expected longer lifetime of the 4-FcAn drug in cells. To test this assumption, we prepared 4-FcAn prodrugs p3 and p4. We found that they induce ROS production both in cell free settings and in cells. Because of the oxidative stress generated in this way cancer cells are killed in the presence of p3 and p4. The ROS-generating ability in cells as well as the anticancer efficacy of the new prodrugs is substantially higher than that of the previously reported structural analogues p1 and p2 thereby supporting the initial hypothesis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interest.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.jorganchem.2022.122305.

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Supporting Information

4-Ferrocenylaniline-based ROS-responsive prodrugs with anticancer activity

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Characterization of new compounds S2-S3

Additional data S4-S5

Figure S1. ¹H-NMR spectrum of Prodrug **p3** in acetone-d₆.

Figure S2. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of prodrug **p3** in acetone-d₆.

Figure S3. ¹H-NMR spectrum of Prodrug **p4** in acetone-d₆.

Figure S4. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of prodrug **p4** in acetone-d₆.

Figure **S5**. UV-visible absorbance spectra of carrier (methanol, inset **A**), drug **1** (10 μ M, inset **B**) or drug **d3** (10 μ M, inset **C**) in methanol / PBS (phosphate buffered saline, 10 mM, pH 7.4) / ammonium acetate buffer, 100 mM, pH 7.4) (v/v/v) containing ferrozine (1 mM). The spectra were acquired at 23.5 ± 1.5 °C at regular time intervals over 6h. The kinetics of absorbance changes at 562 nm are shown in Figure 1 (main text).

Figure **S6**. A calibration plot used for determination of logP values of new compounds.

A control probe lacking any prodrug (1 h incubation)

Prodrug **p2** (upper plot – 5 μM , lower plot – 30 μM , retention time: ~7 min – hydrolyzed product (labelled with black straight line), ~10 min – original prodrug, labelled with red straight line).

Prodrug **p4** (upper plot – 5 μM , lower plot – 30 μM , retention time: ~8 min – hydrolyzed product (labelled with black straight line), ~11 min – original prodrug, labelled with red straight line).

Figure **S6**. HPLC traces of a control probe and prodrugs **p2** and **p4** (both at two concentrations 5 and 30 μM) incubated at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h in aqueous solution at pH 7.

Stable aminoferrocene derivatives inducing production of mitochondrial reactive oxygen species in cancer cells

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Abstract: Elevated level of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and deficient mitochondria are two weak points of cancer cells. Their simultaneous targeting is a valid therapeutic strategy to design highly potent anticancer drugs. The remaining challenge is to limit the drug effects to cancer cells without affecting normal ones. We have previously developed three aminoferrocene (AF)-based drugs, which are activated in the presence of elevated levels of ROS present in cancer cells with formation of electron rich drugs able to generate ROS and reduce mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP). All of them exhibit important drawbacks including either low efficacy or high unspecific toxicity that prevented their application *in vivo* up to date. Herein we describe unusual AF-drugs lacking these drawbacks. These drugs act via an alternative mechanism: they are chemically stable in the presence of ROS, generate mitochondrial ROS in cancer cells, but not normal cells and exhibit anticancer effect *in vivo*.

Introduction

A common consequence of transformation of normal to cancer cells is altered homeostasis of reactive oxygen species (ROS). The transformed cells steadily produce ROS leading to their elevated intracellular level. Furthermore, cancer cells are more sensitive to exogenous ROS than normal cells.^[1] As a consequence, drugs producing ROS can exhibit anticancer effects.^[1] Since ROS is highly cytotoxic, the challenge in the therapeutic application of such drugs is to achieve cancer cell specificity to avoid expected detrimental effects on normal cells and tissues. To address this issue, we have introduced cancer specific aminoferrocene (AF)-based ROS amplifiers (type A drug, R' = PE, Figure 1, the activation is triggered by B-C oxidation).^[2] Other known drugs activated in the presence of ROS and amplifying ROS in cells include procarbazine (HN-NH oxidation),^[3] hydroxyferrocifenes (C-H oxidation)^[4] and organochalcogenides (RXR oxidation, where X=Se or Te).^[5] Activation of the AF-drugs starts with spontaneous hydrolysis of the boronic acid pinacol ester moiety (PE, drugs **1a-7a**, Figure 1A)

with formation of boronic acid derivatives (BA, drugs **1b-7b**, Figure 1A). These further react with ROS, triggering the reaction sequence that leads to formation of AF drug Fc-NH-R'' (Figure 1A, route I). The activation occurs only in ROS-rich (cancer) cells.

Figure 1. A: An outline of two possible routes of activation of AF drugs under oxidative conditions in cancer cells: route I - for type A drugs with R' = PE, BA and route II - for type B drugs with R' = A, F. **B:** A cartoon illustrating generation of mitochondrial ROS (mROS) by type B drugs. **C:** Structures of substituents R' and R'' of drug's shown in A. [Oxidant]: intracellular oxidants, e.g. ROS, peroxidases. Underscored bold numbers indicate new drugs. Bold numbers indicate known reference drugs.

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Redox potentials of Fc-NH-R'' products are shifted -300 to -400 mV with respect to the parent drugs. These electron rich catalyst are capable of donating an electron to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) thereby transforming this less reactive ROS to highly reactive and toxic hydroxyl radicals (HO•).^[2] The latter species can be detected in cytoplasm by using 5(6)-chloromethyl-2',7'-dichlorodihydro-fluorescein diacetate (CM-DCFH-DA). Since the intracellular localization of CM-DCFH-DA is not biased, it senses ROS in the whole cell. In this paper we call the CM-DCFH-DA-sensitive intracellular pool of ROS total ROS or tROS. Both previously developed AF drugs **2a**^[6] and **3a**,^[7] exhibiting anticancer effects in vivo, were found to strongly induce tROS generation. In contrast, they either do not or weakly affect mitochondrial ROS (mROS), detected by using MitoSOX™ probe.

Apart from the elevated ROS, transformed cells have deficient mitochondria. That requires switching glycolysis from typical for normal cells oxidative phosphorylation to anaerobic metabolism.^[8] However, these cells still rely on remaining mitochondrial functions, including, e.g., triphosphate and nucleotide synthesis.^[9] Correspondingly, targeting mitochondria is a viable strategy for anticancer therapy. Based on these considerations, it would be interesting to develop AF drugs able to amplify ROS in proximity to mitochondria (mROS). That would affect mitochondrial function and increase the intracellular ROS level, thereby targeting simultaneously two weak points of cancer cells.

Previously, we have described two ROS-amplifying AF drugs **4a**^[10] and **5a**,^[11] which affect mitochondria in different human cancer cell lines (Figure 1). These drugs exhibit important drawbacks precluding their further development. In particular, **4a** is highly toxic to normal cells, whereas **5a** is taken up by cancer cells poorly leading to its low anticancer efficacy. We have also reported on endoplasmic reticulum (ER)-targeting AF drugs, which generate mROS in human cancer cells.^[12] However, they exhibit substantial unspecific toxicity that precludes their in vivo applications at therapeutically active doses. The observed problems with mROS-generating AF drugs are not surprising. Normal cells are highly sensitive to mROS, since they support stress signaling and induce mutations in mitochondrial and genomic DNAs thereby promoting neoplastic transformation.^[13] Therefore, the cancer vs normal cell specificity for mROS-generating drugs should be especially high to be able to achieve useful therapeutic effects.

We have serendipitously discovered that AF drugs, in which a ROS-sensitive moiety (R' = PE or BA) is replaced with a ROS-resistant fragment (type B drugs, Figure 1A), generate mROS in cancer cells, whereas normal cells remain unaffected. In this paper, we report on detailed studies of these new drugs as well as their close analogues including their synthesis, characterization and basic properties. We studied the mechanism of action of type B drugs and evaluated their anticancer efficacies in vitro (on selected cancer cell lines and primary cells) and in vivo (murine Nemeth-Kellner lymphoma, NK/Ly).

Results and Discussion

Reference drugs **1a-5a** were prepared as previously reported.^[2,6,7,11,12] Drugs **1c-1e**, **2c**, **2d**, **3d**, brominated (**3d**_{Br}, Figure 1A) and fluorogenic (**6d**, **7d**) analogues of some of the drugs as well as control **6a** were prepared as described in detail in the supporting information (S1). All new compounds were >95 % pure

according to C, H, N analysis. Their solubility in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) exceeded 25 μM and in Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) medium containing 5% of fetal bovine serum (FBS) - 100 μM (Table S1, S1).

Preliminary studies

Type A drugs (e.g. **1a-6a**) lose the pinacol fragment (PE) in aqueous neutral solutions within < 2h forming boronic acids (BA, e.g. **1b-6b**, Figure 1A). As previously reported,^[14] the latter species are responsible for the anticancer activity of these drugs. In this work, we used ROS-resistant N,N-dimethylaminocarbonyl (A) analogues as negative controls for type A drugs, since the polarity of the A fragment matches that of the BA fragment. The latter is confirmed by similar n-octanol/water partition coefficients (logP's) of the following pairs of drugs and controls: logP(**1b**) = 2.76 ± 0.23 vs logP(**1c**) = 3.36 ± 0.11 and logP(**2b**) = 3.35 ± 0.25 vs logP(**2c**) = 3.96 ± 0.15 (Table 1). Based on these data, it is expected that passive cellular uptake of the drugs and the controls is comparable to each other. Therefore, differences in their activity should not be related to different uptake efficacies. In contrast to **1a** and **2a**, negative controls **1c** (E_{1/2} = -70 mV vs FcH) and **2c** (E_{1/2} = -10 mV vs FcH) cannot be transformed via route 1 to the electron rich Fc-NH-R'' products (E_{1/2} = -300 to -400 mV vs FcH, Figure 1A). Correspondingly, they (a) are poor catalysts for ROS generation in cell free settings with the efficacies slightly higher than those of ferrocene (FcH, Table 1), (b) induce production of less tROS in representative human cancer ovarian (A2780) cells and (c) are less toxic to A2780 cells than the corresponding drugs **1a** and **2a** (Table 1). In despite of this expected trend, we were puzzled by the fact that both **1c** and **2c** increase the level of tROS in A2780 cells to some degree (**1c** by 2.2 ± 0.6; **2c** by 6.1 ± 0.7 fold as compared to the effect of the carrier only (DMSO)) and exhibit the moderate anticancer activity. In contrast, ferrocene, which has similar to **1c** and **2c** redox potential (Table 1), is not toxic under these conditions. The mechanism of the ROS production by **1c** and **2c** is not related to that of the type A drugs. In the following sections of this paper we will use term "type B" for the new drugs originally derived from negative controls **1c** and **2c** with R' = A, F and CA (Figure 1).

Optimization of the anticancer activity of type B drugs

With the goal to understand the effect of lipophilicity on the anticancer activity of type B drugs, we prepared two analogues of **1c** containing fluorine (**1d**) and a carboxylic acid residue (**1e**) in place of the "A" fragment. **1d** is more (logP = 4.17 ± 0.27) and **1e** (logP = 1.90 ± 0.04) - less lipophilic than **1c**. Redox potentials as well as ROS releasing ability in cell free settings of all these compounds are practically identical (Table 1). We found that the cytotoxicity towards A2780 cells in this small series correlates with lipophilicity (Table 1). To further optimize most active **1d**, we introduced at its carbamate nitrogen either propargyl (P) or 3-(N-piperidinomethyl)benzyl (M) fragments to obtain **2d** and **3d**, correspondingly. Though drug **2d** is slightly more lipophilic than **1d**, it does not lead to the higher cytotoxicity towards A2780 cells. In contrast, substantially more lipophilic **3d** (logP = 6.05 ± 0.07) exhibits the highest activity among all type B drugs reported in this paper: IC₅₀(**3d**) = 7.0 ± 1.3 μM (Table 1). The effect is not only restricted to one cell line. In particular, **3d** is active against Burkitt's lymphoma BL-2 cells (IC₅₀(**3d**) = 3.3 ± 0.3 μM, Table 1)

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as well as primary chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) cells ($IC_{50}(\mathbf{3d}) = 4.8 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{M}$, Figure 2).

Table 1. Comparison of selected properties of type **A** and **B** drugs.

Drug	LogP ^[a]	$E_{1/2}$ ^[b]	ROS releasing efficacy ^[c]	IC_{50} (μM) ^[d]	
				A2780 cells	BL-2 cells
1a	5.00 ± 0.30	-70	57 ± 7	23.9 ± 2.7	35.5 ± 2.5
1b	2.76 ± 0.23	-	-	-	-
1c	3.36 ± 0.11	-70	6 ± 1	46.1 ± 8.5	-
1d	4.17 ± 0.27	-76	7 ± 1	15.0 ± 2.4	17.9 ± 4.8
1e	1.90 ± 0.04	-70	8 ± 1	>50	-
2a	5.51 ± 0.17	-10	54 ± 7	14.2 ± 2.1	20.1 ± 0.9
2b	3.35 ± 0.25	-	-	-	-
2c	3.96 ± 0.15	-10	2.5 ± 0.7	37.1 ± 6.2	-
2d	4.72 ± 0.15	-15	1.1 ± 0.3	16.7 ± 2.5	18.2 ± 1.6
3a	>6.26	-40	54 ± 6	5.6 ± 1.7	3.9 ± 0.3
3b	6.09 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-
3c	5.79 ± 0.03	-35	5 ± 1	-	-
3d	6.05 ± 0.07	-35	2.7 ± 0.8	7.0 ± 1.3	3.3 ± 0.3
3d_Br	6.22 ± 0.07	+116	4.3 ± 0.9	6.2 ± 0.1	-
FcH	3.40	0	0.4 ± 0.2	>50	>50

[a] LogP: n-octanol/water partition coefficients. [b] $E_{1/2}$: redox potentials versus ferrocene/ferrocenium redox couple (FcH/FcH⁺) in mV. [c] ROS releasing efficacy is expressed as the maximal increase of the fluorescence intensity of 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein in the presence of drugs/controls ($(dF/dt)_0$, min⁻¹, F: λ_{ex} = 501 nm; λ_{em} = 525 nm). The increase of $(dF/dt)_0$ for the background (N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 1%, v/v) in 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid buffer (MOPS buffer, 100 mM, pH 7.4) containing N,N,N',N'-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, 10 mM), glutathione (GSH, 5 mM) and H₂O₂ (10 mM) was 0.3 ± 0.1 . [d] IC_{50} : a concentration, at which half of the cells remain viable; A2780: human ovarian cancer cells; BL-2: human Burkitt's lymphoma cells.

Figure 2. Effect of drugs **3a** (inset **A**) and **3d** (inset **B**) on viability of primary cancer and normal cells (CLL, B and T cells). **C:** Effects of **3d** and **3d_Br** on viability of CLL cells. Student's t test: ns – non-significant, $p \geq 0.05$.

The efficacy of **3d** against all studied cells (A2780, BL-2 and CLL cells) was found to be the same as that of the corresponding type A drug **3a** (Table 1, Figure 2, Student's t test).

A mechanism of uptake and anticancer activity of drug **3d**

First, we investigated the uptake of **3d** and known drug **3a** by A2780 cells by monitoring the increase of iron amount ($[\text{Iron}]_i$) in the cells treated with the drugs (Figure 3A). To determine the mechanism of this process, we conducted the experiment at 37 and 4 °C (Figure 3A). At 37 °C the uptake of both drugs was the same and strong, whereas at 4 °C it was significantly inhibited for **3a**, but not affected for **3d**. These data indicate different uptake mechanisms of the drugs. For **3a** it is at least partially energy dependent (active or facilitated) and for **3d** – energy independent (passive).

Figure 3. Uptake efficacy and involvement of ROS in the anticancer effect of type B drug **3d** and reference type A drug **3a**. **A:** The efficacy of uptake of drugs **3a** and **3d** by A2780 cells at 37 °C (black bars) and 4 °C (grey bars), determined by monitoring the increase of the intracellular iron concentration ($[\text{Iron}]_i$). **B:** Increase of tROS (responsive to a CM-DCFH-DA probe) in A2780 cells in the presence of drugs **3a** and **3d** (each 25 μM , 2h incubation), monitored by using flow cytometry: λ_{ex} = 488 nm; λ_{em} = 475-565 nm. The amount of tROS obtained for the "DMSO"-sample was used as a reference and set to "1". The level of tROS for all other samples is indicated in relative units (r.u.). **C:** Effects of N-acetylcysteine (NAC: 1 and 2 mM) on cytotoxicity of a carrier (DMSO), drugs **3a** and **3d** (20 μM). PI= propidium iodide. Live cells are indicated "PI-". Dead (necrotic) cells are indicated "PI+". The sum of "PI-" and "PI+" cells for each sample was set to "1". The relative numbers of "PI-" and "PI+" cells are plotted on the OY axis. **D-O:** Effect of drugs **3a** and **3d** (each 25 μM , 2h incubation) on mROS in A2780 and SBLF9 cells, monitored by fluorescence microscopy: Hoechst (blue color) - λ_{ex} = 365 nm; λ_{em} = 395-495 nm (detection of nuclei by using Hoechst 33342 as a probe); MitoSOXTM (red color) - λ_{ex} = 538-562 nm; λ_{em} = 570-640 nm. **P:** Increase of mROS (responsive to a MitoSOXTM probe) in A2780 cells in the presence of drugs **3a** and **3d** (each 25 μM , incubation: 2h (black bars), 4h (grey bars)), monitored by using flow cytometry: λ_{ex} = 488 nm; λ_{em} = 543-627 nm. Student's t test: * - $p < 0.05$; ** - $p < 0.01$; *** - $p < 0.001$; ns – non-significant, $p \geq 0.05$. Ref: references (colour coded), against which Student's test was applied.

Furthermore, we found that analogously to **3a** drug **3d** induces the statistically significant increase of tROS in A2780 cells. However, the effect of **3d** is substantially weaker than that of **3a** ($p < 0.05$, Student's t test, Figure 3B). Interestingly, the low tROS generated in **3d**-treated cells is still important for the anticancer activity of the drug. This is confirmed by the concentration dependent attenuation of cytotoxicity of **3d** in the presence of the ROS scavenger N-acetyl cysteine (NAC, Figure 3C). As expected, the same effect is also observed for type A drug **3a**. Despite **3d** produces the lower amount of tROS in cells, it exhibits the same anticancer efficacy as the potent ROS generator **3a**. These data indicate that, additionally to tROS, **3d** might induce another intracellular toxicity factor. We found that this factor is mROS. In particular, the level of mROS (detected by using a MitoSOXTM

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probe) in A2780 cells treated either with the carrier or type A drug **3a** for 2 h is very low as indicated by the weak red signal in fluorescence images E and I (Figure 3). Nuclei of the cells were counter-stained with a dye Hoechst 33342 (blue color) that was used as a reference signal for comparing changes in the intensity of the red fluorescence between different samples. In contrast to the control probes, the level of mROS in the **3d**-treated cells is substantially higher as indicated by the intense red signal in image M. These qualitative microscopic data were fully confirmed by the accurate quantification of the intracellular mROS level using flow cytometry (Figure 3P). Since **3d** itself is not a ROS amplifier (in contrast to **3a**) as confirmed by the ROS-release experiment in cell free setting (Table 1), mROS should be generated indirectly. To get a hint on how this can happen, we investigated effects of **3d** on mitochondria and lysosomes of cancer cells. Mitochondria were selected, since drug-induced disturbance of their function can lead to the inefficient electron transfer causing the electron leakage and formation of mROS. Lysosomes were selected, since **3d** could be accumulated in these organelles due to the presence of a piperidine moiety (a lysosomal carrier) in its structure. By using mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP) sensitive probe rhodamine 123 (R123), we found that both **3d** and **3a** strongly reduce MMP in A2780 cells, whereas **2a** is also active, but less efficient (Figure 4A).

Figure 4. Effect of a carrier (DMSO), drugs **2a**, **3a** and **3d** (each 25 μ M, incubation time: 1h (black bars) and 2h (grey bars)) on mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP, probe: R123, inset A) and the lysosome-specific fluorescence (probe acridine orange (AO), inset B). Monitoring by flow cytometry: for R123 - $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 475$ -565 nm; for AO - $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 645$ -745 nm. Student's t test: ** - $p < 0.01$; *** - $p < 0.001$; ns – non-significant, $p \geq 0.05$. Ref: references (colour coded), against which Student's test was applied.

The effect of both type A drugs **2a** and **3a** is saturated after 2h incubation, whereas type B drug **3d** is acting slower. In particular, the MMP of A2780 cells is decreased stronger after 4h than after 2h incubation with **3d** ($p < 0.01$, Student's t test). These data indicate that mROS generated by **3d** can be caused by **3d**-induced reduction of MMP in cancer cells.

Further, we found that drug **3d** quenches the fluorescence of A2780 cells loaded with lysosome-specific probe acridine orange (AO). In contrast to the MMP, this effect is saturated already after 2h incubation. These data might indicate that **3d** is first accumulated in lysosomes before affecting the MMP. As previously reported^[7] **3a** also affects the fluorescence of the AO-loaded cells, whereas **2a** lacking in its structure the piperidine moiety (lysosomal carrier) is not active.

Intracellular species responsible for the anticancer effect of **3d**

To clarify, which intracellular species **3d** or **3d⁺** are responsible for the anticancer activity we conducted a series of experiments in cell free settings and in cells.

Type B drug **3d** is slightly more electron rich than unmodified ferrocene FcH: $E_{1/2}$ (versus FcH/FcH⁺) = -35 mV. Accordingly, it catalyzes transformation of H₂O₂ to HO• 6.8-fold more efficiently than FcH (Table 1). In this reaction **3d** donates an electron to H₂O₂ forming **3d⁺** at least in catalytic amounts. However, in HPLC of the mixture of **3d** (100 μ M) and H₂O₂ (10 mM) we observed only the peak corresponding to **3d**. More polar **3d⁺**, which was expected to elute at the shorter incubation, was not detected (Figure 5A, B). An analogous type B drug **2d** is more electron rich than **3d**: $E_{1/2}$ (versus FcH/FcH⁺) = -70 mV. However, it is also not oxidized in the presence of H₂O₂ as it is evidenced from both HPLC (data not shown) and UV-visible spectroscopy: the absence of a typical for ferrocenium broad absorbance band at ~600 – 900 nm corresponding to the ligand-to-metal (“L→M”) transition (Figure 5C, E).^[15] In another control experiment conducted under the same conditions, the “L→M” transition band at ~900 nm was observed in the spectrum of the mixture of type A drug **2a** (560 μ M) and H₂O₂ (10 mM) (Figure 5D). The intensity of this band steadily grows for over 50 min after addition of H₂O₂ to the solution of **2a** (Figure 5E). The latter behavior was expected based on the previously reported mechanism of **2a** activation by ROS via route I (Figure 1A). We further found that oxidation of type B drugs is possible in the presence of a mixture of H₂O₂ and horseradish peroxidase (HRP), which is a stronger oxidant than H₂O₂ alone. This is indicated by the appearance of the “L→M” transition band in the UV-visible spectrum of the solution containing **2d**, H₂O₂ and HRP (Figure 5C). **2d⁺** is formed almost instantaneously after the HRP addition **2d** and H₂O₂ (Figure 5E).

Figure 5. A, B: HPLC analysis of solutions of **3d** (100 μ M) dissolved in a mixture of CH₃CN (23 %, v/v) in aqueous triethylammonium acetate buffer (121 mM, pH 7.4). The solutions were incubated for 2 min and 4h in the absence (A) and presence of H₂O₂ (B, 10 mM) before the analysis. C: UV-visible spectra of solutions of **2d** (red trace), **2d** incubated with H₂O₂ for 1 h (black trace), **2d** incubated with H₂O₂ and horseradish peroxidase (HRP) for 1 h (blue trace). “L→M”: ligand to metal. D: UV-visible spectra of solutions of **2a** (red trace) and **2a** incubated with H₂O₂ for 1 h (black trace). E: Dependence of the intensity of “L→M” transitions from time in UV-visible spectra of solutions of **2d** ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 760$ nm) and **2a** ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 900$ nm). At the time points indicated by arrows H₂O₂ and HRP were added. Other conditions for C, D and E: solvent - methanol/PBS buffer (pH 7.4), 5/3.5, v/v; [drug] = 560 μ M; [H₂O₂] = 10 \pm 1 mM; [HRP] = 110 \pm 30 nM. F: Dependence of the fluorescence intensity ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 358$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 478$ nm) from time of the solution of **2d** (20 μ M) in acetonitrile/PBS buffer (pH 7.4), 10/79, v/v. At the time points indicated by arrows H₂O₂ (10 \pm 1 mM) and HRP (110 \pm 30 nM) were added. The initial fluorescence intensity is equal to 0.5 \pm 0 a.u. (arbitrary units). The end fluorescence intensity is equal to 71 \pm 3 a.u.

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For the study of possible oxidation of type B drugs in live cells we prepared a fluorogenic analogue of **3d** containing a 7-hydroxycoumarine dye – **7d**. As controls we also prepared **6d**, which is lacking a piperidine moiety (a fluorogenic version of **2d**), and **6a** (a representative fluorogenic type A drug). These drugs are practically not fluorescent due to efficient the photoinduced electron transfer (PET) from the ferrocenyl moiety to the excited state of the dye. Upon oxidation to the ferrocenium species, the fluorescence of **6a** (via route I) **6d** and **7d** (both via route II) is increased, since PET becomes impossible. The experimental data illustrating this behavior for drug **7d** are provided in Figure 5F. Similarly to its analogue **3d**, drug **7d** is practically not responsive to H₂O₂, whereas it is efficiently oxidized by a mixture of H₂O₂ and HRP that leads to the strong and quick increase of the fluorescence intensity.

By using fluorescence microscopy, we found that A2780 cells loaded with **7d** exhibit weak, but significant fluorescence, whose intensity is not increased by the treatment of the cells with H₂O₂ (Figure 6A-C). In contrast, **6d**-loaded A2780 cells were found to be non-fluorescent. However, by using flow cytometry, which is a more sensitive method, we observed that both **6d**- and **7d**-loaded A2780 and BL-2 cells fluoresce significantly stronger ($p < 0.01$ or less, Student's *t* test) than the cells treated with DMSO only (Figure 6D, E). These data indicate that at least some **6d**⁺ and **7d**⁺ are formed within the cells from **6d** and **7d** correspondingly. This reaction cannot triggered by H₂O₂ (compare B and C in Figure 6), but by some other oxidant.

Figure 6. A-C: Fluorescence images ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 335\text{-}383$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 420\text{-}470$ nm) of A2780 cells incubated with fluorogenic drugs **6d** (inset A), **7d** (inset B) and **7d** followed by H₂O₂ (inset C). [Drugs]= 25 μM ; [H₂O₂]= 10 mM. The cells were first incubated with the drugs for 2h, washed and incubation for further 1h with H₂O₂. D: Monitoring uptake/activation of **6a**, **6d** (both 25 μM) and **7d** (1 μM) in A2780 (inset D) and BL-2 cells (inset E) by using flow cytometry: detection at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 405\text{-}495$ nm. Student's *t* test: * - $p < 0.05$; ** - $p < 0.01$; *** - $p < 0.001$; ns – non-significant, $p \geq 0.05$. Ref: references (colour coded), against which Student's test was applied.

Based on the reactivity of **3d** and **7d** in cell free settings (Figure 5), we assume that this oxidant can be an intracellular peroxidase or the oxidant with the “peroxidase-like” activity, e.g. Fe²⁺/H₂O₂. A2780 and BL-2 cells loaded with type A drug **6a** are stronger fluorescent than those loaded with type B drugs **6d** and **7d** (Figure 6D, E). This indicates that **6a** forms the higher amount of ferrocenium species in cells than **6d** and **7d** that is in agreement with properties of type A and B drugs in cell free settings discussed above (Figure 5C, D, E).

To find out whether the ferrocenium species derived from **3d** are important for the anticancer activity of this drug, we prepared its analogue brominated at the ferrocenyl fragment **3d**_{Br} (Figure 1A). The redox potential of **3d**_{Br} ($E_{1/2}$, versus FcH/FcH⁺) is 116 mV, which is by 151 mV higher than the redox potential of **3d**. These data indicate that **3d**_{Br} is more resistant towards oxidation than **3d**. Therefore, we could expect that in cells **3d**_{Br} will form the lower amount of the ferrocenium species than **3d**.

We observed that after 2h incubation with A2780 cells **3d**_{Br} produce similar amount of tROS, but less mROS than **3d** ($p < 0.05$, Student's *t* test). However, the effects of **3d**_{Br} and **3d** on the level of mROS at 4h incubation were found to be the same. Further, we observed that cytotoxicity of **3d**_{Br} and **3d** towards A2780 and CLL cells are identical (Table 1, Figure 2C). Assuming that **3d**_{Br} and **3d** act via the same mechanism, these results allow concluding that the reduced form (**3d**) rather than the oxidized one (**3d**⁺) are responsible for ROS-generating and anticancer properties of drug **3d**.

Cancer cell specificity of drug **3d**

We investigated cancer cell specificity of **3d** in two experiments. First, by using fluorescence microscopy we compared the mROS level in representative cancer (human ovarian A2780 cells) and normal cells (human SBLF9 fibroblasts). These cells were loaded with drug **3d**, incubated for 2h, washed, loaded with MitoSOXTM probe (mROS probe) and imaged. We observed the increased level of mROS in the cancer cells, but not in the normal cells.

In the latter experiment we compared cancer and normal cells of different origins: human ovarian carcinoma versus human primary fibroblasts. Therefore, the effect observed is not necessarily caused by differences in cancer versus normal cellular phenotype. To address this issue, we compared anticancer effects of **3d** towards cancer and normal cells originated from blood. They included chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL), B- and T-cells. We found that the type A drug **3a** exhibits CLL cell specificity over both B- and T-cells (Figure 2A), which is agreement with the previously reported data.^[7] In contrast, the type B drug **3d** kills both CLL and B-cells with similar efficacy, whereas it is substantially less toxic towards T-cells. These data indicate that **3d** is not fully cancer cell specific. It can affect at least some normal cells thereby leading to the undesired toxicity.

Antitumor effects of **3d**

We evaluated the anticancer activity of **3d** in C57/BL6N mice carrying Nemeth-Kellner lymphoma (NK/Ly). The drug was formulated in cremophore/ethanol/saline (1/1/4, v/v/v) mixture. As a negative control we injected the mice with the carrier only. Furthermore, **3a** formulated in the same carrier was used as a positive control. The drugs and the carrier were injected at the dose of 7-8 mg/kg 10 times, every second day. The first injection was done one day after the tumor inoculation. On day 34, when the tumor weight in the carrier group was approaching 15 % of initial animal weight, all animals were sacrificed, tumors were removed, weighted and fixed (Figure 7A). We observed that the average tumor weight in the **3a** group was lower than that in the carrier group ($p < 0.05$, Mann-Whitney test). In contrast, **3d** did not reduce the average tumor weight as compared to the carrier group. Under our experimental settings we observed that tumors grow heterogeneously in the carrier group. Therefore, only strong antitumor effects will be apparent at the end point measurement averaged over all animals. We observed that **3d** inhibits the growth of large tumors (> 5.2 g, dotted red square area in Figure 7A). In particular, only one animal with such a large tumor was present in the **3d** group (7%, N=14). In the positive control **3a** group no such animals were detected (0%, N=14), whereas the carrier group had 5 such animals (26%, N=19). We also found that tumors with masses <0.6 g consist mostly of granulomatous

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tissue. They were identified as regressing tumors. All other tumors were identified as progressing tumors. At the end of the in vivo experiment 3 animals in the **3d** group (21%), 7 animals in the **3a** group (50%) and no animals in the carrier group (0%) had regressing tumors (Figure S2, S1).

Figure 7. A: Tumor weigh in the studied groups at the end of the experiment. Statistic parameters were calculated by Mann-Whitney test. Dotted black line demonstrate the weight limit of 0.6 g, below which abundant granulomatous tissue was found in tumors. The area of large tumors is indicated with dotted red square. B-D: Histological analysis of selected tumors demonstrating blood vessels located deep inside tumor masses in the carrier (inset B), type A drug **3a** (C) and type B drug **3d** (D) groups. Blood vessels are indicated with green asterisks. Cell decay is indicated with yellow arrows. Tumor cells entering blood vessels space are shown with blue arrows. H7E staining, 40x 0.75 high-NA objective.

Histological analysis of tumor samples demonstrated that in all groups tumors are highly vascularized, covered by the distinct border of connective tissue surrounded by granulomatous tissue. Especially strong difference between the groups is observed close to the blood vessels indicated with green asterisks in Figure 7B-D. They are surrounded by the abundant number of growing tumor cells in the carrier group (Figure 7B). An abundant tumor death (blue arrows), formation of picnotic nuclei, apoptotic debris and subsequent necrotic areas (pink color) were observed in the **3a** group (Figure 7C). Furthermore, no tumor cells were observed in vessel spaces making a general impression of the strong toxic action of the compounds coming from deep supplying vessels inside the tumors. In the **3d** group in the area of blood vessels the tumor growth is much less abundant than in the carrier group and some dying cells (blue arrows) are observed. Additional dying tumor cells in other areas are also observed (yellow arrows) (Figure 7C). Thus, **3d** exhibits the moderate anticancer effect in vivo, which is however weaker than that of positive control **3a** at the selected conditions.

Conclusion

By the optimization the chemical structure of type B aminoferrocene-based drug **1c** we could substantially improve its anticancer efficacy towards human ovarian cancer A2780 cells from IC_{50} $46.1 \pm 8.5 \mu\text{M}$ for **1c** to $7.0 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{M}$ for the optimized drug **3d**. We found that **3d** is cytotoxic also towards other cells (Burkitt's lymphoma BL-2 cell line and primary chronic lymphocytic leukemia CLL cells) in the low μMolar range. The anticancer efficacies of **3d** and the best known type A drug **3a** in

vitro are comparable. However, the cancer cell specificity of **3d** is lower than that of **3a**. For example, **3d** exhibits significant toxicity towards B-cells, whereas it does not affect T-cells and SBLF9 fibroblasts. In contrast, **3a** is not toxic to all mentioned normal cells. Drugs **3d** and **3a** acts differently from each other. In particular, the uptake of **3d** occurs via the passive mechanism, whereas the uptake of **3a** is energy dependent. **3d** induces production of mitochondrial ROS (mROS), whereas **3a** generates total ROS and no mROS. Drug **3d** does not generate ROS directly as **3a** does, but rather act indirectly by reducing the mitochondrial membrane potential. By using the fluorogenic version of **3d**, we observed that it is partially oxidized in cells with formation of ferrocenium species. However, an analogue **3d_Br**, which has substantially higher redox potential than **3d**, was found to have the same anticancer efficacy as **3d**. These data indicated that the neutral form of the drug is responsible for its anticancer properties. Finally, we found that **3d** exhibits moderate anticancer activity in vivo against murine Nemeth-Kellner lymphoma in C57/BL6N mice. Thus, this is the only AF-drug, acting by increasing the level of intracellular mROS, which is applicable in vivo. All other known drugs either exhibit low activity^[11] or are too toxic.^[10]

Experimental Section

All experimental data, synthesis and assay protocols are provided in supporting information.

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Keywords: Ferrocene • Drug • Mitochondrion • Reactive Oxygen Species • Anticancer

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Stable aminoferrocene derivatives inducing production of mitochondrial reactive oxygen species in cancer cells

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General

Commercially available chemicals of the best quality from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany) and Alfa-Aesar (Germany) were obtained and used without purification. NMR spectra were acquired on a Bruker Avance 300 (Ettlingen, Germany) or Bruker Avance 400 (Ettlingen, Germany). ESI mass spectra were recorded on a Bruker ESI MicroTOF II (Bremen, Germany) or Bruker maXis 4G mass spectrometers (Bremen, Germany). C/H/N elemental analysis was performed in the microanalytical laboratory of the Department Chemistry and Pharmacy, Organic Chemistry Chairs 1 and 2 of the Friedrich-Alexander-University of Erlangen-Nuremberg. UV-visible spectra were measured on a Cary 100 UV-visible spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies, Frankfurt am Main, Germany) by using either quartz glass cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Müllheim, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL or micro-cuvettes with a sample volume of 100 μ L (BRAND GmbH, Wertheim, Germany). Fluorescence spectra were acquired on a Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer using fluorescence cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Müllheim, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL. The fluorescence of live cells was quantified by using a Guava easyCyte™ 6-2L Flow cytometer from Luminex, USA / Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany. The data were processed using the inCyte™ software package (Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany) and the ModFIT LTTM software (Verity Software House, Topsham, ME, USA). Statistical analysis of the data was conducted by using Student's t-test. Two data sets were considered significantly different from each other for $p < 0.05$.

Synthesis

Boronic acid derivatives **1a-5a** were synthesized as previously reported [S1-S6]. ROS resistant derivatives **1c**, **2c**, **1d-3d**, and **1e** were prepared analogously, except that 4-(hydroxymethyl)phenylboronic acid pinacol ester was replaced with either 4-(hydroxymethyl)-N,N-dimethylbenzamide (for **1c**, **2c**) or (4-fluorophenyl)methanol (for **1d-3d**) or 4-(hydroxymethyl)-benzoic acid (for **1e**). Drug **3d**_Br was obtained analogously to **3d**, except that azidocarbonylferrocene was replaced with 1-azidocarbonyl-1'-bromoferrocene. Synthesis of all other compounds (**6a**, **6d**, **7d**) was prepared by using original procedures. Synthetic protocols and characterization data for all new compounds are provided at the end of this document.

Characterization of drugs in cell free settings

Solubility of drugs in aqueous solutions

Drugs were dissolved in DMSO at concentrations of 20 mM, 10 mM, 5 mM, 2 mM, 1.5 mM, 1 mM and 0.2 mM. These solutions (10 μ L) were transferred to quartz cuvettes containing either phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) or Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) medium containing 5% of fetal bovine serum (FBS) (990 μ L) to obtain solutions (or suspensions) with final concentrations of drugs - 200 μ M, 100 μ M, 50 μ M, 20 μ M, 15 μ M, 10 μ M and 2 μ M. The blank solution was measured with solutions containing DMSO only. The absorbance at 790 nm (where no peak of any drug is observed) of the resulting solutions/suspensions was measured and plotted as a function of concentrations of the drugs. The concentration, whose absorbance at 790 nm reaches the twice of that of the blank absorbance (0.04) was considered as a solubility limit. The solubility was calculated based on at least 3 independent experiments (Table S1).

Table **S1**. Solubility of drugs in two different aqueous solutions.

Drugs	Solubility	
	PBS, μ M ⁱ	RPMI (5% FBS), μ M ⁱⁱ
1c	>200	>200
1d	49 \pm 4	121 \pm 5
1e	>200	>200
2c	117 \pm 3	>200
2d	34 \pm 5	125 \pm 14
3d	26 \pm 2	102 \pm 28
6a	126 \pm 6	>180
6d	113 \pm 11	>200

ⁱ PBS: phosphate-buffered saline, pH 7.4.

ⁱⁱ RPMI (5% FBS): Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) medium containing 5% of fetal bovine serum (FBS).

N-Octanol/water partition coefficient (LogP) of drugs

RP-TLC plates from Macherey-Nagel (Germany, Alugram Aluminiumfolien RP-18 W/UV₂₅₄, stationary phase thickness: 0.15 mm) were used in this assay. Three mixtures of aqueous 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid buffer (MOPS, 100 mM, pH 7.4) and acetonitrile (3:2; 1:1; 2:3; v:v) were used as eluents. Naphthol (LogP= 2.85), benzophenone (LogP= 3.18), anthracene (LogP= 4.50) and perylene (LogP=

6.25) were used as literature known references. Freshly prepared solutions of the samples and references (dissolved in acetone) were spotted on the plates. The solvent migration distance was 4.5 cm. The spots of prodrugs and reference compounds were monitored by using UV-shadowing. Each spot was marked and its position relative to the start line was measured to determine R_f values. For boronic ester derivatives **1a-7a** two spots were observed corresponding to the initial ester and its hydrolyzed form **1b-7b** (Figure 1A, main text of the paper). All measurements were done in triplicates (Table 1, main text).

Redox properties of drugs

To analyze the redox properties of drugs, we used cyclic voltammetry (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV). A drug (1 mM) and tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF₆, 0,1 M; supporting electrolyte) were dissolved in acetonitril and degassed with nitrogen flow for 5 min prior to the measurement. Ag/AgCl reference electrode, Pt counter electrode and glassy carbon (GC) working electrode were used. Scan rate was 50 mV/s for CV and 10 mV/s for DPV. The measurements were conducted at 23 °C. Both methods delivered similar redox potentials ($\Delta E_{1/2}$), which are listed in Table 1, main text.

Monitoring generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the presence of either drugs or control compounds in cell free settings

2',7'-Dichlorofluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA, 4.9 mg) was dissolved in N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 100 μ L) and mixed with aqueous NaOH solution (0.1 M, 900 μ L). This mixture was incubated on a shaker for 30 min at 25 °C in the dark to obtain 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein (DCFH) stock solution (10 mM). Next, 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid buffer (MOPS buffer, 100 mM, pH 7.4) containing N,N,N',N'-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, 10 mM), glutathione (GSH, 5 mM) and H₂O₂ (10 mM) was prepared. Finally, DCFH was diluted in this buffer to 10 μ M concentration. Monitoring of the fluorescence (F) was started (λ_{ex} : 501 nm, λ_{em} : 525 nm). After 5 min, the compound was added at the final concentration of 10 μ M. DMF and FeSO₄ in DMF were used as controls. The measurement was conducted for 300 min. The maximal increase of the fluorescence intensity ($(dF/dt)_0$, min⁻¹) was

determined and used for comparison of efficacies of drugs in the release of ROS in cell free settings (Table 1, main text).

Stability of the representative drug 3d in the absence and presence of hydrogen peroxide: monitoring by HPLC

The stock solution of **3d** in DMSO (10 mM, 5 μ L) was added into a mixture of acetonitrile (23 %, v/v) and aqueous triethylammonium acetate buffer (TEAA, 121 mM, pH 7.4, 490 μ L). Then either H₂O (5 μ L) or H₂O₂ (stock solution concentration 1 M; 5 μ L; final concentration 10 mM) were added, and the resultant solution was shaken at 24°C. The final concentration of the drug was 100 μ M. The mixtures were incubated for either 2 min or 4 h, then centrifuged (5 min, 13400 rpm) to obtain clear solution, which were analyzed by HPLC (detection of UV absorbance at 254 nm (Figure 5A, B). Drug **2d** was found to be as stable as **3d** (data not shown).

Oxidation of representative drugs in the presence of hydrogen peroxide and horseradish peroxidase: monitoring by UV-visible spectroscopy

Stock solutions (1.0 mM) of drugs were prepared in MeOH (2.0 mL). A solution of horseradish peroxidase (HRP) was prepared by dissolving 3 mg HRP in PBS buffer (pH 7.4). The solutions of drugs (500 μ L) were added to the PBS buffer (350 μ L) and mixed. Final concentrations of the drugs were 560 μ M. UV-visible spectra (scanning kinetic mode) were recorded between 350 and 900 nm on Agilent Cary 100 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer. After 5 min H₂O₂ (30% (w/w) in H₂O, 1 μ L, final concentration 10 \pm 1 mM) was added, and the measurement of UV-visible spectra was continued for the following 58 min. Then, the stock solution of HRP solution (30 μ L, concentration 110 \pm 30 nM) was added and the measurement of UV-visible spectra was continued. The

overall experiment time was 145 min. This experiment was repeated 3 times at 22 °C for each drug and reference compound (Figure S1, 5E, main text).

Figure S1. **A:** UV-visible spectra of solutions of ferrocene (FcH), FcH incubated with H₂O₂ for 1 h, FcH incubated with H₂O₂ and HRP for 1 h. **B:** UV-visible spectra of freshly prepared solution of NAAF (N-benzylaminoferrocene, NAAF/fresh) and the same solution kept open to air for 60 min (NAAF/aged). **C:** UV-visible spectra of solutions of **2d**, **2d** incubated with H₂O₂ for 1 h, **2d** incubated with H₂O₂ and HRP for 1 h. **D:** UV-visible spectra of solutions of **2a**, **2a** incubated with H₂O₂ for 1 h. Solvent: MeOH/PBS buffer (pH 7.4), 5/3.5, v/v. [Drug]= 560 μM; [H₂O₂]= 10 ± 1 mM; [HRP]= 110 ± 30 nM. “L→M”: ligand to metal.

Oxidation of 7d in the presence of H₂O₂ and HRP

7d (2 mM in DMF, 10 μ L, final concentration 20 μ M) was added to acetonitrile (100 μ L) and mixed with PBS buffer (pH 7.4, 790 μ L). Monitoring of the fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 358$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 478$ nm) of this solution at 37 °C was started. After 5 min, H₂O₂ (30 % (w/w) in H₂O, 1 μ L, final concentration 10 ± 1 mM) was added, and the fluorescence was monitored for 185 min. Further, HRP (10 μ L, final concentration 110 ± 30 nM) was added and the fluorescence was monitored for 110 min (Figure 5F, main text).

In vitro assays

Cells and cell culture

Human ovarian cancer cell line A2780 was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. A2780 cells were grown in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. SBLF9 primary human fibroblasts were isolated via skin biopsy after local anesthesia from a healthy 20-year-old Caucasian male and subsequently cultivated in F-12 Medium supplemented with 15 % fetal bovine serum, 2 % non-essential amino acids and 1 % penicillin/streptomycin.^[S7] All adherent cells (A2780, DU-145, SBLF9) were cultivated to 80–90% confluence and detached from the flask by using trypsin/N,N,N',N'-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) solution (0.025% / 0.01%, w/v) in PBS. Burkitt lymphoma cell line BL-2 was obtained from DSMZ (Germany) and cultivated in suspension according to recommendations of the manufacturer. These cells were grown to $(0.5\text{--}1.5) \times 10^6$ cells/mL and diluted as required.

Determination of the effect of drugs on viability of selected human cancer cell lines

After the cultivation, A2780 and BL-2 cells the cells were resuspended in the RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS. This suspension was pipetted as 100 μ L/well suspension in a 96-well microtiter plate to the final number of 25.000 cells/100 μ L for adherent cells and 50.000 cells/100 μ L for suspension cells. Adherent cells were pipetted one day before for the attachment and kept left at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) overnight. Next, the stock solutions of drugs dissolved in DMSO at 5

mM, 2.5 mM, 1 mM, 0.5 mM and 0.1 mM were added to the wells giving a final concentration of 50 μ M, 25 μ M, 10 μ M, 5 μ M and 1 μ M and incubated for 48h. Pure DMSO was used as blank, ferrocene and iron hydroxyquinoline ($\text{Fe}(\text{8HQ})_2$) were used as negative and positive controls, respectively. After incubation for 48 h, 20 μ L/well of 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) solution (5 mg/mL in DPBS) was added. After another 3 h incubation under the same conditions, the cells were treated with 90 μ L/well sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, 10% solution in 0.01 M aqueous HCl) and incubated overnight. The next day, the intensity of absorbance at 590 nm was measured and the absorbance at 690 nm was taken as a baseline value in the plate reader (Varioskan Lux Plate Reader, Thermo Fischer, Germany). These data were used to calculate the relative number of viable cells and half-inhibitory-concentration (IC_{50}) of drugs (Table 1, main text).

Effects of drugs on viability of selected human cancer cell lines in the presence of ROS scavenger N-acetylcystein

A2780 cells were seeded in 96 well plate at the concentration of 250 cells/ μ L (100 μ L per well) one day before the experiment in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin and the plate was left at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO_2 (5%) overnight. On the next day, the medium was replaced with a fresh one and the cells were preincubated with N-acetylcysteine (NAC, either 1 or 2 mM in H_2O) for 1h. Then the drugs and controls (20 μ M) were added and further incubated for 24h. The supernatant was collected, the cells re-suspended in DPBS (100 μ L) and added back to the collected supernatant. The cells were trypsinated (0.25 % tripsim, 50 μ L, 5 min, 22 °C). The cell suspension (100 μ L) was mixed with the PI solution (propidium iodide (PI, 330 ng) per 1 mL buffer (conc. 1X), 100 μ L). The obtained mixture was incubated for 20 min at 22 °C in the dark and the fluorescence was measured with CytoFlex flow cytometer (Beckman Coulter, Inc): $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 664 \text{ nm}$. The data were analyzed using CytExpert software. The cells negative for propidium iodide (PI-) were considered viable and the cells positive for PI (PI+) were considered necrotic (Figure 3B, main text).

Accumulation of selected drugs and controls in A2780 cells

A2780 cells (6×10^6 cells/ μL) were seeded in T175 flasks (Greiner, Germany) in RPMI 1640 medium containing 10% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin and incubated for 3 days at 37°C in the chamber filled with 5% CO_2 . Next, the cells were washed with DPBS and a fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium (40 mL, 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, 1% penicillin/streptomycin) was added. The drugs dissolved in DMSO were added into the bottles at final concentration of $10 \mu\text{M}$ (final DMSO concentration: 1 %, v/v) and the cells were further incubated at either 37°C or 4°C for 4h. Next, the cells were washed (2x10 mL DPBS) and trypsinated. After the cells were centrifuged (5 min, 1000 rpm), the cell pellet was mixed with concentrated HNO_3 (100 μL) in an Eppendorf Thermomixer for 10 min at 95°C . After cooling down, water (900 μL) was added and the suspension was centrifuged. The supernatant was analyzed by atomic emission spectrometry (AES): detection of Fe and Zn. Zn amount was used as an internal reference (Figure 3B). Standard solutions for the AES were from Agilent or/and Bernd Kraft.

Determination of effects of drugs on the level of reactive oxygen species in cells

Total ROS (tROS) assay using 5(6)-chloromethyl-2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (CM-DCFH-DA) as a probe: A2780 cells were seeded in a 96 well plate at the concentration of 250 cells/ μL (total volume 100 μL per well) one day before the experiment in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. The plate was left at 37°C in the chamber filled with CO_2 (5%) overnight. On the next day, the cells were washed (2x100 μL DPBS). CM-DCFH-DA (Thermo, stock solution 5 mM in DMSO) was diluted (1:1000; final concentration 5 μM) in the Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) and added to the wells with cells (100 μL) and incubated for 20 min in the incubator. Next, the cells were washed (2x100 μL DPBS) and fresh medium was added (100 μL /well). Drugs, dissolved in DMSO (the final concentration: 25 μM , final DMSO amount: 1 %, v/v), were added and incubated for 2h. Finally, the cells were washed (2x100 μL DPBS), trypsinated and the fluorescence intensity was measured by using CytoFLEX, Beckmann Coulter flow cytometer. Detection parameters: excitation at 488 nm; emission at 525 ± 40 nm (Table S7). The experiment was repeated at least three times (Figure 3C, main text).

mROS assay using MitoSOX™ as a probe: A2780 cells were seeded in a 96 well plate at the concentration of 250 cells/μL (total volume 100 μL per well) one day before the experiment in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. The plate was left at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) overnight. On the next day, the medium was replaced with the fresh one. Drugs, dissolved in DMSO (the final concentration: 25 μM, final DMSO amount: 1 %, v/v), were added, incubated for 2h or 4h. Next, the cells were washed (2x100 μL DPBS). MitoSOX™ (Thermo Fisher Scientific, stock solution in DMSO, 5 mM) was diluted (1:1000) in the Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS), added to the wells with the cells (total volume 100 μL) and incubated for 20 min in the incubator (5 μM final concentration). The cells were washed (2x100 μL DPBS), trypsinated and resuspended in fresh medium (100μL/well). The fluorescence intensity was measured by using CytoFLEX, Beckmann Coulter: excitation at 488 nm: emission at 585 ± 42 nm. The data were analyzed using CytExpert software (Figure 3P, main text).

*Comparison of effects of **3d** on the level of mROS in representative human cancer cells (A2780) and human normal cells (SBLF9)*

A2780 and SBLF9 cells were seeded on a 35 mm imaging dish (μ-Dish 35 mm, high, ibidi GmbH, Germany) at a cell density of 80 cells/μL and 40 cells/μL, respectively, one day before the experiment in the corresponding medium (500 μL; A2780 - RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin; SBLF9 - F-12 Medium supplemented with 15 % fetal bovine serum, 2 % non-essential amino acids and 1 % penicillin/streptomycin). Next day, drug **3d** in fresh medium (2,5 mM stock solution, 25 μM final concentration in 2 mL) was added and incubated for 2 h in the incubator. Then the cells were washed with PBS (2 x 2 mL) and Hoechst 33342 (1 mg/mL in DMSO) and MitoSOX™ (5 μM in DMSO) in HBSS (1 mL) were added and incubated for 20 min in the incubator. Next, the cells were washed, and fresh medium (2 mL) was added. The images were taken with a Zeiss Axio Vert.A1 with objective: 40x/1.30 Oil DIC. A filter set for detection of MitoSOX™: λ_{ex}: 538-562 nm; λ_{em}: 570-640 nm. A filter set for detection of Hoechst 33342: λ_{ex} = 365 nm; λ_{em} = 395-495 nm (Figure 3D-O, main text).

Effects of drugs on mitochondrial membrane potential of A2780 cells

A2780 cells were seeded in a 96 well plate at the concentration of 250 cells/ μL (total volume 100 μL per well) one day before the experiment in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. The plate was left at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) overnight. On the next day, the medium was replaced with the fresh one. Drugs dissolved in DMSO were added (the final concentration: 25 μM , final DMSO amount: 1 %, v/v) and incubated for 2h or 4h. Next, the cells were washed (2x100 μL DPBS). R123 (Sigma Aldrich, stock solution 1 g/L in DMSO) was diluted (1:1000) in the Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) and added to the wells (100 μL) and incubated for 20 min in the incubator (100 $\mu\text{g/L}$ final concentration). Next, the cells were washed (2x100 μL DPBS), trypsinated and resuspended in fresh medium (100 $\mu\text{L/well}$). The fluorescence intensity was measured by using CytoFLEX, Beckmann Coulter: excitation 488 nm, emission 525 \pm 40 nm. The data were analyzed using CytExpert software (Figure 4A, main text).

Effects of drugs on lysosomes of A2780 cells

A2780 cells were seeded in a 24 well plate at the concentration of 200 cells/ μL (total volume 500 μL per well) one day before the experiment in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. The plate was left at 37 °C in the chamber filled with CO₂ (5%) overnight. On the next day, the medium was replaced with the fresh one. Drugs (the final concentration of 25 μM) were added and incubated for 1h, 2h and 4h. Next, the cells were washed (2x500 μL DPBS). Acridine Orange (AO, Sigma Aldrich, stock solution 40 mg/L in DMSO) was diluted (1:1000) in the Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS), added to the wells (500 μL) and incubated for 20 min in the incubator (final concentration: 40 $\mu\text{g/L}$). Next, the cells were washed (2x500 μL DPBS), trypsinated and resuspended in fresh medium (200 $\mu\text{L/well}$). The fluorescence intensity was measured by using Guava Easy Cyte Flow Cytometry, Millipore. Detection parameters: excitation at 488 nm; emission at 695 \pm 50 nm. The data were analyzed using guavaSoft 2.7 software (Figure 4B, main text).

*Monitoring the activation of fluorogenic derivative **6d** and **7d** in A2780 cells by using fluorescence microscopy*

A2780 cells in 2000 μL RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin were seeded on a 35 mm imaging dish (μ -Dish 35 mm, high, ibidi GmbH, Germany) at a cell density of 80 cells/ μL one day before the experiment. On the next day, the cells were washed with DPBS (2 x 2 mL). A fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium (2 mL) was added. **6d** or **7d** in DMSO (stock solution 2.5 mM, final concentration 25 μM) were added and incubated in the incubator at 37 °C containing 5% CO_2 for 2 h. The cells were washed with DPBS (2 x 2 mL) and the fresh medium (2 mL) was added. The cells were further incubated with H_2O_2 (stock solution 10 M, final concentration: 10 mM) for 1 h. The fluorescence images were taken with a Zeiss Axio Vert.A1 with objective 40x/1.30 Oil DIC and the following filter set: $\lambda_{\text{ex}}= 335\text{-}383$, $\lambda_{\text{em}}= 420\text{-}470$ nm (Figure 6, main text).

*Monitoring the activation of fluorogenic derivatives **6a**, **6d** and **7d** in A2780 and BL-2 cells by using flow cytometry*

A2780 cells in RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin were seeded in 96 well plate at concentration of 250 cells/ μL (100 μL per well) one day before the experiment. On the next day, the medium was replaced with the fresh portion of RPMI 1640 medium (100 μL). **6a** (25 μM), **6d** (25 μM) or **7d** (1 μM) were dissolved in DMSO and pipetted into cells at different final concentrations (the final DMSO concentration was kept at 1 %, v/v) and incubated for 2 and 4. Next, the cells were trypsinated and the fluorescence intensity ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}= 405$, $\lambda_{\text{em}}= 405\text{-}495$ nm) was measured by using CytoFLEX flow cytometer, Beckmann Coulter. The data were analyzed using CytExpert software (Figure 6D, E, main text).

In vivo experiments

Ethics

Studies involving animals, including housing and care, method of euthanasia, and experimental protocols were approved by the Ethical committee of Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical University, protocols 20200525/4; 20180226/2. All experiments

were designed to comply with principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement).

Mice

Black C57/BL6N mice were bred at the animal house of Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical University (Lviv, Ukraine). The animals were kept in clean environment, with water and food available ad libitum. Totally 50 animals were used in study.

NK/Ly tumor

NK/Ly lymphoma were obtained from established cell lines, maintained in the animal house of Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical University (Lviv, Ukraine) by repetitive inoculation of NK/Ly cell grown in ascites of black C57/BL6N mice and were continuously re-transplanted in ascitic form by the intra-abdominal (growth as ascites) of aliquots of ascites containing 1 million of NK/Ly cells into C57/BL6N mice.

For tumor inoculation 1 million of NK/Ly cells were suspended in 0.9% NaCl solution and were injected subcutaneously at the base of the leg of C57/BL6N mice at day 0 of the experiment. Upon tumor inoculation mice were weighted before and every next day during the experiment. The place of injection was monitored every second day for the conversion of formed granuloma-like formation into growing tumors, the later was usually observed after day 13. Tumor width, length and depth was measured with caliper. If the size of granulomatous mass at the place of injection was not increasing during 3 successive measurements at days 13, 15 and 17 the inoculation was considered not successful and mouse was excluded from the experiment.

For treatment of animals 60-80 μ L of solution of drug in cremophor/EtOH/saline (1/1/4, w/w/w) were injected intraperitoneal from the site of abdomen opposite to the site of the tumor inoculation. The compound was injected at mg/kg of mouse weigh; amount of injected compound was corrected for mice weight (usually between 25-35 g). At day 34, when the tumor weigh in the untreated group was approaching 15% of initial animal weigh, all animals were sacrificed, tumors were removed, weighted and fixed.

Experiments were repeated in duplicates for groups **3a** and **3d**; in each case the group of sibling male mice was splitted equally between compared groups. As a control the

carrier cremophor/EtOH/saline (1/1/4, w/w/w) solution was used. For this control group additional triplicate repeat was performed.

After 24 h fixation in PFA, the tumors were photographed to compare their sizes (Figure S2), then fixing solution was changed for a fresh one, after 24 h the tumors were cut along the long or biggest axis into halves, embedded in paraffin and serial sections of 7 μm were prepared, de-paraffinized, stained with H&E and embedded. Microscopy was performed with an Olympus BX51 fluorescent microscope (Olympus, Tokio, Japan) equipped with 40x 0.75 and 60x 0.9NA water immersion objectives as described elsewhere.^[S8] Histological evaluation was made independently by 2 qualified pathologists.

Figure **S2**. Photos of tumors at the end of experiment. The proportions of animals with regressing tumors are indicated with green color in the circular diagrams. The proportions of animals with progressing tumors are indicated with orange color.

Synthetic protocols and characterization of new drugs

Synthesis of **1c**

1e (200 mg, 527 μmol , **1e** synthesis is described below) was dissolved in anhydrous dichloromethane (DCM, 5 mL) at $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under N_2 atmosphere and 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC, 101 mg, 527 μmol), 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine (DMAP, 129 mg, 1.05 mmol) and dimethylamine hydrochloride (86 mg, 1.05 mmol) were added. The reaction mixture was warmed up to $22\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred for 18h. It was then quenched with water and extracted with DCM (3x25 mL), dried over Na_2SO_4 and the solvent was removed under vacuum. The crude product was purified via column chromatography (DCM:MeOH, 15:1, v/v) and the product was obtained as orange solid (175 mg, 82%). Thin layer chromatography (TLC, SiO_2 , eluent DCM:MeOH, 15:1, v:v) $R_f = 0.38$. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (at $70\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 500 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 8.74 (s, 1H), 7.46 (d, $J = 8.5\text{ Hz}$, 2H), 7.42 (d, 2H), 5.16 (s, 2H), 4.47 (s, 2H), 4.09 (s, 5H), 3.93 (t, $J = 1.9\text{ Hz}$, 2H), 2.94 (s, 6H). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ HR-MS (ESI+), m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{FeN}_2\text{O}_3$ 406.0974, found 406.0973. C, H, N analysis: calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{FeN}_2\text{O}_3$ (%) – C 62.09, H 5.46, N 6.90, found – C 61.52, H 5.49, N 6.82.

Synthesis of **1d**

Ferrocenyl azide (7 g, 27.45 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous toluene (100 mL) and heated up to $105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. (4-fluorophenyl)methanol (3.88 mL, 35.68 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for further 3 h at $105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. After it was stirred for further 18h at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the solvent was removed, and crude product was purified via column

chromatography (DCM:acetone, 99:1, v:v). The product was obtained as orange solid (8.37 g, 23.70 mmol, 86%). TLC (SiO₂, eluent DCM:Acetone, 99:1, v:v) R_f = 0.4. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.95 (s, 1H), 7.46 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 5.5 Hz, 2H), 7.27 – 7.18 (m, 2H), 5.09 (s, 2H), 4.46 (s, 2H), 4.08 (s, 5H), 3.92 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO) δ 163.00, 160.58, 153.53, 133.17, 133.14, 130.28, 130.20, 115.31, 115.10, 96.53, 68.69, 64.80, 63.60, 59.96, 39.52. HRMS (ESI+), *m/z*: calculated for C₁₈H₁₆FFeNO₂ 353.0509, found 353.0501. C, H, N analysis: calculated for C₁₈H₁₆FFeNO₂ (%) – C 61.22, H 4.57, N 3.97; found – C 61.30, H 4.71, N 4.01.

Synthesis of 1e

Ferrocenoyl azide (5 g, 19.60 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous toluene (80 mL) and heated up to 105 °C. 4-(hydroxymethyl)benzoic acid (2.98 g, 19.60 mmol) was added and stirred for further 2 h at 105 °C. After it was stirred for further 18 h at 25 °C, the precipitated product was separated by centrifugation (2500 rpm, 5 min). It was further washed with cold isopropanol (4x10mL) and dried under vacuum. The product was obtained as pale yellow-brownish solid (6.39 g, 18.85 mmol, 86%). TLC (SiO₂, eluent DCM:MeOH, 95:5, v:v) R_f = 0.60. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 12.99 (s, 1H), 9.04 (s, 1H), 7.96 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.50 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 5.18 (s, 2H), 4.47 (s, 2H), 4.09 (s, 5H), 3.93 (t, *J* = 1.9 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 167.06, 153.43, 141.99, 130.24, 129.43, 127.43, 96.51, 68.72, 64.83, 63.62, 59.97. HRMS (ESI+), *m/z*: calculated for C₁₉H₁₇FeNO₄ 379.0502, found 379.0486. C, H, N analysis: calculated for C₁₉H₁₇FeNO₄ (%) – C 60.18, H 4.52, N 3.69, found – C 60.13, H 4.67, N 3.67.

Synthesis of 2c

1c (585 mg, 1.44 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 8 mL) under N_2 atmosphere and Cs_2CO_3 (1.41 g, 4.32 mmol), tetrabutylammonium iodide (TBAI, 1.59 g, 4.32 mmol) and propargyl chloride (312 μL , 4.32 mmol) were added to the solution. After stirring for 18 h at 22 °C, insoluble Cs_2CO_3 was filtered, and the solvent was partially removed in vacuum. The product was precipitated with the addition of water and centrifuged (2500 rpm, 3 min). The solid was further washed with water. The product was obtained as highly dense orange oil (467 mg, 1.05 mmol, 73%). TLC (SiO_2 , eluent DCM:Acetone, 90:10, v:v) $R_f = 0.46$. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 7.49 – 7.40 (m, 4H), 5.22 (s, 2H), 4.52 (s, 2H), 4.48 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 2H), 4.18 (s, 5H), 4.06 (t, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 2H), 3.35 (s, 1H), 2.93 (d, $J = 32.7$ Hz, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 169.75, 153.39, 137.52, 136.07, 127.42, 127.06, 80.61, 74.69, 68.91, 66.62, 64.33, 62.24, 34.72. HRMS (ESI+), m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{FeN}_2\text{O}_3$ 444.1131, found 444.1090. C, H, N analysis: calculated for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{BFeN}_2\text{O}_3$ (%) – C 64.88, H 5.44, N 6.31, found – C 64.66, H 5.47, N 6.18.

Synthesis of **2d**

1d (3.00 g, 8.49 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous DMF (30 mL) and Cs_2CO_3 (8.30 g, 25.48 mmol), TBAI (9.39 g, 25.48 mmol) and propargyl chloride (1.84 mL, 25.48 mmol) were added to the solution. After stirring for 18 h at 25 °C, insoluble Cs_2CO_3 was filtered, and the solvent was removed in vacuum. The crude product was purified via column chromatography (hexane:acetone, 4:1, v:v). The product was obtained as orange solid (2.85 mg, 7.28 mmol, 86%). TLC (SiO_2 , eluent hexane:acetone, 4:1, v:v) $R_f = 0.47$. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 7.48 (dd, $J = 8.4, 5.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.25 – 7.18 (m, 2H), 5.15 (s, 2H), 4.50 (s, 2H), 4.46 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 2H), 4.18 (s, 5H), 4.05 (t, $J =$

2.0 Hz, 2H), 3.32 (s, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO) δ 163.03, 160.61, 153.36, 132.57, 132.54, 130.18, 130.14, 115.32, 115.11, 99.93, 80.58, 74.61, 68.88, 66.37, 64.29, 62.19, 39.52 HRMS (ESI+), m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{FFeNO}_2$ 391.0666, found 391.0664. C, H, N analysis: calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{FFeNO}_2$ (%) – C 64.47, H 4.64, N 3.58, found – C 64.40, H 4.65, N 3.64.

Synthesis of 3d

1d (600 mg, 1.70 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous DMF (10 mL) under nitrogen atmosphere. Then Cs_2CO_3 (2.77 g, 8.49 mmol) and TBAI (1.25 g, 3.40 mmol) were added to the solution. After stirring for 1 h at 23 °C, 1-(3-(chloromethyl)benzyl)piperidine hydrochloride^[S3] (884.10 mg, 3.40 mmol) was added. The mixture was stirred for 18 h at 23 °C. Then, Cs_2CO_3 was filtered, and the solvent was removed in vacuum. The product was precipitated with the addition of water and centrifuged (2500 rpm, 3 min). The solid obtained was further washed with water. The crude product was purified by column chromatography, yielding an orange solid (320 mg, 1.7 mmol, 35%). TLC (SiO_2 , eluent DCM:Acetone, 7:3, v:v) R_f = 0.44. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ 7.45 – 7.12 (m, 8H), 5.15 (s, 2H), 4.88 (s, 2H), 4.37 (s, 2H), 4.07 (s, 5H), 3.99 (t, J = 2.0 Hz, 2H), 3.36 (s, 2H), 2.26 (s, 4H), 1.44 (t, J = 5.5 Hz, 4H), 1.37 (s, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ 164.53, 162.10, 155.43, 140.54, 139.75, 133.94, 131.17 (d, J = 9.6 Hz), 129.05, 128.17, 127.57, 125.77, 115.96 (d, J = 21.6 Hz), 102.51, 69.74, 67.19, 65.00, 64.21, 63.20, 55.19, 54.25, 26.82, 25.18. HRMS (ESI+), m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{33}\text{FFeN}_2\text{O}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ 541.1949, found 541.1909. C, H, N analysis: calculated for $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{45}\text{BFeN}_2\text{O}_4$ (%) – C 68.54, H 7.00 N 4.32. found – C 68.80, H 6.32, N 5.35.

Synthesis of intermediate S2

S1^[S9, S10] (600 mg, 1.80 mmol) and 4-fluorobenzyl alcohol (249 mg, 215 μL , 1.98 mmol) were dissolved under a nitrogen atmosphere in anhydrous toluene (36 mL) and heated to 105 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The reaction mixture was stirred for a further 2 h. Solvent was removed and the residue was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) to yield product **S2** as an orange foam (650 mg, 1.5 mmol, 83%). TLC (silica gel, eluent iso-hexane/acetone, 4/1, v/v, R_f = 0.30). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 8.03 (s, 1H), 7.65 – 7.37 (m, 2H), 7.29 – 7.01 (m, 2H), 5.13 (s, 2H), 4.63 (s, 2H), 4.45 – 4.27 (m, 2H), 4.19 – 4.06 (m, 2H), 4.05 – 3.90 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = 164.57, 162.15, 154.62, 134.29, 134.26, 131.19, 131.11, 116.07, 115.85, 99.57, 79.78, 71.65, 68.79, 67.10, 66.11, 62.67. ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, Acetone- d_6) δ = -115.90. HRMS (ESI): calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrFFeNO}_2$ ($[\text{M-e}]^+$): 430.9614; found m/z : 430.9614. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrFFeNO}_2$: C 50.04, H 3.50, N 3.24; found: C 50.17, H 3.55, N 3.49.

Synthesis of 3d_Br

S2 (150 mg, 0.35 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous DMF (1.7 mL) under a nitrogen atmosphere. Cesium carbonate (452 mg, 1.39 mmol), cesium iodide (89 mg, 0.35 mmol). After stirring for 0.5 h at rt, 1-(3-(chloromethyl)benzyl)piperidine hydrochloride (181 mg, 0.69 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred overnight. After filtration, DMF was removed from the yellow mixture by using rotary evaporator at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The

residue was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, iso-hexane/acetone, 6/1 to 3/1, v/v) to yield product as a brown oil (80 mg, 0.13 mmol, 37%). TLC (silica gel, eluent iso-hexane/acetone, 6/1, v/v, $R_f = 0.21$). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 7.42$ (s, 2H), 7.30 – 6.97 (m, 6H), 5.23 (s, 2H), 5.00 (s, 2H), 4.55 (s, 2H), 4.41 (s, 2H), 4.10 (s, 2H), 4.07 – 3.98 (m, 2H), 3.40 (s, 2H), 2.32 (s, 4H), 1.61 – 1.45 (m, 4H), 1.45 – 1.33 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = 164.55, 162.13, 155.16, 140.56, 139.37, 133.86, 133.83, 131.26, 131.22, 129.13, 128.25, 127.55, 125.73, 116.09, 115.87, 103.83, 79.35, 71.69, 69.06, 67.82, 67.33, 64.94, 64.13, 55.15, 53.60, 26.79, 25.16$. ^{19}F NMR (283 MHz, Acetone- d_6) $\delta = -115.61$. HRMS (ESI): calcd for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{32}\text{BrFFeN}_2\text{O}_2$ ($[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$): 619.1053; found m/z : 619.1061. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrFFeNO}_2$: C 60.12, H 5.21, N 4.52; found: C 60.36, H 5.49, N 4.65.

Synthesis of **6a**

In 50 mL round bottom flask, **2a** (240 mg, 480.77 μmol) was dissolved in anhydrous DCM (3.2 mL) and anhydrous acetonitrile (21 mL) under N_2 atmosphere. DIPEA (418 μL , 2.40 mmol) and 3-azido-7-hydroxycoumarin (97.67 mg, 480.77 μmol) was added. In another vial, CuI (9.16 mg, 48.08 μmol) and tris(benzyltriazolylmethyl)amine (TBTA, 25.51 mg, 48.08 μmol) was dissolved in 4 mL anhydrous acetonitrile and added into the reaction mixture. After it was stirred 18h at 25°C, the solvent was removed and crude product was purified via column chromatography (DCM:Aceton, 9:1, v/v). The product was obtained as yellow solid (231 mg, 328.89 μmol , 68%). TLC (SiO_2 , eluent DCM:MeOH, 9:1, v:v) $R_f = 0.63$ ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 10.90 (s, 1H), 8.59 (s, 1H), 8.43 (s, 1H), 7.75 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.65 (d, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.39 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 6.91 (dd, $J = 8.6, 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.85 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 5.20 (s, 2H), 5.04 (s, 2H), 4.59 (s, 2H), 4.14 (s, 5H), 4.04 (t, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 2H), 1.27 (s, 12H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 162.46, 156.25, 154.63, 144.34, 139.60, 136.14, 134.49, 130.93, 127.14, 124.14, 119.27, 114.25, 110.29, 102.14, 83.64, 68.79, 66.86, 64.23, 24.62. HR-MS

(ESI+), m/z : calculated for $C_{36}H_{35}BFeN_4O_7$ 702.1950, found 702.1964. C, H, N analysis: calculated for $C_{36}H_{35}BFeN_4O_7$ (%) – C 61.56, H 5.02, N 7.98. found – C 61.46, H 5.04, N 8.04.

Synthesis of 6d

In 100 mL round bottom flask, **2d** (150 mg, 383.41 μ mol) was dissolved in anhydrous DCM (2.3 mL) and anhydrous acetonitrile (21 mL) under N_2 atmosphere. DIPEA (334 μ L, 1.92 mmol) and 3-azido-7-hydroxycoumarin (77.89 mg, 383.41 μ mol) was added. In another vial, CuI (7.30 mg, 38.34 μ mol) and TBTA (20.35 mg, 38.34 μ mol) was dissolved in 3 mL anhydrous acetonitrile and added into the reaction mixture. After it was stirred 18h at 25°C, the solvent was removed and crude product was purified via column chromatography (DCM:MeOH, 99:1 \rightarrow 90:10, v/v). the product was obtained as orange solid (161 mg, 270.87 μ mol, 71%). TLC (SiO_2 , eluent DCM:MeOH, 9:1, v:v) R_f = 0.58. 1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 8.58 (s, 1H), 8.39 (s, 1H), 7.74 (d, J = 8.7 Hz, 1H), 7.45 (t, J = 7.0 Hz, 2H), 7.18 (t, J = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 6.89 (dd, J = 8.5, 2.3 Hz, 1H), 6.84 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 5.16 (s, 2H), 5.02 (s, 2H), 4.58 (s, 2H), 4.13 (s, 5H), 4.04 (t, J = 2.0 Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (151 MHz, DMSO) δ 162.64, 162.44, 161.02, 156.28, 154.64, 144.35, 136.16, 132.58, 132.56, 130.95, 130.33, 124.15, 119.31, 115.33, 115.19, 114.27, 110.33, 102.15, 100.53, 68.80, 66.37, 64.23, 62.32, 54.91, 39.52. HR-MS (ESI+), m/z : calculated for $C_{30}H_{23}FFeN_4O_5$ 594.0997, found 594.0988. C, H, N analysis: calculated for $C_{30}H_{23}FFeN_4O_5$ (%) – C 60.62, H 3.90, N 9.43. found – C 59.81, H 3.88, N 9.23.

Synthesis of 7d

Intermediate **S3** (50.0 mg, 88 μ mol) was dissolved in DCM (1 mL) and diluted with acetonitrile (10 mL). Then DIPEA (75 mg, 44 μ mol) and 3-azido-7-hydroxycoumarin (18 mg, 88 μ mol) were added. In a separate vial CuI (1.71 mg, 8.8 μ mol) and TBTA (4.77 mg, 8.8 μ mol) were dissolved in acetonitrile (1 mL) by ultrasonication. Then the catalyst was added to the reaction mixture and the reaction was stirred for 80 minutes at 22 °C. After that the reaction mixture was washed with water (100 mL), extracted with EtOAc (3 x 70 mL) and the combined organic phases were dried over MgSO₄. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, petroleum ether/ethylacetate 7:3, v/v) to give a yellow solid. TLC (SiO₂, eluent DCM/MeOH, 10/1, v/v). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) 10.94 (s, 1H), 8.98 (s, 1H), 8.67 (s, 1H), 7.80-7.75 (m, 3H), 7.37-7.14 (m, 6H), 6.94-6.88 (m, 2H), 5.18 (s, 2H), 4.96 (s, 2H), 4.43 (s, 2H), 4.10 (s, 5H), 4.02 (s, 2H), 3.46 (s, 2H), 2.33 (s, 4H), 1.48-1.38 (m, 8H), 1.24 (s, 2H). ¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ (ppm) 163.47, 163.12, 161.20, 161.05, 156.82, 146.83, 139.95, 137.06, 133.17, 133.14, 131.58, 130.59, 126.97, 125.06, 122.56, 119.69, 115.78, 115.56, 110.80, 101.63, 69.32, 66.71, 64.66, 62.98, 62.70, 54.27, 53.52, 41.34, 26.81, 25.84, 24.31, 10.38. HR-MS (ESI+), *m/z*: calculated for C₄₂H₃₈FFeN₅O₅ [M-e]⁺ 768.2278, found 767.2279.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ and HRMS spectra of reported intermediates and drugs

Figure S3. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of **1c** in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S4. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum of **1c** in DMSO-d_6 .

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Figure S5. High resolution of ESI-TOF mass spectrum of **1c**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot - theoretical spectrum.

Figure S6. ¹H-NMR spectrum of **1d** in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S7. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of **1d** in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S8. High resolution ESI-TOF mass spectrum of **1d**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S9. ¹H-NMR spectrum of **1e** in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S10. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of **1e** in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S11. High resolution of ESI-TOF mass spectrum of **1e**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot - theoretical spectrum.

Figure S13. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of **2c** in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

Figure S14. High resolution of ESI-TOF mass spectrum of **2c**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot - theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S15**. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of **2d** in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure **S16**. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum of **2d** in DMSO-d_6 . Peak “m” is overlapping with DMSO peak.

Figure **S17**. High resolution of ESI-TOF mass spectrum of **2d**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot - theoretical spectrum.

Figure **S18**. ¹H-NMR spectrum of **3d** in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S19. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of **3d** in Acetone-d₆.

Figure S20. High resolution of ESI-TOF mass spectrum of **3d**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot - theoretical spectrum.

4xu014326
HX028-B1609-conc

Figure S21. ¹H-NMR spectrum of drug S2 in Acetone-d₆.

Figure S21. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of drug S2 in Acetone-d₆.

4xu024077
HX066-B1501-conc

Figure S24. ¹H-NMR spectrum of drug 3d_Br in Acetone-d₆.

Figure S25. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of drug 3d_Br in Acetone-d₆.

3xu012818
HX066-B1501-conc

Figure S26. ¹⁹F-NMR spectrum of drug 3d_Br in Acetone-d₆.

Figure S27. High resolution ESI mass spectrum of drug 3d_Br: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S28. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of **6a** in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S29. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum of **6a** in DMSO-d_6 .

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Figure S30. ESI mass spectrum of prodrug **6a**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

Figure S31. ¹H-NMR spectrum of **6d** in DMSO-*d*₆.

Figure S32. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of **6d** in DMSO-*d*₆.

Figure S33. ESI mass spectrum of prodrug **6d**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum

Figure S34. ¹H-NMR spectrum of 7d in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S35. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of 7d in DMSO-d₆.

Display Report

Analysis Info		Acquisition Date		12/14/2020 2:22:30 PM	
Analysis Name	D:\Data\2020\Mokhir-2020\Thomas-FcVAN--25- d	Operator	MD		
Method	tune_pos_low.m	Instrument	micrOTOF	213750.10364	
Sample Name	Low concentration Tunemix				
Comment	MeOH CH ₂ Cl ₂				

Acquisition Parameter					
Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Set Nebulizer	0.3 Bar
Focus	Active			Set Dry Heater	200 °C
Scan Begin	50 m/z	Set Capillary	4000 V	Set Dry Gas	3.0 l/min
Scan End	1550 m/z	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V	Set Divert Valve	Waste

Bruker Compass DataAnalysis 4.2

printed: 12/14/2020 2:25:48 PM

by: MD

1 of 1

Figure S36. ESI mass spectrum of prodrug **7d**: upper plot – experimental spectrum; bottom plot – theoretical spectrum.

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Hybrids of a 9-anthracenyl moiety and fluorescein as chemodosimeters for the detection of singlet oxygen in live cells†

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Singlet oxygen (¹O₂) plays an important role in human innate immune response, plant physiology and anticancer photodynamic therapy (PDT). Therefore, its monitoring by convenient and sensitive methods (e.g. by detecting a fluorescence signal) by using non-toxic reagents would be advantageous. Known fluorogenic ¹O₂-chemodosimeters can potentially consume reducing agents in cells leading to the generation of toxic side products that limit their applications. In this paper we report on a series of 9-anthracenyl-fluorescein hybrids, which do not require any reducing agents for their reaction with ¹O₂. The selected compound **8d** at a very low concentration of 100 nM is able to detect ¹O₂ in live human promyelocytic leukemia HL-60 cells with over 35-fold fluorescence signal enhancement within only 20 min assay time. This chemodosimeter is not toxic to HL-60 cells at concentrations ≤1 μM (higher concentrations were not tested) even at long incubation times ≤48 h.

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Introduction

Singlet oxygen (¹O₂) is an excited state of triplet oxygen (³O₂). This compound can be produced either *via* photosensitizer-mediated¹ or thermal chemical reaction *e.g.* between ClO[−] and H₂O₂.² Though ¹O₂ is highly reactive, it is also formed in nature. In particular, the photosensitized synthesis takes place in plants (a natural pigment chlorophyll acts as a photosensitizer³) and human skin,¹ whereas the thermal one – in neutrophils thereby mediating the killing of bacteria.⁴ This is one of the key chemical reactions responsible for the normal function of the innate immune system in humans. Furthermore, ¹O₂ is a cytotoxic mediator that is photochemically generated during the photodynamic therapy (PDT) of cancer diseases.⁵ Therefore, the detection of ¹O₂ directly in live cells is important for understanding its biological function and has implications in medicine, *e.g.* in controlling of PDT efficacy as well as diagnosis of neutrophil pathologies.

Excellent chemiluminescent chemodosimeters suitable for the detection of ¹O₂ in live cells are known: *e.g.* commercially available *trans*-1-(2'-methoxyvinyl)pyrene⁶ and recently reported SOCL-CPP.⁷ Though a lot of effort was invested in the search for suitable fluorogenic chemodosimeters, the best known systems are still not ideal for practical applications. For example, Singlet Oxygen Sensor Green (SOSG, Thermo Fischer, Scheme 1A) was the first commercially available fluorogenic reagent for ¹O₂ detection. Supposedly, it is a hybrid system containing a fluorescein dye covalently linked to a 9-methylanthracen-10-yl fragment (compound **1**, where Rⁱ = R^{iv} = R^v = H, Rⁱⁱ = CH₃, Rⁱⁱⁱ = 2'-substituted fluorescein residue, Scheme 1). SOSG suffers from a relatively high residual fluorescence in the absence of ¹O₂ (see *e.g.* Fig. 1A) that causes the undesirable background signal thereby reducing sensitivity in the detection of ¹O₂. Furthermore, SOSG can itself catalyse ¹O₂ formation and induce its own decomposition.⁸ Finally, for the related compound HOCD-IR-780 (Scheme 1A) it is known that the endoperoxide intermediate initially formed in the reaction with ¹O₂ is converted to the di-ol derivative (Scheme 1A).⁹ The latter redox process consumes an endogenous reducing agent (Red) that might lead to the generation of toxic radicals and disturbance of redox balance in live cells. For other previously reported fluorogenic chemodosimeters, *e.g.* Aarhus sensor green¹⁰ (Scheme 1A), Si-DMA (now commercially available, *e.g.* from Merck),¹¹ compound **2** developed by our group¹² (Scheme 1B), and **3**¹³ (Scheme 1B) as well as SOSG, similar redox processes are expected to occur in the presence of ¹O₂.

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Scheme 1 (A, B) Known probes (1–3) for the detection of singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) and mechanisms of their reactions with $^1\text{O}_2$; toxic species/reactive chemical fragments released in these reactions are red coloured; sign “?” indicates unknown species, which should have been formed to account for the atom balance in the chemical equation of the shown reaction. (C) A structure of new $^1\text{O}_2$ -probe **4** and the mechanism of its reaction with $^1\text{O}_2$.

Fig. 1 (A) Fluorogenic response of newly prepared probes **4** and **8b–e** (each 2 μM) and known $^1\text{O}_2$ probe SOSG (Singlet Oxygen Sensor Green; Thermo Fischer, 2 μM) in the presence of photochemically generated $^1\text{O}_2$: F_0 – initial fluorescence intensity ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 495 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 515 \text{ nm}$); F_{60} – fluorescence intensity after 60 min of irradiation with red light in the presence of photosensitizer In(pyropheophorbide-a)chloride (0.5 μM) in phosphate/NaCl buffer (pH 7.4); (B) fluorogenic response (F_{60}/F_0) of newly prepared probes **4** and **8b–e** (each 2 μM) in the presence of different reactive oxygen species. (Each experimental conditions are described in the “Experimental” section of the paper.

leading to the formation of toxic species as outlined in Scheme 1A and B; toxic products/moieties are labelled with red colour.

The goal of this work was to develop chemodosimeters with low background fluorescence in the absence of $^1\text{O}_2$ and strong $^1\text{O}_2$ -mediated fluorescence increase. We wanted to achieve that the endoperoxide intermediate formed in the latter reaction is quickly converted to stable products without external reducing agents. That would solve the problem of undesired redox processes induced by the known $^1\text{O}_2$ -chemodosimeters in live cells.

Results and discussion

A structure of $^1\text{O}_2$ -chemodosimeter **4** reported in this paper is shown in Scheme 1C. In this molecule a fluorescein dye is masked by 3'-*O*-alkyl and 6'-*O*-aryl groups. The 3'-*O*-alkyl contains a carboxylic group to provide for the solubility of the probe in neutral aqueous solution. Another group is an $^1\text{O}_2^-$ reactive 9-anthracenyl fragment. Chemodosimeter **4** will react with $^1\text{O}_2$ with the formation of endoperoxide **4** $_{\text{O}_2}$, which is expected to decompose cleanly to 9,10-anthraquinone AQ and strongly fluorescent **5**. Electrons from a C(10)–H bond will be used in this reaction step as intramolecular reductants. Thus, no external electrons will be required to form the stable final products. These considerations are based on our previous experience with 9-anthracenyl derivatives of RNAs and DNAs.^{14–21}

We prepared compound **4** as outlined in Scheme 2. In particular, fluorescein was first 3'-*O*-alkylated with 2-bromo-2-methylpropionate to obtain derivative **6** (yield 15%). Further alkylation of the second phenolic oxygen with 9-bromoanthracene in the presence of a catalyst $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/t\text{-BuXPhos}$ (1/1) (leading to **7a** with the yield of 12%), followed by hydrolysis of the methyl ester by LiOH furnished non-fluorescent com-

Scheme 2 Synthesis of $^1\text{O}_2$ probes **4** and **8b–8e**: (a) *t*-BuOK, methyl 2-bromo-2-methylpropionate; (b) R-Hal, where Hal = Br or Cl, further details are described in “Synthetic procedures” section; (c) LiOH, THF, water.

pound **4** with the overall yield of 1.4% over three steps. The low yield is caused by a low conversion of the starting materials in the first and second steps. The final step (hydrolysis) occurs quantitatively according to the chromatographic analysis, whereas the isolated yield was 78%.

Next, we studied the reaction of **4** with $^1\text{O}_2$ by using electro-spray mass spectrometry (ESI-MS). Compound **4** (final concentration: 30 μM) was dissolved in CH_3CN and H_2O_2 was added: 9/1 (v/v), final concentration of H_2O_2 – 30 mM. After incubation for 1 h at 22 $^\circ\text{C}$ the ESI mass spectra of the resulting solution in both negative and positive modes were acquired. We detected in the spectra peaks corresponding to 9,10-anthraquinone (AQ, calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 209.0602, found m/z 209.0608, ESI $^+$) and compound **5** (calcd for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_7\text{O}_7$ $[\text{M} - \text{H}]^-$ 417.3935, found 417.3940, ESI $^-$). These results (formation of AQ in the reaction of probe **4** with $^1\text{O}_2$) were further corroborated with ^1H NMR spectroscopy (Fig. S25, ESI †). Moreover, in the fluorescence spectrum of a solution of **4** treated with H_2O_2 we observed the characteristic of compound **5** emission band centred at $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 515$ nm ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488$ nm). These data confirm the mechanism of the reaction of $^1\text{O}_2$ with compound **4** outlined in Scheme 1C.

To evaluate the performance of **4**, we compared the $^1\text{O}_2$ -mediated increase of fluorescence of this compound with that of commercially available chemodosimeter SOG (Fig. 1A). The fluorescence intensity ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 495$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 515$ nm) of a solution of **4** (2 μM) in phosphate/NaCl buffer (pH 7.4) was increased from 2.4 arbitrary units (a.u., F_0) to 26.3 a.u. (F_{60}) upon reaction with $^1\text{O}_2$, which was generated in the presence of the photosensitizer In(pyropheophorbide-a)chloride 11 (0.5 μM) upon irradiation with red light. This corresponds to an 11.2-fold fluorescence increase (F_{60}/F_0). In contrast, under the same conditions F_{60}/F_0 for SOG was found to be only 4.2-fold that is due to the rather high background fluorescence of the latter chemodosimeter ($F_{60} = 194.2$ a.u.). Importantly, we observed that the fluorogenic response of compound **4** is specific towards $^1\text{O}_2$ as compared to other reactive oxygen species including H_2O_2 ($F_{60}/F_0 = 1.7$), $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ ($F_{60}/F_0 = 1.1$), HO^\cdot ($F_{60}/F_0 = 1.4$) and control conditions ($h\nu =$ red light irradiation in the absence of the photosensitizer, $F_{60}/F_0 = 1.6$, Fig. 1B).

Furthermore, we explored the role of substituents in the 10th position of the anthracene moiety (replacement of $-\text{H}^{(10)}$ for $-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{NHAc}$ and $-\text{NH}_2$) and the type of linker between this moiety and a fluorophore (comparing the direct linkage to the fluorophore with that *via* a methylene bridge) in the reaction of **4** with $^1\text{O}_2$.

Since $^1\text{O}_2$ is an electron deficient molecule, we expected that the energies of HOMOs of the anthracene-containing chemodosimeters will correlate with their reactivity in the addition of $^1\text{O}_2$ (the first step in the reaction outlined in Scheme 1C). Therefore, we determined the energies of HOMOs of derivatives modelling **4** and its analogues **8b–8e**, where the fluorescein fragment was replaced with a phenyl group, by using the B3LYP hybrid density functional and the 6-31G** basis set (Fig. 2, experimental description is given in the ESI †). 9-Amino-10-phenyloxanthracene was used as a reference com-

Fig. 2 Relative HOMO energies of simple anthracene derivatives. These compounds are models of probes **4** and **8a–e**. 9-Amino-10-phenyloxanthracene was used as a reference compound (relative HOMO energy 0). This compound was found to be easily oxidized even in the presence of triplet oxygen.

pound. We observed that the reference compound was mostly electron rich, followed by the group of derivatives with similar HOMO energies (models of **8b**, **8d**, **4**, **8c**) and concluding with a substantially more electron deficient model of **8b**.

To validate these theoretical data, we prepared the corresponding derivatives **8b–8e** as outlined in Scheme 2 and Schemes S1, S2 in the ESI † . In particular, we found that 9-bromo-10-nitroanthracene is reactive enough to directly alkylate intermediate **6** in the presence of slight excess Cs_2CO_3 leading to **7b** with the moderate isolated yield of 57%. After the hydrolysis of **7b** by LiOH compound **8b** (replacement of $-\text{H}^{(10)}$ for $-\text{NO}_2$) was obtained with the yield of 51%. To reduce a nitro-group in **7b** we used $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. However, the product (the reference compound, where the nitro-group is converted to an amino-group) was found to be extremely unstable under aerobic conditions. This did not allow the isolation of this product in pure form. Therefore, we conducted the reduction of **7b** in the presence of acetic acid anhydride (Ac_2O) to trap the unstable intermediate as the *N*-acylated product, **7c**. Under the experimental conditions used in the synthesis of **4**, as described above, the ester group of **7c** was hydrolysed leading to compound **8c** (replacement of $-\text{H}^{(10)}$ for $-\text{NHAc}$). Compounds **7d** and **7e** were obtained by the alkylation of intermediate **6** with the corresponding 9-(chloromethoxy)anthracene and 2,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9-(chloromethoxy)anthracene. The latter two reagents were generated *in situ* from 9-(methylthiomethoxy)anthracene derivatives and sulfuryl chloride as described in the Experimental section. The following hydrolysis furnished the desired products **8d** and **8e**.

We found that, in agreement with the DFT calculations, derivative **8b** carrying the strongest electron-acceptor moiety $-\text{NO}_2$ reacts less efficiently with $^1\text{O}_2$ compared to other prepared compounds (Fig. 1B). Interestingly, the reactivities of **8e**, **8d**, **4**, and **8c** are substantially different from each other (**8e** > **8d** > **4** > **8c**), whereas according to the DFT calculation the addition of $^1\text{O}_2$ to all of these compounds would go on with similar efficacy (Fig. 3). This might indicate that both reaction

Fig. 3 (A) Monitoring the formation of $^1\text{O}_2$ in HL-60 cells loaded with In (pyropheophorbide-a)chloride (InPpa, 200 nM) upon irradiation with red (650 nm) light. **8d** (100 nM) was used as a probe (black bars). Cells loaded only with InPpa (striped bars) or only probe **8d** (grey bars) were used as controls; (B) effect of probe **8d** on the viability of HL-60 cells (incubation for 48 h). Similar effects were obtained for probe **4** (data not shown).

steps (addition of $^1\text{O}_2$ as well as AQ formation, Scheme 1C) contribute to the overall reaction rate. It could also be noted that linking of the anthracene moiety to the dye *via* a methylene bridge (**8d**, **8e**) is more favorable for the chemodosimeter reactivity than its direct linking (compare with the data for **4** and **8c**, Fig. 1B).

Based on the high reactivity with $^1\text{O}_2$ (Fig. 1B) and its moderate synthetic accessibility we selected chemodosimeters **4** and **8d** for further experiments. The goal was to confirm that the effects observed in cell free settings are transferrable to the cells. We selected human promyelocytic leukemia cells HL-60 for these experiments based on their accessibility in our laboratory and the possibility of convenient and quantitative monitoring of the intracellular fluorescence of these non-adherent cells by using flow cytometry (Fig. 3A). We observed that **8d** (100 nM) remains intact (non-fluorescent) in live HL-60 cells for the duration of at least 20 min. The same result was obtained for the cells loaded with both **8d** (100 nM) and photosensitizer In(pyropheophorbide-a)chloride (200 nM). However, when the latter cells were irradiated with red light, the conditions that are known to lead to the generation of $^1\text{O}_2$ in cells,^{14,15} the fluorescence of **8d** was dramatically increased (38.6-fold in 20 min) in a time dependent fashion (black bars in Fig. 3A).

It is important that **8d** is not toxic to HL-60 cells at concentrations of up to 1 μM (higher concentrations were not tested) even at incubation times up to 48 h (Fig. 3B). Probe **4** exhibited similar effects in the flow cytometry assay (data not shown).

Finally, we confirmed that probe **4** can also be used in combination with fluorescence microscopy for the detection of $^1\text{O}_2$ in adherent cancer cells: prostate cancer DU-145 cells we used as an example (Fig. S26, ESI[†]).

Experimental

General information

Unless otherwise specified, all reactions were carried out under an atmosphere of nitrogen using oven-dried glassware.

Commercially available chemicals were used without further purification. Anhydrous reagents: *o*-xylene, CH_2Cl_2 , *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), dioxane, trimethylamine (TEA), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), CHCl_3 as well as fluorescein, potassium *t*-butoxide (*t*-BuOK), methyl 2-bromo-2-methylpropionate, 9-nitroanthracene, 9-bromoanthracene, $\text{CH}_3\text{SCH}_2\text{Cl}$, sodium hydride (60% dispersion in mineral oil), bromine, $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$, 2-di-*tert*-butylphosphino-2',4',6'-triisopropylbiphenyl (*t*-BuXPhos), Cs_2CO_3 , SO_2Cl_2 , anthracene, *tert*-butyl chloride (*t*-BuCl), AlCl_3 , $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_6]$, glacial acetic acid (AcOH), Sn dust, xanthine oxidase (XO) and xanthine were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. CH_3NO_2 was purchased from Alfa Aesar and Singlet Oxygen Sensor Green (SOSG) from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on a Merck DF-Alufoilen (60F254, 0.2 mm pre-coated plates). Compounds on TLC plates were visualized by exposure to UV light. NMR spectra were acquired on a 300 MHz Bruker Avance spectrometer. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were referenced to the residual protonated solvent (^1H) or the solvent itself (^{13}C). All chemical shifts are reported in parts per million (ppm). For CDCl_3 , the shifts are referenced to 7.27 ppm for ^1H NMR spectroscopy and 77.0 ppm for ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy. For acetone- d_6 , the shifts are referenced to 2.05 ppm for ^1H NMR spectroscopy and 29.9 ppm for ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy. Abbreviations used in the description of resonances are: s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), quin (quintet), br (broad), m (multiplet), dd (doublet of doublets), and ddd (doublet of doublet of doublets). Coupling constants (*J*) are quoted to the nearest 0.1 Hz. ESI and APPI measurements were recorded on a micrOTOF II focus mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonik GmbH, Germany) in a positive and negative mode. Fluorescence spectra were acquired on an Agilent Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer by using fluorescence cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL. The fluorescence of live cells was quantified using a Guava easyCyte™ 6-2L flow cytometer (Merck Millipore). Channel FL1 was used to quantify the activation of probes **4** and **8d** ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 515\text{--}540 \text{ nm}$). Channel FL2 was used to quantify dead cells, which were loaded with propidium iodide (PI, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 488 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 570\text{--}606 \text{ nm}$). The data were processed using the inCyte™ software package (Merck Millipore).

Synthetic procedures

Compound 6. A suspension of fluorescein (26.6 g, 80 mmol) in DMF (500 mL) was prepared and *t*-BuOK (9 g, 80 mmol) was added. After the solution became clear, 2-bromo-2-methylpropionate (5.6 mL, 40 mmol) was added in one portion. The reaction mixture was stirred at 22 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 48 h. After that, the reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with EtOAc (3 \times 150 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with brine (50 mL), dried (MgSO_4), and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification of the residue by flash column chromatography (silica gel, elution gradient: from 30 : 1 $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{MeOH}$ (v/v) to 20 : 1 $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{MeOH}$, both solvent mixtures contained 0.5% TEA) gave compound **6** as a brown syrup (5.0 g,

11.6 mmol, 14.5%). $R_f = 0.29$ (silica gel, 20:1:1 CH₂Cl₂/MeOH/TEA, v/v/v); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.96–8.05 (m, 1H), 7.56–7.75 (m, 2H), 7.12–7.19 (m, 1H), 6.80–6.73 (m, 1H), 6.70–6.61 (m, 2H), 6.60–6.54 (m, 2H), 6.51 (dd, $J = 9.0, 2.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 1.64 (s, 6H); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 174.6, 170.1, 158.7, 157.3, 152.6, 152.5, 152.2, 135.1, 129.8, 129.2, 128.9, 126.7, 125.1, 124.2, 115.0, 112.7, 112.4, 110.6, 105.7, 103.1, 79.5, 52.8, 25.4, 25.2; electrospray ionisation (ESI) – high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS): calcd for C₂₅H₂₁O₇ [M + H]⁺: 433.1282, found 433.1278.

For the synthesis of intermediates **7a**, **7b**, **7d** and **7e** the corresponding halogenated anthracene derivatives R_a-Br (9-bromoanthracene), R_b-Br (9-bromo-10-nitroanthracene), R_d-Cl (9-(chloromethoxy)anthracene) and R_e-Cl (9-(chloromethoxy)-2,6-di(*tert*-butyl)anthracene) were used as reactants (Scheme 2). Compound R_a-Br is commercially available. Compound R_b-Br was prepared according to a procedure reported elsewhere.²² Compounds R_d-Cl and R_e-Cl were generated *in situ* from synthetically accessible derivatives R_d-SCH₃ and R_e-SCH₃ by using sulfonyl chloride as outlined in Schemes S1 and S2 in the ESI.[†]

Compound 7a. A suspension of Pd(OAc)₂ (1.25 g, 5.6 mmol), *t*-BuXPhos (2.36 g, 5.6 mmol), and Cs₂CO₃ (9.04 g, 27.8 mmol) in *o*-xylene (15 mL) was stirred at 22 °C for 30 min. 9-Bromoanthracene (1.43 g, 5.5 mmol) and compound **6** (2.40 g, 5.6 mmol) in dioxane (15 mL) were added and the resulting mixture was heated at 110 °C for 18 h. The reaction mixture was quenched with water and the aqueous layer was separated and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 50 mL). The combined organic layers were dried (MgSO₄), filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification of the residue by flash column chromatography (alumina (grade III), eluent – CH₂Cl₂) gave the title compound **7a** as a yellow solid (400 mg, 0.66 mmol, 12%). $R_f = 0.72$ (alumina, eluent – CH₂Cl₂); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 8.43 (s, 1H), 7.98–8.12 (m, 5H), 7.58–7.72 (m, 2H), 7.41–7.55 (m, 4H), 7.20 (d, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.67–6.77 (m, 2H), 6.59–6.67 (m, 1H), 6.45–6.55 (m, 3H), 3.73 (s, 3H), 1.59 (s, 6H); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 174.2, 169.2, 161.6, 157.2, 152.7, 152.6, 151.9, 144.7, 135.0, 132.3, 129.8, 129.5, 128.8, 128.4, 126.8, 126.2, 125.8, 125.0, 124.4, 124.3, 124.1, 122.0, 115.0, 112.5, 112.3, 112.2, 105.5, 103.0, 82.9, 52.7, 25.4, 25.1; ESI-HRMS: calcd for C₃₉H₂₉O₇ [M + H]⁺: 609.1908, found 609.1912.

Probe 4. To a solution of intermediate **7a** (110 mg, 0.18 mmol) in THF (0.58 mL) was added a 1.9 M aqueous solution of LiOH (0.29 mL). The mixture was degassed (3 × freeze/pump/thaw cycles) and stirred at 22 °C overnight. Next, the reaction mixture was quenched with HCl (pH = 2) and the resulting mixture was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 1 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried (MgSO₄), and concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was recrystallized from ethyl acetate/*n*-hexane (5 mL, 2/3, v/v) to give probe **4** as white solid (84 mg, 0.14 mmol, 78%). $R_f = 0.39$ (alumina, 20:1 MeOH/TEA, v/v); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, acetone-d₆) δ (ppm) = 8.61 (s, 1H), 8.15–8.24 (m, 2H), 8.03–8.11 (m, 2H), 7.95–8.02 (m, 1H),

7.70–7.86 (m, 2H), 7.50–7.60 (m, 4H), 7.29–7.37 (m, 1H), 6.59–6.87 (m, 5H), 6.55 (d, $J = 2.5$ Hz, 1H), 1.59 (s, 6H); ¹³C NMR (100.5 MHz, acetone-d₆) δ (ppm) = 175.1, 169.5, 162.7, 158.8, 153.7, 153.5, 152.8, 145.6, 136.5, 133.5, 131.2, 131.0, 129.9, 129.7, 127.9, 127.7, 127.0, 125.7, 125.7, 125.5, 125.2, 122.7, 116.3, 114.4, 113.5, 113.3, 106.3, 103.7, 82.9, 80.2, 25.6; ESI-HRMS: calcd for C₃₈H₂₅O₇ [M – H][–]: 593.1606, found 593.1604. C, H, N analysis: calcd for C₃₈H₂₆O₇: C 76.8%, H 4.4%; found C 77.0%, H 4.2%.

9-Bromo-10-nitroanthracene. A slightly modified literature procedure was used for the synthesis of this compound.²² To a stirred solution of 9-nitroanthracene (4.90 g, 22.0 mmol) in nitromethane (100 mL), bromine (1.12 mL, 22.0 mmol) was added dropwise at 22 °C. The reaction mixture was heated at 50 °C for 2 h. The reaction mixture was quenched slowly with saturated NaHCO₃ solution and the aqueous layer was separated and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (2 × 50 mL). The combined organic layers were dried (MgSO₄), filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification of the residue by flash column chromatography (silica gel, 1:10 CH₂Cl₂/petroleum ether) gave the title compound as a yellow solid (1.28 g, 4.2 mmol, 19%). $R_f = 0.2$ (silica gel, 1:10 CH₂Cl₂/petroleum ether); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 8.53–8.68 (m, 2H), 7.84–7.97 (m, 2H), 7.63–7.73 (m, 4H); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 129.9, 129.0, 128.2, 128.0, 126.4, 122.7, 121.7. Atmospheric pressure photo-ionisation (APPI)-HRMS: calcd for C₁₄H₈⁷⁹BrNO₂ [M]⁺: 300.97384, found 300.97339.

Compound 7b. A mixture of compound **6** (4.64 g, 10.7 mmol), 9-bromo-10-nitroanthracene (4.21 g, 14.0 mmol, 1.3 eq.) and Cs₂CO₃ (5.25 g, 16.1 mmol, 1.5 eq.) in DMF (40 mL) was stirred at 75 °C for 24 h. The reaction mixture was quenched with water and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 50 mL). The combined organic layers were dried (MgSO₄), filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification of the residue by flash column chromatography (silica gel, eluent – CH₂Cl₂) gave the title compound **7b** as a yellow solid (4.02 g, 6.1 mmol, 57%). $R_f = 0.47$ (silica gel, eluent – CH₂Cl₂); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 8.12 (d, $J = 8.85$ Hz, 2H), 7.98–8.07 (m, 3H), 7.59–7.72 (m, 4H), 7.53 (ddd, $J = 0.94, 6.64, 8.81$ Hz, 2H), 7.16–7.25 (m, 1H), 6.69–6.81 (m, 2H), 6.61–6.69 (m, 1H), 6.43–6.58 (m, 3H), 3.74 (s, 3H), 1.59 (s, 6H); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 174.1, 169.1, 160.9, 157.2, 152.6, 152.5, 151.8, 147.3, 142.0, 135.0, 129.8, 129.2, 128.8, 127.0, 126.7, 125.1, 124.0, 123.9, 123.6, 122.4, 121.7, 115.1, 113.3, 112.1, 112.0, 105.4, 103.1, 82.6, 79.4, 52.6, 25.3, 25.1; ESI-HRMS: calcd for C₃₉H₂₈NO₉ [M + H]⁺: 654.1759, found 654.1761.

Probe 8b. Intermediate **7b** (392 mg) was hydrolysed according to the protocol used for the preparation of probe **4**. Probe **8b** was obtained as a brown solid (196 mg, 0.31 mmol, 51%). $R_f = 0.18$ (alumina, 20:1 MeOH/TEA, v/v); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 8.11 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.95–8.07 (m, 3H), 7.59–7.74 (m, 4H), 7.49–7.54 (m, 2H), 7.19 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 1H), 6.70–6.76 (m, 2H), 6.62–6.68 (m, 2H), 6.55–6.60 (m, 1H), 6.53 (d, $J = 2.4$ Hz, 1H), 1.60 (s, 6H); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

δ (ppm) = 178.1, 169.2, 161.0, 156.7, 152.6, 152.5, 151.8, 147.3, 142.0, 135.1, 129.9, 129.9, 129.3, 128.9, 127.0, 126.7, 125.1, 124.0, 123.9, 123.6, 122.4, 121.8, 116.0, 113.3, 112.8, 112.0, 106.7, 103.1, 82.6, 79.4, 25.3, 25.0; ESI-HRMS: calcd for $C_{38}H_{24}NO_9$ $[M - H]^-$: 638.1457, found 638.1471; C, H, N analysis: calcd for $C_{38}H_{25}NO_9$: C 71.3%, H 3.9%, N 2.2%; found C 71.0%, H 4.1%, N 2.0%.

Probe 8c. $SnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (10.0 g, 44.4 mmol) was suspended in acetic anhydride (30 mL) and heated to 80 °C for 30 min. Next, intermediate **7b** (2.9 g, 4.44 mmol) was added and the resulting mixture was heated at 80 °C for 24 h and concentrated *in vacuo*. The resulting solid was suspended in CH_2Cl_2 (200 mL), filtered through a plug of alumina (grade III) and concentrated *in vacuo* to give a brown residue containing intermediate **8d**. We did not manage to purify this intermediate. Therefore, the mixture was directly subjected to hydrolysis. In particular, the brown residue was suspended in THF (4 mL) and 1 M aqueous solution of LiOH (3 mL) was added. The resulting mixture was degassed ($3 \times$ freeze/pump/thaw cycles) and stirred at 22 °C overnight. Next, the reaction mixture was quenched with HCl (pH = 2) and the resulting mixture was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3×20 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried ($MgSO_4$), and concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was dissolved in CH_2Cl_2 (5 mL) and loaded into a small column filled with alumina (grade III). For removing impurities the column was first washed with CH_2Cl_2 (100 mL) and then with methanol (100 mL). The resulting fractions were disposed. Finally the column was washed with 20:1 MeOH/TEA (v/v) and the respective fractions were combined and concentrated *in vacuo*. The resulting white solid was dissolved in CH_2Cl_2 (100 mL) and washed with 0.1 M aq. HCl (15 mL) and water (3×20 mL). The CH_2Cl_2 layer was dried ($MgSO_4$), and concentrated *in vacuo* to give probe **8c** as a brown solid (410 mg, 0.63 mmol, 14% over 2 steps). R_f = 0.52 (alumina, 20:1 MeOH/TEA, v/v); 1H NMR (300 MHz, acetone- d_6) δ (ppm) = 9.56 (s, 1H), 8.23–8.26 (m, 2H), 8.02–8.08 (m, 2H), 7.95–8.02 (m, 1H), 7.67–7.82 (m, 2H), 7.46–7.60 (m, 4H), 7.26 (d, J = 7.35 Hz, 1H), 6.78–6.88 (m, 2H), 6.57–6.73 (m, 3H), 6.48 (m, 1H), 2.42 (s, 3H), 1.55 (s, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, acetone- d_6) δ (ppm) = 175.1, 170.8, 170.7, 169.3, 162.5, 158.7, 153.5, 153.3, 152.6, 144.8, 136.3, 131.0, 130.9, 130.3, 129.6, 129.2, 129.0, 127.7, 127.4, 127.2, 125.6, 125.5, 125.3, 125.0, 122.8, 116.2, 114.3, 113.2, 106.1, 103.6, 82.9, 80.2, 25.7, 25.6, 23.3; ESI-HRMS: calcd for $C_{40}H_{28}NO_8$ $[M - H]^-$: 650.1820, found 650.1827; C, H, N analysis: calcd for $C_{40}H_{29}NO_8$: C 73.7%, H 4.5%, N 2.2%; found C 73.4%, H 4.5%, N 2.3%.

9-(Methylthiomethoxy)anthracene (compound R_d-SCH3). To a solution of anthrone (4.00 g, 20.6 mmol, 1 equiv.) in anhydrous DMSO (100 mL) sodium hydride (60% dispersion in mineral oil) (907 mg, 22.7 mmol, 1.1 eq.) was added in small portions. After stirring for 30 min at 22 °C, CH_3SCH_2Cl (1.72 mL, 1.99 g, 20.6 mmol) was added dropwise resulting in a deep red solution, which was then stirred for 24 h at 22 °C. The reaction mixture was then slowly quenched with water (50 mL). The resulting aqueous mixture

was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3×50 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried ($MgSO_4$), and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification of the residue by flash column chromatography (silica gel, from 1:9 to 2:8 CH_2Cl_2 /i-hexane, v/v) gave the title compound as a white solid (367 mg, 1.44 mmol, 7%). R_f = 0.42 (silica gel, 2:8 CH_2Cl_2 /i-hexane); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 8.35 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H); 8.25 (s, 1H); 7.93–8.04 (m, 2H); 7.42–7.56 (m, 4H), 5.39 (s, 2H), 2.38 (s, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 150.0, 132.3, 128.3, 125.5, 125.3, 124.8, 122.8, 122.5, 80.2, 16.0; ESI-HRMS: calcd for $C_{16}H_{14}OSNa$ $[M + Na]^+$: 277.0663, found 277.0670.

Probe 8d. Sulfuryl chloride (381 μ L, 637 mg, 4.7 mmol) was dissolved in 50 mL of anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 . Next the solution was ice cooled and 9-(methylthiomethoxy)anthracene (1.20 g, 4.7 mmol) was added. The resulting yellow reaction solution was stirred for 1 h at 22 °C and then the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The black residue was dissolved in anhydrous DMF (2 mL) and added rapidly to a solution obtained by stirring compound **6** (2.04 g, 4.7 mmol) and *t*-BuOK (530 mg, 1.0 eq.) dissolved in anhydrous DMF (20 mL) for 1 h. The resulting solution was then stirred for 24 h at 22 °C and slowly quenched with water (50 mL). Next 20 mL of CH_2Cl_2 was added, the layers were separated, and the aqueous layer was further extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3×50 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried ($MgSO_4$), and concentrated *in vacuo*. To the resulting residue, THF (4 mL) was added followed by the addition of 1 M aqueous solution of LiOH (3 mL). The mixture was degassed ($3 \times$ freeze/pump/thaw cycles) and stirred at 22 °C overnight. Next, the reaction mixture was quenched with HCl (pH = 2) and the resulting mixture was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3×20 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried ($MgSO_4$), and concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was dissolved in CH_2Cl_2 (5 mL) and loaded into a small column filled with alumina grade III. For removing impurities, the column was first washed with CH_2Cl_2 (100 mL) and then with methanol (100 mL). The resulting fractions were disposed. Finally, the column was washed with 20:1 MeOH/TEA (v/v) and the respective fractions were combined and concentrated *in vacuo*. The resulting white solid was dissolved in CH_2Cl_2 (100 mL) and washed with 0.1 M aq. HCl (15 mL) and water (3×20 mL). The CH_2Cl_2 layer was dried ($MgSO_4$), and concentrated *in vacuo* to give the title compound as a brown solid (63 mg, 0.10 mmol, 2% over 2 steps). R_f = 0.12 (alumina, 20:1 MeOH/TEA, v/v); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 8.29 (s, 1H); 8.12–8.21 (m, 2H), 7.96–8.09 (m, 3H), 7.60–7.75 (m, 2H), 7.38–7.52 (m, 4H), 7.20–7.26 (m, 2H), 6.86–6.91 (m, 2H), 6.77–6.83 (m, 1H), 6.70–6.77 (m, 1H), 6.65 (dd, J = 2.4, 9.0 Hz, 1H), 5.93 (s, 2H), 1.68 (s, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) = 177.6, 169.4, 159.1, 156.7, 152.9, 152.4, 152.0, 149.6, 135.1, 132.1, 129.8, 129.4, 128.9, 128.2, 126.7, 125.7, 125.5, 125.1, 124.6, 124.0, 123.4, 122.3, 115.8, 113.0, 112.9, 112.8, 106.9, 103.6, 96.4, 82.9, 79.6, 25.3, 25.1; ESI-HRMS: calcd for $C_{39}H_{27}O_8$ $[M - H]^-$: 623.1711, found 623.1720; C, H, N analysis: calcd for $C_{39}H_{28}O_8$: C 75.0%, H 4.5%; found C 75.4%, H 4.4%.

2,6-Di-*tert*-butyl-9-(methylthiomethoxy)anthracene. To a solution of 2,6-di-*tert*-butylanthrone²³ (11.7 g, 38.1 mmol) in anhydrous DMSO (300 mL) sodium hydride (60% dispersion in mineral oil) (1.68 g, 41.9 mmol, 1.1 eq.) was added in small portions. After stirring for 30 min at 22 °C, CH₃SCH₂Cl (3.19 mL, 3.68 g, 38.1 mmol) was added dropwise to obtain a deep red solution, which was stirred for 24 h at 22 °C. The red reaction solution was then slowly quenched with water (150 mL), the layers were separated, and the aqueous layer was further extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 75 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried (MgSO₄), and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification of the residue by flash column chromatography (silica gel, from 1 : 9 to 2 : 8 CH₂Cl₂/*i*-hexane, v/v) gave the title compound as a white solid (730 mg, 2.0 mmol, 5%). *R*_f = 0.26 (silica gel, 1 : 4 CH₂Cl₂/*i*-hexane, v/v); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 8.25–8.34 (m, 2H); 8.20 (s, 1H); 7.87–7.99 (m, 2H); 7.54–7.67 (m, 2H), 5.42 (s, 2H); 2.47 (s, 3H); 1.50 (s, 9H), 1.49 (s, 9H); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 149.8; (2 × 147.4), 132.2, 131.1, 128.0, 124.9, 124.8, 124.4, 123.3, 122.6, 122.2, 122.1, 116.7, 79.9, 35.2, 34.9, 31.0, 30.9, 16.0; ESI-HRMS: calcd for C₂₄H₃₀NaOS [M + Na]⁺: 389 1910, found 389.1903.

Compound 7e. To an ice cold solution of 2,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9-(methylthiomethoxy)anthracene (655 mg, 1.8 mmol) in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (25 mL) was added sulfonyl chloride (145 μL, 243 mg, 1.8 mmol). The resulting yellow solution was stirred for 1 h at 22 °C and then the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The black residue was dissolved in anhydrous DMF (3 mL) and added rapidly to a solution obtained from stirring for 1 h compound **6** (778 mg, 1.8 mmol) and *t*-BuOK (202 mg, 1.8 mmol) in anhydrous DMF (7 mL). The resulting solution was then stirred for 24 h at 22 °C and slowly quenched with water (50 mL). Next, 20 mL of CH₂Cl₂ was added, the layers were separated, and the aqueous layer was further extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 50 mL). The organic layers were combined, dried (MgSO₄), and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification of the residue by flash column chromatography (alumina, from 9 : 1 to 8 : 2 *i*-hexane/ethyl acetate, v/v) gave the title compound as a brown oil (143 mg, 0.2 mmol, 11%). *R*_f = 0.38 (8 : 2 *i*-hexane/ethyl acetate, v/v); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 8.38–8.45 (m, 2H), 8.14 (d, *J* = 9.23 Hz, 1H), 8.01–8.10 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.78 (m, 4H), 7.31 (d, *J* = 2.45 Hz, 1H), 7.19–7.26 (m, 1H), 6.86–6.95 (m, 1H), 6.79–6.82 (m, 1H), 6.67–6.76 (m, 2H), 6.51–6.61 (m, 1H), 5.95 (s, 2H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 1.66 (s, 6H), 1.49 (s, 9H), 1.24 (s, 9H); ¹³C NMR (100.6 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 174.3, 169.3, 159.1, 157.3, 152.9, 152.6, 152.1, 149.2, 148.6, 148.2, 135.0, 133.4, 131.4, 131.2, 129.8, 129.5, 128.9, 127.9, 127.3, 126.8, 126.5, 125.6, 125.3, 125.1, 124.5, 124.5, 124.0, 123.9, 123.4, 122.1, 119.4, 117.0, 115.0, 113.1, 112.8, 112.4, 105.8, 103.5, 96.4, 82.8, 79.5, 52.7, 35.3, 35.0, 30.9, 30.6, 25.4, 25.3; APPI-HRMS: calcd for C₄₈H₄₅ClO₈ [M]⁺: 784.2803, found 784.28162.

Probe 8e. Probe **8e** was obtained by the hydrolysis of intermediate **7e** (143 mg, 0.18 mmol) analogously to the preparation of probe **4**. The title compound was obtained as a brown solid (21 mg, 0.03 mmol, 15%). *R*_f = 0.13 (20 : 1 MeOH/TEA,

v/v); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) δ (ppm) = 8.36–8.45 (m, 2H), 8.29 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 1H), 8.15 (d, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.01–8.06 (m, 1H), 7.84–7.93 (m, 1H), 7.72–7.84 (m, 3H), 7.27–7.41 (m, 2H), 7.00 (dd, *J* = 2.5, 8.8 Hz, 1H), 6.90 (d, *J* = 8.67 Hz, 1H), 6.76–6.86 (m, 2H), 6.67–6.76 (m, 1H), 6.10–6.23 (m, 2H), 1.65 (s, 6H), 1.48 (s, 9H), 1.22 (s, 9H); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) δ (ppm) = 169.5, 160.1, 158.8, 153.9, 153.6, 152.9, 150.8, 150.0, 149.3, 136.3, 131.1, 130.7, 2 × 129.9, 128.9, 128.0, 127.8, 126.7, 126.5, 125.7, 2 × 125.1, 124.5, 124.4, 123.6, 119.8, 118.4, 116.5, 114.6, 113.9, 113.7, 106.5, 104.3, 97.4, 83.0, 80.4, 36.1, 35.7, 3 × 31.2, 3 × 31.1, 25.8, 25.7. The signal for carboxyl carbon was not detected in the spectrum; ESI-HRMS: calcd for C₄₇H₄₂ClO₈ [M – H][–]: 769.2574, found 769.2591; C, H, N analysis: calcd for C₄₇H₄₃ClO₈: C 73.2%, H 5.6%; found C 73.0%, H 5.3%.

Monitoring the fluorogenic response of ¹O₂ probes in cell free settings in the presence of different reactive oxygen species (typical procedures)

“Singlet oxygen” test. The solutions were pipetted into a cuvette in the following order: water (867 μL), 1 M phosphate buffer (100 μL, pH 7.4), 5 M NaCl (30 μL), 1.6 mM probe **8d** in DMF (1.3 μL) and 487 μM In³⁺ (pyropheophorbide-*a*)chloride (InPpa) in DMF (1 μL). Final concentrations were as follows: 100 mM phosphate buffer; 150 mM NaCl; 2 μM **8d**; 0.5 μM InPpa; 0.3% DMF (v/v). The cuvette was closed by using a Teflon® cap and the fluorescence of the solution was measured (λ_{ex} = 495 nm, λ_{em} = 515 nm; *F*₀). The cuvette was irradiated for 60 min with LED Array 672 (λ_{max} = 650 nm) in a paper cardboard box covered with aluminum foil to induce ¹O₂ production catalysed by InPpa. Next, the cuvette was removed from the cardboard box and the fluorescence of the solution was measured (λ_{ex} = 495 nm, λ_{em} = 515 nm; *F*₆₀). The same experiment was repeated in the absence of the photocatalyst (InPpa) to evaluate the possibility of direct probe activation by red light.

“Hydrogen peroxide” test. The solution of probe **8d** (2 μM) in phosphate buffer (100 mM) containing NaCl (150 mM) and DMF (0.3%, v/v) was prepared as described above (“singlet oxygen” test). H₂O₂ (final concentration: 10 mM) was added and the fluorescence of the resulting solution was measured (λ_{ex} = 495 nm, λ_{em} = 515 nm) immediately after H₂O₂ addition (*F*₀) and after 60 min incubation at 22 °C (*F*₆₀).

“Superoxide anion radicals” test. This experiment was conducted similar to the “hydrogen peroxide” test, except that a mixture of xanthine (33 mM) and xanthine oxidase (4 units per L) was added in place of H₂O₂. The preparation of a stock solution of xanthine oxidase (100 units per L): xanthine oxidase (lyophilised powder, 3.57 mg, 5 units) was dissolved in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer (1000 μL) at pH 7.4 which contained 1% DMF (v/v).

“Hydroxyl radicals” test. This experiment was conducted similar to the “hydrogen peroxide” test, except that FeSO₄ (0.6 mM) was also added to convert H₂O₂ to HO[•]. The same experiment was repeated in the absence of H₂O₂ to evaluate

the direct effect of Fe²⁺ ions on the activation of the probes. Furthermore, Fe²⁺ ions in the latter experiment were replaced with the same amounts of other bioavailable metal ions including K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ to evaluate their possible effects on the ¹O₂ probes. We did not observe fluorogenic response of the new chemodosimeters in any of these cases.

Cellular assays

The human promyelocytic leukemia cell line (HL-60) was cultured in Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 medium supplemented with 10% FCS and 5 μg mL⁻¹ penicillin/streptomycin (all media and supplements from Gibco Invitrogen Corp., Karlsruhe, Germany).

Monitoring the formation of ¹O₂ in live HL-60 cells by flow cytometry. The cells, grown as described above, were centrifuged, and the medium was replaced with RPMI 1640 medium (5% FCS, 1% L-glutamine, 1% penicillin/streptomycin) to obtain suspensions containing 10⁶ cells per mL. Stock solutions (1 μL) of probe **8d** (5 and 50 μM in DMF) and InPpa (100 μM) were added to the cellular suspensions (500 μL). After incubation for 20 min, washing of the cells with the medium and their resuspension in fresh medium, the cells were irradiated with red light (LED Array 672, λ_{max} = 650 nm; time = 0, 2, 5, 10, 15 and 20 min) to induce the production of ¹O₂. Intracellular activation of the probe was monitored by using flow cytometry: λ_{ex} = 488 nm, λ_{em} = 515–540 nm (FL1 channel).

Determination of cytotoxicity of ¹O₂ probes towards HL-60 cells. The cells, grown as described above, were centrifuged, and the medium was replaced with RPMI 1640 medium (5% FCS, 1% L-glutamine, 1% penicillin/streptomycin) to obtain suspensions containing 10⁶ cells per mL. Stock solutions (5 μL) of compound **8d** (0.1, 1, 10 and 100 μM in DMF) were added to the cellular suspensions (500 μL) and incubated for 48 h. At the end of the incubation period propidium iodide (PI, 1 μL, 1.5 mM in water) was added to label dead cells and in 5 min the suspension of the cells was analysed by using flow cytometry: λ_{ex} = 488 nm, λ_{em} = 570–606 nm (FL2 channel). Viable cells remain PI-negative: no signal detected in the FL2 channel. Four replicates were tested for each concentration of the prodrug. Three independent experiments were conducted to confirm the effect of the probes on the viability of HL-60 cells.

Conclusions

We developed the synthesis of a series of fluorescein derivatives coupled to 9-anthracenyl fragments and have shown that some of these compounds (**4**, **8d**, **8e**) exhibit excellent fluorogenic response in the presence of ¹O₂ in cell-free settings exceeding in the best case 20-fold. We found that these new chemodosimeters are ¹O₂ specific (as compared to red light irradiation, H₂O₂, O₂^{•-} and HO[•]). Finally, the selected compound **8d** was found to be non-toxic to human promyelo-

cytic leukemia HL-60 cells at concentrations below 1 μM (higher concentrations were not tested) even at long incubation times (≤48 h) and retain its ability to detect ¹O₂ in live HL-60 cells.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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Supporting Information

Hybrids of a 9-anthracenyl moiety and fluorescein as chemodosimeters for detection of singlet oxygen in live cells

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Outline of synthesis of probes **8d** and **8e**

Scheme S1. Synthesis of probe **8d**: a) chloromethyl methyl sulfide, NaH, DMSO, rt, 24 h, 7%; (b) SO₂Cl₂, CH₂Cl₂, 22 °C, 1 h; (c) compound **6**, *t*-BuOK, DMF, rt, 24 h; d) LiOH, H₂O/THF, 22 °C, 24 h, (2% over 2 steps).

Scheme S2. Synthesis of probe **8e**: (a) according to (1). Whitton, A. J.; Kumberger, O.; Müller, G.; Schmidbaur, H. *Chem. Ber.* **1990**, *123*, 1931-1939 and (2) Whitton, A. J.; Kumberger, O.; Müller, G.; Schmidbaur, H. *Chem. Ber.* **1990**, *123*, 1931-1939: *t*-BuCl, AlCl₃, CHCl₃, reflux, 24 h, 34%; (b) according to U. Müller, V. Enkelmann, M. Adam and K. Müllen, *Chemische Berichte* **1993**, *126*, 1217-1225: (NH₄)₂Ce(NO₃)₆, THF/H₂O, rt, 2 h, 64%; (c) according to Müller, U.; Enkelmann, V.; Adam, M.; Müllen, K. *Chem. Ber.* **1993**, *126*, 1217-1225 and Müller, U.; Enkelmann, V.; Adam, M.; Müllen, K. *Chem. Ber.* **1993**, *126*, 1217-1225: Sn, AcOH, HCl, 81%; (d) Chloromethyl methyl sulfide, NaH, DMSO, rt, 18 h, 5%; (e) SO₂Cl₂, CH₂Cl₂, rt, 1 h; (f) compound **6**, *t*-BuOK, DMF, rt, 24 h, 11%; (g) LiOH, H₂O/THF, rt, 24 h, 15%.

NMR spectra of intermediates and new singlet oxygen probes **4**, **8b-8e**

Figure S1. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **6**.

Figure S2. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **6**.

Figure S3. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **7a**.

Figure S4. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **7a**.

Figure S5. ^1H NMR spectrum of probe 4.

Figure S6. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of probe 4.

Figure S7. ^1H NMR spectrum of 9-bromo-10-nitroanthracene.

Figure S8. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 9-bromo-10-nitroanthracene.

Figure S9. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **7b**.

Figure S10. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **7b**.

Figure S11. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **8b**.

Figure S12. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **8b**.

Figure S13. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **8c**.

Figure S14. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **8c**.

Figure S15. ^1H NMR spectrum of 9-(methylthiomethoxy)anthracene.

Figure S16. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 9-(methylthiomethoxy)anthracene.

Figure S17. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **8d**.

Figure S18. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **8d**.

Figure S21. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **7e**.

Figure S22. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **7e**.

Figure S23. ^1H NMR spectrum of probe **8e**.

Figure S24. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of probe **8e**.

Calculation of energies of highest occupied orbitals (HOMOs) of simple models mimicking probes **4**, **8a-e**

Geometry optimizations were performed using the B3LYP¹ hybrid density functional and the 6-31G**²⁻¹¹ basis set with Gaussian16.¹² Frequency calculations of the optimized structures were used to confirm stationary points (minima). Checkpoint files were converted to formatted checkpoint files using the formchk command and cube files containing MO data were obtained with the cubegen command from the Gaussian suite. Visualization of the HOMO isosurfaces was performed with vmd 1.9.3,^{13, 14} using orbital isovalues of -0.02 (yellow) and 0.02 (blue).

Table S1.

Gaussian 16 (B3LYP/6-31G**)				
Probe	Model structure	HOMO energy [eV]	HOMO	Relative HOMO-energies [eV]
Reference		reference, E=0		
8e		-0.43		
8d		-0.43		

4		-0.50		
8c		-0.51		
8b		-1.01		

Intensity of green color in the last column of this table indicates the reactivity of the corresponding anthracene derivative with $^1\text{O}_2$ as predicted based on energies of the HOMOs.

Figure **S25**. ¹H NMR spectroscopic monitoring conversion of probe **4** (5 mM) to anthraquinone **AQ** in the presence of photochemically generated ¹O₂. ¹O₂ was generated upon irradiation of photosensitizer pyropheophorbide a (Ppa, 0.1 eq, 0.5 mM) with red light (650 nm) for 1 h and 14 h. Spectrum of reference compound **AQ** is shown as a red trace. Peaks of **AQ** appearing upon the transformation of probe **4** are indicated with dotted, black lines.

Figure **S26**. Fluorescence microscopy images combined with optical image of DU-145 cells before (left column) and after (right column) irradiation under red channel. A: Cells treated with a carrier DMF; B: Cells treated with probe **4** (1 μM); C: Cells treated with InPpa (0.1 μM); C: Cells treated with probe **4** (1 μM) and InPpa (0.1 μM).

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